

EU ETS2 and Social Climate Fund: Enabling decarbonisation in transport and buildings that works for all

Authors:

Annabel Vella (VITO), Inge Mayeres (TML), Odysseas Platsakis (Exergia), Ruken Karakus Acipinar (VITO), Tom Dauwe (VITO), Dimitris Sarantaridis (Exergia), Sabine Gores (Öko-Institut), Reena Skribbe (Öko-Institut)

EEA project managers:

Melanie Sporer, Stéphane Quefelec

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<https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-cm>
etccm@vito.be

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Executive summary

This report focuses on the extension of the EU Emissions Trading System (EU ETS) to fuels used in road transport and buildings, hereinafter referred to as EU ETS2, together with the design and implementation of the Social Climate Fund. It covers emission trends and underlying drivers in the road transport and buildings sectors, the functioning and regulatory architecture of the EU ETS2¹, the cap and compliance processes, and the mechanisms that support price stability and fairness. The assessment also explores how auctioning revenues are intended to finance climate and social objectives and how the EU ETS2 interacts with wider EU legislation on energy efficiency, renewable energy, buildings performance, vehicle standards and funding instruments. The report delves into distributional impacts across and within Member States, examining indicators of energy and transport poverty, structural drivers of vulnerability and the potential effects of carbon pricing on households, transport users and micro-enterprises. It also reviews the wide range of decarbonisation measures available to end users in transport and buildings, including behavioural, technological and structural options, and the enabling conditions required for their adoption.

Emissions Context and the Need for Accelerated Action

Greenhouse gas emissions from road transport and buildings remain among the most persistent and challenging sources of emissions in the EU. Road transport emissions have shown limited progress since 2005, remaining broadly stable or only slightly declining despite policy efforts. Recent greenhouse gas emissions from road transport continue to reflect a complex interaction between rising travel demand and technological progress. Increasing passenger kilometres have kept overall emissions high, yet several policy driven factors have mitigated growth. The energy efficiency of cars has improved substantially, an effect that became more pronounced after the introduction of mandatory CO₂ standards for new vehicles in 2009. A higher share of biofuels has also contributed to lowering emissions, supported by EU level mandates, with these fuels being considered carbon neutral within the greenhouse gas inventory framework. In recent years, electrification has begun to influence emissions, although its overall contribution remains modest up to now. As a result, to date efficiency improvements and biofuel uptake have played a greater role in shaping emission trends than fleet electrification.

Emissions from buildings have declined since 2005, but progress has been uneven across Member States and strongly influenced by climate conditions, fuel prices, and the pace of renovation. The long-term downward trend reflects improvements in building energy performance, gradual uptake of more efficient heating systems, and a shift away from the most carbon intensive fuels. Warmer winters in several years further reduced heating demand, contributing to short term fluctuations in emissions. Despite these reductions, many countries continue to rely heavily on natural gas and heating oil, while a large share of the building stock remains poorly insulated and in need of deep renovation. Renovation rates continue to fall short of levels required to meet long term climate targets, and energy demand for heating remains high in older, inefficient buildings. As a result, although emissions have decreased since 2005, the buildings

¹ In November 2025, Member States reached an agreement on a General Approach on the Climate Law, confirmed by the EP plenary vote, which foresees the postponement of the application of the EU ETS2 by one year, to 2028. The Commission, meanwhile, is delivering on a proposal for a buffer mechanism as part of a bigger package addressing Member States' concerns about future carbon-price levels and volatility, and to help accelerate investments ahead of the launch of the ETS2 market, as announced at the ENVI Council in October 2025 (EC, 2025a).

This report was drafted before these recent developments were concluded and therefore refers to the functioning of EU ETS2 and Social Climate Fund as set out in the current ETS Directive (EU, 2023b) and Social Climate Fund Regulation (EU, 2023a).

sector retains substantial decarbonisation potential, requiring sustained improvements in renovation depth, heating electrification and clean heat infrastructure.

The EU ETS2 and the Social Climate Fund: Structure, Scope and Functioning

The EU ETS2 establishes a cap-and-trade system for fuels used in buildings, road transport and additional sectors, with a declining cap designed to align these sectors with EU climate objectives. The EU ETS2 was initially scheduled to become fully operational in 2027, with a possible delay of one year in case of exceptionally high oil or gas prices. In November 2025, the European Council, supported by the European Parliament, agreed to delay the start of the system to 2028 (European Parliament, 2025) to ensure a smoother implementation and policy coordination. Although no further changes are expected, trilogue discussions and the formal adoption of this legislative change are still outstanding.

Under the EU ETS2, fuel suppliers are required to obtain and surrender allowances corresponding to the emissions of the fuels they market to the sectors covered by the EU ETS2. All allowances are auctioned, with revenues directed to Member States, both directly and via the Social Climate Fund. A dedicated Market Stability Reserve (MSR), hereinafter referred to as MSR2, regulates the supply of allowances to limit excessive price fluctuations. The compliance architecture requires regulated entities to hold a CO₂ permit by 2025, to report emissions annually and, from 2028 onward, to surrender allowances covering verified emissions. Penalties for non-compliance follow the structure of the existing EU ETS. Provisions for fairness require that auctioning revenues support climate and social measures, including investments in energy efficiency, clean mobility and protection of vulnerable groups.

The Social Climate Fund is a central pillar accompanying the EU ETS2. It is designed to mitigate distributional impacts arising from carbon pricing by financing long-term structural measures that reduce fossil fuel consumption in transport and buildings. Optionally, Member States can also finance temporary income support with a limited share of the total cost of their Social Climate Plan. The Fund supports investments such as building renovation, clean and efficient heating systems, access to zero- and low-emission transport options, and the development of public transport and shared mobility services. The Fund is distributed to EU Member States according to a predefined allocation formula reflecting factors such as population, income levels and the expected impact of carbon pricing on households and micro-enterprises. These national allocations finance the measures set out in each country's Social Climate Plan, which defines eligible groups, specifies the interventions to be funded and outlines how the support will address both short-term affordability challenges and longer-term decarbonisation needs. Through this structure, the Social Climate Fund aims to ensure that resources raised through the EU ETS2 are channelled into measures designed and implemented by Member States to support a fair and inclusive transition.

Coherence with the Wider EU Policy Framework

The EU ETS2 operates within a broader policy architecture that includes horizontal legislation and sector specific measures for energy efficiency, renewable energy, buildings and transport. Its price signal complements the Energy Efficiency Directive and the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive, which drive reductions in energy demand and improvements in building performance. The Renewable Energy Directive supports the shift to cleaner heating sources, including heat pumps and renewable based district heating, while the Energy Taxation Directive influences price incentives for fuel use. In transport, the CO₂ emission performance standards for new vehicles set increasingly stringent fleetwide targets that accelerate the penetration of zero emission vehicles. Complementary sustainable transport policies, including the Alternative Fuels Infrastructure Regulation, TEN-T development, and modal shift objectives, create the structural conditions for reducing fossil fuel dependence. EU funding programmes such as the Recovery and Resilience Facility, Cohesion Policy funds, LIFE and InvestEU provide financial instruments that enable Member States to implement measures aligned with ETS2-driven incentives. The resulting policy mix ensures that carbon pricing interacts with regulatory and financial measures in a mutually

reinforcing way, supporting cost effective emission reductions while expanding access to clean energy and mobility solutions.

Price Dynamics and Expected Impacts

Allowance prices in the EU ETS2 will be shaped by a range of structural and policy related factors that influence fuel demand in buildings and road transport. Key drivers include changes in energy consumption, the rate of energy efficiency improvements, the uptake of heat pumps and zero emission vehicles and broader developments in energy markets and macroeconomic conditions. Interactions with other EU legislation, such as energy efficiency and renewable energy requirements and CO₂ emission standards for vehicles, will also influence the demand for emission allowances over time. The declining cap and the MSR2 provide mechanisms that adjust allowance supply and help stabilise prices, reducing the likelihood of sustained volatility.

Model based assessments indicate that the EU ETS2 can deliver significant emissions reductions when combined with the wider EU policy framework. The carbon price signal is expected to encourage lower fossil fuel consumption, accelerate renovation and clean heating deployment and support the transition to zero emission mobility. The scale of these reductions will depend on the speed of technology uptake, the effectiveness of complementary legislation and the enabling role of financial support. When supported by the Social Climate Fund and other EU financing instruments, the EU ETS2 is projected to contribute meaningfully to achieving the EU's 2030 climate targets.

Socio-economic Vulnerability and Distributional Patterns

Households and transport users experience the impacts of carbon pricing unevenly, depending on income, housing conditions, heating systems, mobility needs and access to affordable alternatives. Indicators from self-reported surveys and household budget data show large differences in energy and transport affordability across the EU, with many households struggling to cover utility bills, maintain adequate warmth or access essential mobility. Structural factors, such as poor building performance, car dependence, limited public transport options and restricted access to capital, intensify exposure to higher fuel costs. Weather conditions further influence vulnerability, as colder climates and longer heating seasons increase household sensitivity to changes in heating fuel prices. Differences in settlement patterns, commuting distances and availability of low-cost mobility alternatives reinforce these unequal conditions and shape the scale of support required to ensure a fair transition.

Differences across Member States are particularly pronounced. Arrears on utility bills range from less than 2% in some countries to more than 30% in others. The share of the population reporting inadequate warmth varies equally widely, while affordability constraints for car ownership are significant in several lower income Member States. These disparities demonstrate that a uniform carbon price interacts with very heterogeneous socio-economic conditions, making targeted support essential for ensuring fairness. Beyond income effects, structural factors shape vulnerability. Regions with limited public transport, dispersed settlement patterns and long commuting distances are more exposed to rising transport fuel costs. Buildings with poor thermal performance require much higher energy inputs to maintain adequate comfort, amplifying cost impacts. Renters face split incentives that hinder investment in energy improvements, while micro-enterprises often lack access to capital for clean technology upgrades.

Decarbonisation Options in Road Transport

The Avoid–Shift–Improve framework provides a structured approach to reducing emissions from road transport by lowering the need for travel, encouraging cleaner modes and improving the efficiency and carbon intensity of vehicles and fuels.

Avoid options reduce the demand for motorised travel by influencing travel behaviour and logistics. Teleworking and digital meetings reduce commuting needs, while trip consolidation lowers vehicle kilometres by combining errands and deliveries. Improved logistics planning, such as optimising delivery frequency, routing and/or consolidation centres, decreases freight kilometres travelled. Over the longer term, land use planning measures and the increased availability of local services can reduce the need for long distance commuting and enhance accessibility without additional transport demand.

Shift options support the movement of passengers and freight toward lower carbon or more efficient modes. Increasing the availability, frequency and quality of public transport enables substitution away from private cars, especially in urban areas. Investment in cycling and walking infrastructure facilitates the shift to active mobility. Carpooling, ride sharing and shared mobility services broaden access to mobility without requiring individual vehicle ownership. For freight, shifting goods from road to rail or inland waterways can substantially reduce emissions, especially for long distance transport. These options require supportive infrastructure, operational planning and, in many cases, targeted investment to ensure high service quality and accessibility.

Improve options enhance the efficiency and carbon performance of vehicles and fuels. Strengthening vehicle efficiency standards accelerates improvements in internal combustion engine vehicles during fleet turnover. Electrification through battery electric and plug-in hybrid vehicles reduces tailpipe emissions, while further electrification of vans and, increasingly, heavier vehicles will amplify these benefits. Renewable and low carbon fuels, including advanced biofuels and synthetic fuels, can reduce emissions in segments where electrification remains limited in the near term. Behavioural measures such as eco-driving, vehicle maintenance, route optimisation tools, or low resistance tyres yield additional short-term reductions. Vehicle add-ons, such as aerodynamic kits for freight vehicles, and digital tools that improve fleet management may further enhance overall system efficiency.

Decarbonisation Options in Buildings

Decarbonisation in buildings can also be structured according to the avoid, shift, improve framework. **Avoid options** focus on reducing energy demand by preventing heat loss and lowering the need for space heating. This includes insulation of walls, roofs and floors, improved glazing, airtightness measures and the adoption of energy efficient building designs. Renovation passports and energy performance certificates support these actions by guiding households toward staged renovation pathways and reducing informational barriers.

Shift options involve transitioning away from fossil-based heating technologies toward low carbon and renewable alternatives. This includes replacing oil and gas boilers with heat pumps, connecting buildings to renewable based district heating networks and enabling community level renewable heat solutions. Electrification of heating supported by decarbonised electricity supply, as well as the uptake of solar thermal and other renewable sources, shifts energy use toward cleaner systems and reduces reliance on fossil fuels.

Improve options target the performance of existing systems through more efficient technologies and behavioural measures. These include upgrading to high efficiency boilers where immediate replacement with low carbon alternatives is not yet feasible, improving the efficiency of distribution systems within buildings, installing smart controls and thermostats and adopting energy saving behaviours. Additional improvements arise from the use of efficient appliances, enhanced ventilation systems and modernised energy management solutions. Together, these avoid, shift and improve measures provide a comprehensive pathway for lowering emissions from the building stock in both the short and long term.

Financing, Investment Needs and Enabling Policies

Financing instruments play a crucial role in supporting building renovation and clean mobility. Grants, subsidies and zero interest loans reduce the upfront cost of high investment measures, particularly for low-income households. Tax incentives, such as reduced value added tax rates on renovation works or tax credits for low carbon technologies, broaden affordability. Innovative models, including pay as you save schemes and heat pump leasing arrangements, allow households to spread costs over time and repay investments through energy savings, lowering financial barriers to adoption.

EU level funding further strengthens national efforts. Resources from the Social Climate Fund, the Recovery and Resilience Facility, Cohesion Policy funds, LIFE, InvestEU and EIB financing can be combined to support large scale renovation programmes, district heating expansion, heat pump deployment and improvements in public transport and active mobility infrastructure. Effective coordination with national planning frameworks and adequate administrative capacity are essential to ensure that these instruments are used efficiently and reach intended beneficiaries.

Complementary and enabling actions are equally important for ensuring that households and transport users can adopt low carbon options. Strengthened advisory services, one stop shops and technical assistance provide guidance for renovation planning and clean heating installation, while simplified procedures and well targeted support schemes improve access to finance. Investments in public transport, active mobility and alternative fuel infrastructure expand the availability of low emission mobility choices. Capacity building for local authorities and service providers, together with skills development and training programmes, helps ensure that the workforce is equipped to deliver renovations, install clean heating technologies and support sustainable mobility solutions. These enabling conditions help remove financial, informational and administrative barriers and allow the incentives created by the EU ETS2 to translate into real behavioural and technological change.

Fairness and the Social Climate Fund

The Social Climate Fund provides a key mechanism to ensure that the introduction of carbon pricing in buildings and road transport does not disproportionately affect vulnerable households, transport users and micro-enterprises. Its resources finance structural investments that help reduce reliance on fossil fuels over time, together with the option of providing temporary income support.

The Social Climate Plans are the central implementation tools of the Fund. They are prepared by Member States and must outline how each country will use its allocated Social Climate Fund resources. These Plans identify national patterns of vulnerability, define the groups eligible for support and present a coherent package of measures that both mitigate short-term impacts from higher fuel prices and enable longer-term shifts toward cleaner heating and mobility solutions. They must be aligned with National Energy and Climate Plans and other relevant EU legislation to ensure consistency across policy areas. The Plans must also demonstrate transparent and credible use of revenues, reflecting evidence that clear communication of carbon revenue allocation is essential for public acceptance. Member States are required to conduct public consultation and engage with local authorities and civil society to ensure that proposed measures reflect national and regional needs. The Fund can additionally support capacity building, monitoring and communication efforts, which strengthen administrative implementation and help households and micro-enterprises navigate available support. Through these combined measures, the Social Climate Fund plays a central role in ensuring that the transition enabled by the EU ETS2 is both environmentally effective and socially fair.

A Fair and Effective Pathway to Climate Neutrality

A successful transition in buildings and road transport can be supported by a range of mutually reinforcing approaches that combine carbon pricing with regulatory measures, accessible finance, targeted social support and sustained investment. The EU ETS2 provides a robust price signal to reduce emissions, while the Social Climate Fund and national policies help ensure that vulnerable groups are protected from disproportionate impacts. Large scale investments in public transport, building renovation, clean heating technologies and local energy systems create the structural conditions for households and transport users to move away from fossil fuels. Ensuring that clean alternatives are available, affordable and accessible across the EU is essential for meeting climate targets and strengthening social resilience. When supported by social measures, transparent use of revenues and well targeted investments, the EU ETS2 can drive deep emissions reductions in sectors that are central to Europe's climate transition.

1. Introduction

The EU Emissions Trading System (EU ETS) is one of Europe’s flagship climate policy instruments, designed to reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions effectively and efficiently. Set up in 2005, it was the first international cap-and-trade system. Since then, the EU ETS has undergone several important changes and improvements. The EU ETS has proven to be very effective in reducing GHG emissions (ETC CM, 2024) and as a result, there has been a continuous trend to increase the scope of this mechanism, from installations in the energy sector and manufacturing industry to aircraft operators and emissions from maritime transport. The EU ETS can be seen as a prominent example of the finding by Stechemester et al. (2024) on “the important role of price-based instruments in well-designed policy mixes and the policy efforts necessary for closing the emissions gap.”

In 2021, the European Commission proposed a more extensive update of the EU ETS to accommodate the higher ambition level for emission reductions by 2030 (EC, 2021a). This included, among other elements, the extension of the EU ETS to road transport, buildings and small industries, which were not covered under the existing EU ETS². This report focuses on this latest extension, particularly the road transport and buildings sectors, hereinafter referred to as EU ETS2. In contrast to other sectors, the overall GHG emissions in the road transport sector increased from 1990 until their peak in 2007, with only a modest decrease since then. In the buildings sector, emissions have seen a substantial and accelerating decrease over the last decades, but the reduction rate still needs to accelerate to be consistent with the EU’s 2030 and 2050 targets (EEA, 2025a). The EU ETS offers additional incentives for accelerated reductions with its price signal and declining cap. It also complements the existing portfolio of regulations, policy instruments and measures at EU and national level, for example, the Carbon Dioxide (CO₂) Emissions Performance Standards for Road Vehicles (EU, 2023b, 2024a) and the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EU, 2024b).

Unlike earlier scope extensions, the emissions from the road transport and buildings sectors do not fall under the original EU ETS, hereinafter referred to as EU ETS1, but under a separate system, the EU ETS2. While the two systems are very similar and share similar processes, both have their own cap and diverging carbon prices are likely. The regulated entities under the EU ETS2 are fuel suppliers (and not end consumers, such as households or car users), which will be required to monitor and report emissions and to surrender allowances to cover the emissions from the fuels they have sold to consumers covered by the EU ETS2. The EU ETS2 was planned to become fully operational in 2027, with a possible delay of one year in case of exceptionally high oil or gas prices. Separately thereof, in November 2025, the European Council, supported by the European Parliament, agreed to delay the start of the system to 2028 (European Parliament, 2025) to ensure smoother implementation and policy coordination. Although no further changes to the agreed one-year postponement are expected, trilogue discussions and the formal adoption of this legislative change are still outstanding.

The EU ETS2 cap is set to target CO₂ emissions reductions of 42% by 2030 compared to 2005 levels, therefore aimed to have a substantial contribution to the EU’s and the EU Member States’ 2030 climate targets. As part of the EU ETS2 framework, the Social Climate Fund was established to contribute to a socially fair transition towards climate neutrality. It will provide dedicated funding to Member States to support structural investments and measures in energy efficiency, decarbonisation of buildings and clean mobility as well as temporary direct income support benefitting the most vulnerable groups, who are disproportionately affected by higher energy and transport costs during the green transition.

² Additional sectors from small industrial sources correspond with the sources of emissions from Energy industries (sector 1.A.1.) and manufacturing industries and construction (1.A.2., defined in 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories). These emissions are not considered further in this report, which focuses on the two larger emission sources under the EU ETS2 - the road transport and buildings sector.

Box 1 **Sectoral scope of the EU ETS2.**

The EU ETS2 covers CO₂ emissions from the **road transport, buildings, and additional sectors**, defined as follows. The codes between brackets refer to the corresponding Common Reporting Format/Common Reporting Tables (CRF/CRT) categories of the IPCC emission inventory guidelines:

- Commercial/institutional buildings (1A4a): fuel combustion for space heating, hot water, cooking, etc.
- Residential buildings (1A4b): fuel combustion in households for space heating, hot water, cooking, off-road vehicles and machinery used in this sector (e.g. lawn mowers).
- Road Transportation (1A3b): all combustion and evaporative emissions arising from fuel use in road vehicles (cars, motorcycles, light- and heavy-duty vehicles such as trucks, busses, urea-based additives for catalysts, etc.). However, agricultural vehicles used on paved roads and military operations are excluded.
- Fuel combustion for the production of combined heat and power plants and heating plants (1A1a(ii) and (iii)), when producing heat for commercial or residential buildings, either directly or via district heating networks. Installations already covered by the EU ETS1 are excluded from the EU ETS2.
- Other fuel combustion in the energy Industries (1A1) and fuel combustion in the manufacturing industries and construction (1A2) that is not covered by the EU ETS1. This excludes fuels used for non-energetic purposes for process input.

Member States can choose to unilaterally opt-in CO₂ emissions from other sectors or parts of other sectors that are not included under the EU ETS1 or EU ETS2, subject to approval by the European Commission³.

1.1. Study scope and structure

This report explores how the EU ETS2 will help reduce GHG emissions in the road transport and buildings sectors, which need to decarbonise faster in order to meet the EU's ambitious climate targets. It also looks into how the Social Climate Fund can support households in the transition to more sustainable transport and buildings in Europe, preventing transport and energy poverty. The report is based on extensive desk research with EU legislation on the EU ETS2 at its core. The initial phase involved a systematic collection of available literature on the EU ETS2, complemented with additional sources, such as quantitative data on GHG emission trends in the transport and buildings sectors, including previous works conducted by the EEA. The literature reviewed includes reports from the European Commission, individual Member States, other stakeholders, research papers and academic publications. This process aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the EU ETS2 and the Social Climate Fund, as well as gaps and uncertainties.

It is important to note that this report was drafted before the recent political discussions on the postponement of the application of the ETS2 by one year to 2028, were concluded, and before the EC proposal package on buffer mechanisms, announced during the Environment Council in November, was published. The report therefore refers to the functioning of EU ETS2 and Social Climate Fund as set out in the current ETS Directive (EU, 2023b) and Social Climate Fund Regulation (EU, 2023c).

³ For example, the European Commission has approved unilateral opt-in of additional sectors by Austria, Finland, the Netherlands and Sweden.

2. Emission Trends in Transport and Buildings

Key messages:

- Transport and buildings remain major sources of greenhouse gas emissions in the EU. While emissions in EU ETS1 sectors have fallen by 48% between 2005 and 2023, reductions in non-ETS1 sectors are more challenging due to millions of decentralised sources such as vehicles and households, higher upfront investment needs, and weaker direct benefits from falling renewable electricity costs.
- Road transport emissions declined by modest 4.5% between 2005 and 2023. Passenger cars account for around 60% of these emissions, and the sector remains to 93% reliant on fossil fuels, despite rising biofuel use and rapid electrification in most recent years. Significant energy efficiency improvements and increased biofuel use, driven by policy intervention, have supported emission reductions but were largely offset by growing transport demand.
- Building emissions fell by 37.5% over the same period, mainly through energy efficiency measures and a cleaner energy mix. However, heating in 2023 still depends heavily on fossil fuels, particularly in households, which account for 75% of fossil fuel use in the sector. Emissions declined despite increases in both the number and size of buildings, highlighting the effectiveness of decarbonisation efforts.
- Achieving climate neutrality by 2050 requires deeper cuts across all sectors. The introduction of ETS2, extending carbon pricing to road transport and buildings, will strengthen incentives to accelerate the decarbonisation in these sectors in line with the EU's climate ambition.

2.1. Introduction

The transport and buildings sectors in the EU are significant contributors to GHG emissions, exhibiting varied trends in recent years. Despite technological advancements and increased sales of electric vehicles, emissions from road transport have been challenging to abate, largely due to increased demand for mobility and freight. In contrast, emissions from fossil fuel combustion in buildings have been decreasing since 2005 (EEA, 2025b). This was mainly due to energy efficiency improvements, retrofitting of existing buildings and further deployment of low-carbon technologies such as heat pumps. However, the pace of decarbonisation in both sectors must accelerate to meet the EU's ambitious climate targets, including achieving net-zero emissions by 2050.

The EU ETS1 has contributed to a significant reduction in emissions with stationary installations demonstrating emission reductions of 48% in the period 2005 to 2023 (51% until 2024). In comparison, the reduction between 2005 and 2023 of emissions, which are covered under the ETS2 is 18%. In Figure 1 these developments are shown. In addition, the emission development along the timeline is depicted for the three sectors of ETS2: CO₂ emissions of the buildings and road transport sector covered by the EU ETS2 (i.e. direct emissions from fossil fuels) have decreased by 37% and 5% respectively. In 2023, 89% of emissions under the ETS2 are located under these two sectors, while 11% of ETS2 emissions relate to fuel combustion in energy industries (1A1) and in manufacturing industries and construction (1A2) that is not covered by the EU ETS1. These emissions decreased by 17% between 2005 and 2023.

Figure 1 Emissions trends of the ETS1 stationary and ETS2 in EEA scope⁴, in percentage change.

Source: EEA Greenhouse Gases – data viewer (EEA, 2025b), EU Emissions Trading System (ETS) data viewer (EEA, 2025c), compilation by Öko-Institut 2025.

Figure 2 Emissions trends of the EU ETS1 stationary, EU ETS2, EU ETS2 by sector in EEA scope, in million tonnes of CO₂-equivalent.

Source: EEA Greenhouse Gases – data viewer (EEA, 2025b), EU Emissions Trading System (ETS) data viewer. (EEA, 2025c).

⁴ The European Economic Area scope of the EU ETS consists of the Member States of the European Union and three countries of the European Free Trade Association (Iceland, Liechtenstein, and Norway).

The slower GHG reduction rate in road transport and, to some extent, in the building sector compared to EU ETS1 sectors can be attributed to several significant differences, such as the fact that EU ETS1 emissions are concentrated in large industrial and energy facilities where emissions can be cut more efficiently with centralised measures than in the road transport and buildings sectors with their millions of decentralised sources (vehicles and households). Also, the sectors covered under the EU ETS1 have seen a sharp drop in electricity costs as wind and solar with near zero-marginal costs have entered the grid. As a result, reducing emissions in EU ETS1 has been comparatively cheaper (Günter et al., 2024). For the sectors of the EU ETS2, upfront costs of transitioning to low-emission technologies are capital intensive, which makes it harder for individuals to invest in such measures (Keliauskaitė et al., 2024). Carbon pricing has clearly created direct financial incentives for emission reductions in the EU ETS1 sectors and the EU ETS2 will offer the necessary additional incentives for accelerated emission reductions in the road transport and building sector, as long as other price drivers such as energy taxation are aligned with the climate targets.

2.2. Emission trends and drivers in road transport

While part of the CO₂ emissions from aviation and shipping and the CO₂ emissions from electricity production for rail and electric road transport are covered under the EU ETS1, the CO₂ emissions from fuel combustion in road transport are included in the new ETS, the EU ETS2.

Road transport is the largest source of GHG emissions within the transport sector. In 2023, it emitted 757.1 Mt CO₂-equivalent (CO₂e) (EEA, 2025d), accounting for 72.9% of the GHG emissions from the transport sector, including international shipping and aviation. Despite overall GHG emissions falling by 31.7% since 2005, road transport emissions have decreased just by 4.4%. As a result, road transport's share of total GHG emissions has grown from 17.4% in 2005 to 24.4% in 2023, a trend which is likely to continue without intervention.

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the EU's GHG emissions from road transport dropped significantly in 2020, then rebounded in 2021 and 2022, and remained below emission levels in 2019. In 2023, road transport emissions fell by 1% compared to 2022 (Figure 3).

Figure 3 Emissions from road transport in the EU-27, 2005-2023, in million tonnes CO₂e.

Source: EU GHG emission inventory (EEA, 2025d).

Throughout the years, CO₂ emissions accounted for about 98% to 99% of the exhaust GHG emissions from road transport. The exhaust emissions of GHGs are considered direct emissions according to the reporting rules for GHG inventories under the UNFCCC. Member States also report emissions related to the production and distribution/transmission of fuels and electricity for road transport in the energy sector of

the GHG inventory. However, only direct emissions from fuel combustion in the road transport sector fall under the EU ETS2.

Road transport still relies mostly on fossil energy (Figure 4). In terms of energy content, the share of fossil energy was 92.8% in 2023. Renewables and biofuels accounted for 6.7% and electricity for a mere 0.5%. Among the fossil fuels, the share of diesel grew until 2016-2017, but decreased in the years thereafter. In 2023 diesel accounted for 63.7% of final energy consumption in road transport.

Figure 4 Final energy consumption in road transport in the EU-27, 2005-2023, in million TJ.

Source: Eurostat, Complete energy balances (nrg_bal_c).

Within road transport, cars accounted for 59.9% of GHG emissions in 2023, followed by heavy-duty trucks and buses (26.9%), and light-duty trucks (12.0%)⁵. Motorcycles and other road transport accounted for the remaining 1.2% (Figure 5). This ranking in importance has been the same since 2005 (see also Figure 3, and for illustration the shares in 2005 in Figure 5). However, since 2005 some of the road modes have seen a faster reduction in GHG emissions than others. GHG emissions from light-duty trucks and heavy-duty vehicles have fallen less than the average road transport GHG emissions since 2005 (by respectively 3.7% and 0.3%, compared to 4.4% on average), while GHG emissions from cars have fallen more than average (namely by 5.3%).

⁵ For the names of the Nomenclature For Reporting (NFR) source codes for road transport emissions the terminology of EC (2025c) is used, with the terms “light-duty trucks” for NFR category 1.A.3.b.ii and “heavy-duty trucks and buses” for NFR category 1.A.3.b.iii. In the emission inventory guidelines of EMEP and EEA (2023), these NFR categories are referred to as, respectively “light commercial vehicles (<3.5t)” and “heavy-duty vehicles (>3.5t) including buses”. The latter include trucks, coaches and buses.

Figure 5 Share of road transport modes in GHG emissions from road transport, EU-27, 2005 and 2023, in percentage.

Source: EU GHG emission inventory (EEA, 2025d).

To explore the drivers behind the trends in GHG emissions of the most emitting road transport categories, the decomposition analysis that was conducted in EEA (2022) has been updated with recent evolutions up to 2022⁶. The scope of the analysis comprises CO₂ emissions of passenger cars and heavy goods vehicles. The CO₂ emissions account for approximately 99% of the GHG emissions from these transport modes. The scope of the analysis is the tank-to-wheel (TTW) or exhaust emissions, accounted for in the GHG emissions inventories and covered under the EU ETS2.

For cars the main driving factor behind the evolution in CO₂ emissions has been the evolution in passenger transport volumes (Figure 6). In other words, when passenger volumes grew, CO₂ emissions followed and vice versa. The impact of the financial economic crisis between 2009-2012 and the COVID-19 pandemic in recent years is clearly visible as sharp declines in the trend. This was combined with a growing modal share of car transport (represented by the “modal split” effect, with an especially pronounced impact in the COVID-years).

The improved energy efficiency of cars - the energy consumption per passenger-km was 8.2% lower in 2023 than in 2000 - and the higher share of biofuels contributed to lowering the CO₂ emissions. The “energy efficiency effect” appears after 2009 when mandatory emission reduction targets for new cars sold in the EU were adopted. The “biofuel effect” is also the result of policies. Biofuels are considered carbon neutral in the GHG emission inventory.

In the most recent years, the impact of the electrification in road transport appears, though it is still small. Despite the strong increase in newly registered electric vehicles⁷ to a share of 21.6% in 2022 and 22.5% in 2023 (EEA, 2025e), and with nearly one in four new cars sold in the EU in 2023 being an electric vehicle, only 3% of the total passenger car fleet in the EU was battery electric or plug-in hybrid in 2023 (EEA, 2025a).

In 2023 the CO₂ emissions from cars were almost the same as in 2000. The decomposition analysis shows that the higher emissions associated with higher transport demand and a higher car modal share than in 2000 were counterbalanced by the higher energy efficiency of cars, the use of biofuels and the electrification of cars.

⁶ The reader is referred to the TERM 2021 report (EEA, 2022) for a description of the methodology. The decomposition analysis considers different underlying factors. The evolution of these factors between 2000 and 2023 is reported in Annex 1.

⁷ In the referenced report of the EEA, the term “electric vehicles” covers both battery electric vehicles and plug-in hybrid electric vehicles (EEA, 2025e).

Figure 6 Decomposition analysis of the CO₂ emissions from passenger cars in the EU-27, 2000-2023, in percentage change in CO₂ emissions compared to 2000, and contribution of different factors to this change.

Notes: Driving factors: Percentage contribution of driving factors to percentage change in CO₂ emissions from passenger cars.

Source: ETC CM elaboration, update of the analysis in the TERM 2021 report (EEA, 2022).

The CO₂ emissions from heavy goods vehicles (HGVs) were approximately 1.5% higher in 2023 compared to 2000. A period of growth until 2007 was followed by annual reductions until 2014, after which emissions started increasing. The impact of COVID-19 pandemic is evident, but less so and shorter than for car transport. In 2021 and 2022 the CO₂ emissions picked up again, to fall in 2023. The fall between 2022 and 2023 is mainly related to lower inland freight transport demand.

Freight demand has been a key factor contributing to the observed trends in 2000-2023 (Figure 7). The modal share of HGVs in terms of load carried over distance (tonne-km) put an upward trend on CO₂ emissions from these vehicles (represented by the “modal split” effect in the figure). Improvements in energy efficiency have contributed to limiting the increase in emissions, together with the adoption of biofuels. The energy consumption per tonne-km is estimated to have dropped by approximately 19% between 2000 and 2023, more significantly than for passenger cars.

Figure 7 Decomposition analysis of the CO₂ emissions from heavy goods vehicles in the EU-27, 2000-2023, in percentage change in CO₂ emissions compared to 2000, and contribution of different factors to this change.

Notes: Driving factors: Percentage contribution of driving factors to percentage change in CO₂ emissions from heavy goods vehicles.

Source: ETC CM elaboration, update of the analysis in the TERM 2021 report (EEA, 2022).

2.3. Emission trends and drivers in the buildings sector

In the building sector, total emissions consist of direct and indirect emissions⁸. Direct emissions come from the combustion of fossil fuels for heating in residential and non-residential buildings (e.g., oil and gas used in boilers for heating, gas for cooking, etc.), while indirect emissions come from the electricity and heat use, which may be produced elsewhere using fossil fuels. Indirect emissions are covered by EU ETS1, while direct emissions fall under the EU ETS2; this section therefore focuses mainly on the trend in direct emissions⁹. Direct emissions from energy used in buildings represented 13% of total GHG emissions in the EU-27 in 2023. These emissions have decreased by approximately 37% in the period 2005-2023 and by 21% since 2015, but accelerated emission reductions are needed to meet the EU’s emission targets for 2030¹⁰ (EEA, 2024a).

Figure 8 shows the period since 2005 for comparison with the EU ETS1 and illustrates details in direct and indirect emissions trends for residential¹¹ and non-residential buildings.

⁸ See the EEA indicator [Greenhouse gas emissions from energy use in buildings in Europe](#).

⁹ The EU ETS2 covers the “direct” CO₂ emissions from energy use in buildings defined as, from a statistical perspective, the following two IPCC emissions categories in GHG inventories:

- Commercial/institutional buildings (1A4a): fuel combustion for space heating, hot water, cooking, etc.
- Residential buildings (1A4b): fuel combustion in households for space heating, hot water, cooking, off-road vehicles and machinery used in this sector (e.g. lawn mowers), etc.

¹⁰ The EEA’s Trends and Projections 2024 report bases its analyses of sectoral progress towards 2030 on the modelled emissions from the MIX 55 scenario, which represents the core policy scenario underpinning the 2030 Climate Target Plan.

¹¹ The terms ‘residential building’ and ‘household’ are used interchangeably throughout the report.

Figure 8 Breakdown of greenhouse gas emissions from energy use in buildings in the EU-27, 2005-2023, in million tonnes CO₂e¹².

Notes: Data for indirect emissions from energy use in buildings are currently available only up to 2022.

Source: EEA GHG – data viewer (EEA, 2025b).

Direct emissions in the residential and non-residential sectors have decreased by 37% and 36% respectively between 2005 and 2023. This reflects responses to the EU decarbonisation strategy, including energy saving measures adopted in line with obligations under the Energy Efficiency Directive and the Building Energy Performance Directive, as well as in response to price signals created by the Energy Taxation Directive. A further, though smaller, contribution comes from the shift from fossil-fuel heating to renewable energy sources, such as heat pumps, supported by the Renewable Energy Directive (see Section 3.4 for more details on these legislations). Since 2015, direct emissions in the residential and non-residential sectors have decreased by 20% and 23% respectively.

The energy consumption in buildings has not fluctuated much since 2005 (14% and 8% for the residential and non-residential sectors respectively). Especially since 2015, the energy consumption of the residential sector has decreased even less (7%), while for the non-residential sector it has decreased by 8%. However, the consumption of fossil fuels has been decreasing since 2005 for the residential and non-residential sectors (by 37% and 36% respectively) (Figure 9 and Figure 11). It is worth noting that the trend is stable between 2015 and 2020, with an increase in the use of fossil fuels in 2021, mainly due to the increase of natural gas, before decreasing in 2022 and 2023.

¹² All GHG gases have been taken into account in this graph, while only CO₂ is covered under ETS2 scope. It is noted, however, that the contribution of GHGs other than CO₂ is negligible in the emissions from buildings.

Figure 9 Breakdown of household energy consumption by type of fuel in the EU-27, 2005-2023, in TJ.

Notes: Eurostat SIEC codes are displayed next to fuel types. It should be noted that the sum of energies from different fuel types might exceed the energy corresponding to “Total” since there are overlaps in the SIEC classification.

Source: Eurostat energy balances (Eurostat, 2025a).

Figure 10 Breakdown of non-residential buildings energy consumption by type of fuel in the EU-27, 2005-2023, in TJ.

Source: Eurostat energy balances (Eurostat, 2025a).

62% of households’ final energy consumption is used for space heating making it the most energy-intensive end-use in buildings. Half of space heating demand relies on fossil fuels, mainly natural gas. Moreover,

when considering all fossil fuel use in households, 75% is used for space heating, indicating that this activity is the main driver of fossil fuel use in residential buildings.

Decomposition analysis of CO₂ emissions from households, published by Odyssee-Mure (Odyssee Mure, 2025) shows the main drivers in emissions trend¹³ (Figure 11). Between 2005 and 2022, the decrease of CO₂ emissions by almost 32% (130 MtCO₂) is mainly attributable to energy savings (93.8 MtCO₂), decarbonisation (reflecting a change in the energy mix) (84.4 MtCO₂) and climate differences (23.5 MtCO₂). The decrease of energy use for heating in winter due to rising temperature is reflected in the climate component in the following figure.

However, other factors work in opposite direction. A significant rise in CO₂ emissions can be attributed to the increased number of dwellings (42.5 MtCO₂), the larger average dwelling sizes (20.4 MtCO₂), as well as the increased number of appliances per dwelling (15.4 MtCO₂).

Overall, energy savings have played a crucial role in mitigating increases in household energy consumption and CO₂ emissions in recent years. Behavioural changes and climate variations have also influenced energy consumption, although their impact has been smaller compared to decarbonisation of the energy mix and energy savings in the analysed period.

Figure 11 Decomposition analysis of CO₂ emissions from households in the EU-27, 2005-2022, in percentage.

Notes: The decomposition analysis of energy consumption and CO₂ emissions from the buildings sector, is based on Eurostat and national data.

Source: Odyssee-Mure (Odyssee Mure, 2025).

¹³ Note that the decomposition analysis presented do not differentiate between direct and indirect emissions as defined in the beginning of this section.

3. The EU ETS2 and the Social Climate Fund

Key messages:

- The EU ETS2 introduces a carbon pricing framework for buildings and road transport by setting an EU-wide cap and upstream price signal to align the sectors' mitigation trajectory with the 2030 climate targets.
- It operates as a cap-and-trade system, setting a declining EU-wide emissions ceiling and requiring fuel suppliers to surrender allowances equal to the carbon content of the fuels they place on the market. All allowances are auctioned, and the price is determined by supply and demand in the market.
- The system includes several design features for price stability. These provisions include an emergency brake that can postpone the start year during periods of high energy prices, and a market stability reserve that can release allowances in the event of rapid price increases.
- The Social Climate Fund functions as an essential counterpart to ETS2. It uses a share of ETS2 auction revenues to support households and micro-enterprises with limited capacity to respond to higher fossil fuel costs. Member States must prepare a national Social Climate Plan with the measures and investments that will be funded under the Social Climate Fund. The fund emphasises structural measures, including building renovation, heating system upgrades, and zero- and low-emission mobility, complemented by time-limited income support.
- The EU ETS2 complements key EU climate and energy policies by reinforcing their objectives through a consistent carbon price. It supports the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive by strengthening incentives for renovation and efficient heating, aligns with vehicle CO₂ standards by encouraging uptake of low and zero emission vehicles, and contributes to the Renewable Energy Directive goals by promoting a shift away from fossil fuels in heating and transport.

3.1. Shaping of the EU ETS2 and the Social Climate Fund from proposal to legislation

In 2020, the European Commission published the communication *Stepping up Europe's 2030 climate ambition*. This document emphasised the need to update the legislative framework to reflect the increased ambition levels, particularly proposing to expand the EU ETS1 to additional sectors. This was followed by the proposed amendments to Directive 2003/87/EC to align the EU ETS with the goal of a 55% reduction in EU GHG emissions by 2030. The proposal introduced a stricter emissions cap with a more ambitious linear reduction factor, adjusted rules for free allocation of allowances and the Market Stability Reserve (MSR), included maritime transport, expanded the coverage of emissions from the aviation sector, increased funding for the Innovation and Modernisation Funds, and established a separate EU ETS2 for road transport, buildings and other industries not covered by the EU ETS1.

The EU ETS2, as set up in the amended Directive (EU) 2023/959 (EU, 2023c) and amended Regulation (EU) 2023/957 (EU, 2023a), includes several mechanisms to control the potential impact of allowance prices on households. For example, it introduces a price containment mechanism, which allows the release of additional allowances to prevent price spikes, an MSR to balance supply and demand and keep price volatility in check, and an emergency break that could lead to postponement of the start by one year (to 2028) if the gas and/or oil price are exceptionally high in 2026. Separately thereof, in November 2025, it was agreed by the European Council, supported by the European Parliament, to delay the start of the system to 2028 to ensure smoother implementation and policy coordination (European Parliament, 2025). In parallel with the EU ETS2, a Social Climate Fund intrinsically linked with the EU ETS2 was introduced. The Fund aims at alleviating the potential social and economic impacts arising

from the ETS2, promoting investments that address the root causes of energy and transport poverty, reduce dependency on fossil fuels, and deliver lasting benefits to vulnerable households and micro-enterprises, while also allowing for temporary relief to vulnerable households. Member States may use the Social Climate Fund to support structural measures and investments in energy efficiency and renovation of buildings, clean heating and cooling and integration of renewable energy, as well as for zero- and low-emission mobility solutions. Member States will also have the option of spending a maximum of 37.5% of the resources on temporary direct income support. The Social Climate Fund was agreed among the co-legislators in early 2023. It will run from 2026 to 2032 with funding up to EUR 65 billion by pooling revenues from both the EU ETS2 and the EU ETS1. Together with a mandatory minimum co-financing of 25% of the measures and investments benefitting from the fund, it should mobilise at least EUR 86.7 billion of public funding over its lifetime. The text was adopted on 10 May 2023 and Regulation (EU) 2023/955 establishing the Social Climate Fund entered into force on 5 June 2023.

3.2. The functioning of the EU ETS2

3.2.1. The EU ETS2 in brief

The EU ETS2 is a market-based instrument to control GHG emissions by providing economic incentives for reducing emissions and by internalising their costs. It consists of an ETS for road transport, buildings, and small industry sectors, covering the CO₂ emissions from fuel combustion. After a three-year preparatory period, the system was originally planned to start in 2027 (or at the latest in 2028 in case of exceptionally high energy prices¹⁴). In November 2025¹⁵, it was agreed by the European Council, supported by the European Parliament, to delay the start of the system to 2028 to ensure smoother implementation and policy coordination (European Parliament, 2025). As the report was prepared before this decision was taken, the discussion below does not fully take into account the implications of this decision on the timing of the different steps for the implementation of the EU ETS2.

The EU ETS2 is a so-called ‘cap-and-trade’ system, just like the current EU ETS (referred to in this report as the EU ETS1). It sets an aggregate emissions cap or ceiling for all sectors covered. The regulated entities in the EU ETS2 are fuel suppliers. They must report CO₂ emissions to a competent authority in the Member State and surrender allowances according to the carbon content of the fuels they bring onto the market for the sectors covered by the EU ETS2. One allowance is required per tonne of CO₂. The price of the allowances is determined in the market by the interaction between the supply and demand of the emission allowances. In the EU ETS2, all allowances will be auctioned, and a part of the corresponding revenue will be used to finance the Social Climate Fund (see section 3.2.9). The remainder will be given to the Member States to use for climate and social purposes. To monitor this, Member States have to report how EU ETS2 auctioning revenues are used; they already have an obligation to do this for EU ETS1 auctioning revenues.

The EU ETS2 ensures that the desired reduction in CO₂ emissions is achieved at the lowest possible cost, given all other (necessary) government policies that are in place to reduce emissions in EU ETS2 sectors. As the EU ETS2 is a separate system from the EU ETS1 (which covers the GHG emissions from electricity

¹⁴ The discussion in this section was drafted before this package of proposals was published.

This situation is defined as follows: if either the average Brent crude oil price in the first half of 2026 is more than double the average of the five preceding years, or if the average natural gas price in January-June 2026 is higher than the average gas price in February and March 2022. The European Commission will publish, by 15 July, if this is the case.

¹⁵ In October 2025 it was announced that a package of proposals is prepared by the European Commission with regards to the EU ETS2. The aim is to address concerns about future carbon-price levels and volatility, and to help accelerate investments ahead of the launch of the ETS2 market (EC, 2025a). The discussion in this section was drafted before this package of proposals was published and before the delay was agreed.

plants, large industrial installations, aviation within the European Economic Area and maritime), the price of the emission allowances is likely to be different from that of the EU ETS1.¹⁶

The emissions from the sectors under the EU ETS2 must fall by 42% from 2005 levels by 2030. The ceiling of the EU ETS2 decreases each year according to a linear path.

The EU ETS2 is organised as an upstream system because of technical feasibility and administrative efficiency. This means that it is the entities releasing the fuel for consumption¹⁷ (i.e. supplying the fuel to the ETS2 activities) that must submit the allowances, rather than the end consumers (individual car users, homeowners, etc.). As the regulated entities will factor the price of the allowances into the fuel price for the end users according to the CO₂ intensity of the fuels, this will give an incentive to the end users to reduce their emissions. On the supply side, the fuel suppliers also get the incentive to change their fuel mix.

3.2.2. Scope

The **sectoral** scope of the EU ETS2 was presented in Box 1.

The **fuels** covered are the same as the ones covered by the Energy Taxation Directive (ETD):

- (Un)leaded petrol, gas oil, kerosene, liquified petroleum gas (LPG), natural gas, heavy fuel oil, coal and coke¹⁸,
- any other product intended for use, offered for sale or used as motor fuel or heating fuel¹⁹. This includes any fuel additives used as motor fuel, certain bio-based fuels, and any other hydrocarbons for heating purposes, except for peat.

An indicative list of the fuels excluded from the EU ETS2 is as follows:

- Peat,
- Waste used as fuels (hazardous or municipal waste used as fuel²⁰),
- Waste-derived fuels (mostly used in ETS installations),
- Solid biomass (e.g. wood-based fuels), and
- Charcoal from wood.

Biomass used for combustion is zero-rated (i.e. an emission factor of zero) on condition that it satisfies the sustainability and GHG savings criteria defined by Directive (EU) 2018/2001 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2018 on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources (recast). Hydrogen has a zero CO₂ emission factor at the point of use and therefore does not trigger EU ETS2 obligations.

¹⁶ This implies that additional efficiency gains could be attained by having one ETS covering the sectors of both the EU ETS1 and EU ETS2. However, it was chosen not to do so, in order not to endanger the good functioning of the EU ETS1. At a later stage (by end of October 2031) the European Commission is required to evaluate whether it is feasible to integrate the sectors covered by the EU ETS2 into the EU ETS1.

¹⁷ In most cases these are the same entities that are liable for the excise duties on fuels. With this approach it is aimed to keep the administrative burden as small as possible. The impact assessment of the extension of the EU ETS1 to road transport and buildings estimated the number of regulated entities to be approximately 11,400 (approximately 7,000 tax warehouses for oil, approximately 1,400 regional and local gas suppliers, and approximately 3,000 coal suppliers) (EC, 2021b). With the inclusion of the additional sectors in the scope of the EU ETS2, this number will likely be higher.

¹⁸ I.e. the fuels listed in Table A and C of the Energy Tax Directive (ETD).

¹⁹ As specified in Article 2(3) of the ETD.

²⁰ The amended EU ETS1 includes provisions for the inclusion of emissions from waste incineration in the EU ETS1 system.

The **countries** covered by the EU ETS2 are the 27 EU Member States and the three EEA-EFTA states: Iceland, Liechtenstein and Norway (EEA Joint Committee, 2025).

By way of derogation, if a **national carbon tax** for the release of fuel to the sectors under the EU ETS2 is notified to the Commission before 2024, the related regulated entities, may be exempted from surrendering ETS2 allowances until the end of 2030 under certain conditions. These include the condition that the national carbon tax should be higher than the average auction clearing price of the EU ETS2 (which would mean that replacing the national carbon tax by the EU ETS2 would reduce the price incentive). For example, Ireland²¹ and Norway²² have undertaken steps in order to obtain a derogation to exempt EU ETS2 regulated entities from the obligation to surrender emissions allowances for the years 2027-2030. The procedure is currently ongoing (Ireland, Department of the Environment, Climate and Communications, 2024; Norway. Ministry of Climate and Environment, 2025; Norway, Royal Ministry of Finance, 2024).

3.2.3. The emissions cap

In December 2024 the Commission published the EU-wide quantity of allowances for the EU ETS2 in 2027. This cap is set at 1,036,288,784 allowances for 2027 (corresponding with 1,036.29 Mt CO₂), for the EU-27 and the three EEA-EFTA States.

The cap for 2027 has been calculated based on the average CO₂ emissions from fuel combustion in the EU ETS2 sectors from 2016 to 2018²³.

The EU ETS2 cap from 2028 will be determined at a later stage, based on the average CO₂ emissions reported by the EU ETS2 regulated entities for the years 2024 to 2026. It should then decrease annually by a 5.38% linear reduction factor. If the emissions in 2024-2026 are higher than required, the directive provides for a recalculation of the linear reduction factor to reach the 42% emission reduction in 2030. The opposite is not the case: if the emissions in 2024-2026 are lower than the trajectory leading to the 2027 cap, the linear reduction factor of 5.38% is maintained.

3.2.4. Auctioning and trading

In the EU ETS2, all emission allowances will be placed on the market via auctioning (primary market). Besides the primary market, it can be expected that spot, futures, options, and forward contracts will be traded on the secondary markets²⁴. Both on-exchange and off-exchange (over-the-counter [OTC]) trading are allowed for. The European Securities and Markets Authority (ESMA) is mandated to monitor the integrity and transparency of the entire European carbon market²⁵. Regulated entities can purchase

²¹ As from 1 May 2025, the carbon tax in Ireland is EUR 63.5 per tonne CO₂. This is scheduled to increase annually up to EUR 100 per tonne CO₂ in 2030 (Ireland, Department of Finance, 2024).

²² In 2024 Norway levied a CO₂ tax on mineral oil, petrol, natural gas, and LPG, equivalent to approximately 1,176 NOK per tonne CO₂ (or approximately EUR 101.5 per tonne CO₂) (Norway, Royal Ministry of Finance, 2024).

²³ This average is reduced up to the year 2027 as follows:

- until 2024, through a linear reduction trajectory consistent with the one for all emissions within the scope of the Effort Sharing Regulation,
- for the years 2025-2027, through an annual linear reduction factor of 5.1% in accordance with the EU ETS Directive.

²⁴ For example, on 28 April 2025 EEX announced the introduction of new futures contracts related to the EU ETS2, subject to regulatory approval, and on 6 May 2025 ICE launched a EUA 2 futures contract (EEX Group, 2025; ICE, 2025).

The first future contracts were traded on ICE in the beginning of May 2025, though still with thin volumes, The price was approximately EUR 73.60 per tonne CO₂ (Carbon Pulse, 2025).

²⁵ The revised EU ETS Directive (Directive (EU) 2023/959) requires ESMA to oversee various aspects of the carbon market, such as market volatility, price evolution, auction operations, trading activities (including over-the-

allowances either in the primary auctions or on secondary markets. As in EU ETS1, borrowing of emission allowances is prohibited but there is unlimited banking. Banking of emission allowances refers to the ability of the regulated entities to save (or bank) unused emission allowances for future use instead of using them or selling them immediately. This feature is a key flexibility mechanism, allowing companies to manage their compliance costs and plan for the longer term.

With the start in 2028, the number of allowances auctioned for the start of the ETS2 will be 130% of the emissions cap set for 2029. The 30% additional allowances (“frontloading of allowances”) may be auctioned until 31 May 2029. This will be offset by decreasing the annual emission allowances by an equal number of allowances over the period 2030-2032. The frontloading is used to ensure a smooth start of the EU ETS2, and to allow the regulated entities to reduce their price and liquidity risk by hedging or buying ahead allowances.

3.2.5. Market Stability Reserve for the EU ETS2

As in the case of the EU ETS1, there will be a Market Stability Reserve (MSR) for the EU ETS2 (hence referred to as the MSR2). These two reserves will be operated separately.

The MSR2 aims to make the carbon market of the EU ETS2 resilient to major future shocks by managing the balance between supply and demand of emission allowances. This is to ensure price and supply stability, thereby enhancing the effectiveness of the system for decarbonising the EU ETS2 sectors. With the start in 2028, 600 million emissions allowances will be put in the MSR2 in 2028. This is additional to the cap for 2028.

The December 2025 proposal for amending the MSR2 includes an extension of the validity of the allowances in the reserve which have not been released before end 2030 (EC, 2025b).

Regular operation of the MSR2

In normal conditions, the MSR2 will be operated based on the Total Number of Allowances in Circulation (TNAC). The TNAC is a metric that is used to determine the surplus of allowances in the EU ETS2. It is defined as the number of allowances that have been issued and are left in the market after the surrendering of allowances for compliance reasons. Hence, TNAC reflects the difference between the allowances issued and the verified emissions, and its value activates the MSR if one of the following two conditions is met:

- If the TNAC is lower than 210 million in a year, 100 million allowances will be released from the MSR2 and added to the allowances available for auctioning. If there are less than 100 million allowances left in the MSR2, all will be released.
- If the TNAC exceed 440 million in a year, 100 million allowances will be deducted from auctioning and placed in the MSR2 over a period of twelve months, starting on September 1 of the next year.

The December 2025 proposal of the Commission to amend the MSR2 includes an additional mechanism to allow for a gradual release of allowances from a TNAC level of 260 million allowances (EC, 2025b).

Operation of the MSR2 in case of excessive price increases

There is no hard cap on the price of the EU ETS2 emission allowances. However, in case of high prices of the EU ETS2 allowances or fast prices increases it is provided that the MSR2 will release additional allowances according to the provisions shown in the table below.

counter trading), liquidity, trading volumes, and the behaviour of market participants, including financial intermediaries.

Table 1 Operation of the MSR2 in case of excessive price increases.

Conditions	Allowances released from the MSR2
In 2027-2028: average price of the allowances during three consecutive months is more than 1.5 times the price in the six consecutive months prior to this	50 million
From 2029: average price of the allowances during three consecutive months is more than two times the price in the six months prior to this	50 million
average price of the allowances during three consecutive months is more than three times the price in the six consecutive months prior to this	150 million
Until the end of 2029: average allowance price exceeds EUR ₂₀₂₀ 45 per tonne CO ₂ ²⁶ for more than two consecutive months	20 million ^a

Notes: ^a It is possible under the existing legislation to inject twice 20 million allowances, but it is not automatic (see Article 30h(7)). To clarify this, the December 2025 proposal of the European Commission to amend the MSR2 contains a Commission declaration and adds a top-up mechanism to double the release of allowances (from 20 to 40 million allowances) when the measure is triggered (EC, 2025b).

Source: Article 30h of the amended ETS Directive (EU) 2023/959 (EU, 2023c).

To avoid an excessive release of allowances, the number released is not additive. If the condition for the release of 20 million allowances is met at the same day as the condition for releasing 50 or 150 million allowances, then only 50 or 150 million allowances will be released.

Moreover, it is stipulated that after a release of allowances based on the previous conditions, no further allowances will be released for the 12 months consecutive to that release. However, in certain circumstances (see also note A for Table 1) this may be overruled by the Commission, together with the Member States.

3.2.6. Monitoring, reporting and verification

The trade in emission allowances is made possible via the **Union Registry**. This is the accounting system that keeps track of all account/permit holders, the emission allowances they hold and records all transfers. The annual procedure of monitoring, reporting and verification (MRV), together with all the associated processes, is known as the EU ETS **compliance cycle**. The rules for monitoring and reporting are set out in the Monitoring and Reporting Regulation (MRR) (EC, 2023a). The timeline for the compliance cycle is summarised in the table below.

²⁶ In EUR₂₀₂₄, this corresponds with approximately EUR 55 per tonne CO₂.

Figure 12 Timeline of the EU ETS2 compliance cycle.

Note: The elements in italics are not strictly a compliance obligation but are added in the table for information purposes.

Source: ETC CM elaboration based on EU (2023c) and EC (2024a).

Regulated entities covered by the EU ETS2 are required to hold a CO₂ permit by 1 January 2025, as well as an approved monitoring plan for the monitoring and reporting of their annual emissions. Every year regulated entities must submit an emissions report by 30 April for the emissions of the previous year. From 2026, the data for a given year will have to be verified by an accredited verifier²⁷. With the start in 2028, from 2029, once annual verified emissions are reported, regulated entities will have to surrender the equivalent number of allowances by 31 May of that year.

Penalties for non-compliance, such as operating without the necessary permits or failing to surrender the required allowances, are determined by each Member State's domestic legislation. Member State penalties for non-compliance must include an excess emissions penalty for missing allowances, in the same way as for EU ETS1.

3.2.7. Provisions for the review of the EU ETS2

The EU ETS Directive specifies that with a start of auctioning in 2028, by 1 January 2029, the Commission shall report to the European Parliament and to the Council on the implementation of the provisions for the EU ETS2 regarding their effectiveness, administration and practical application, including on the application of the rules regarding the MSR2. Where appropriate, the Commission shall accompany that report with a legislative proposal for amending the Directive. By 31 October 2031, the Commission shall assess the feasibility of integrating the sectors covered by the EU ETS2 into the EU ETS1.

²⁷ According to the Accreditation and Verification Regulation (AVR) (EC, 2024b).

3.2.8. Mechanisms to ensure a fair transition

Within the EU ETS2 several mechanisms have been introduced to facilitate the transition and support end consumers, particularly in the context of potential energy price volatility and socio-economic disparities.

The safeguard mechanism which delays the activation of EU ETS2 to 2028 if oil and gas prices rise above a certain threshold has been applied under the EU Climate Law, on which there is a provisional political agreement between the European Parliament and the EU Member States. As discussed in Section 3.2.5, in case of high prices of EU ETS2 allowances or fast price increases, the MSR2 will release additional allowances to help mitigate excessive price increases and provide greater predictability for households and businesses. Additionally, the Social Climate Fund was established by Regulation (EU) 2023/955 (EU, 2023d) to contribute to a socially fair transition towards climate neutrality by addressing the potential social impacts of the EU ETS2. The next section describes in more detail how this will take shape.

3.2.9. Distribution and use of auctioning revenues

The EU ETS2 auctioning revenues will be distributed to the Member States, as summarised in Figure 13. The way in which the revenues are allocated to the different Member States as well the purposes for which they may be used are detailed below.

Figure 13 Distribution of the auctioning revenues of the EU ETS2, split between Social Climate Fund and Member States.

Source: Adapted by ETC CM from Eden et al. (2023).

The Social Climate Fund

Part of the revenues is distributed to the Member States via the Social Climate Fund. This was established with the aim to give financial support to the EU Member States for the measures and investments included in their national Social Climate Plans. These measures and investments must help vulnerable households, vulnerable micro-enterprises, and vulnerable transport users who are affected by higher energy and transport costs during the green transition. The main intention is not to compensate vulnerable households and micro-enterprises for their additional costs, but to support them in investing or changing

behaviour to reduce emissions and relieve the CO₂ related costs associated to the use of fossil fuel. In this way, it is aimed to make households more resilient to any future price increases.

The Social Climate Fund is additional to other EU funds, such as the Modernisation Fund, Just Transition Fund, European Structural and Investment Funds, Recovery and Resilience Facility, and InvestEU, as well as national or regional funding.

The support by the Social Climate Fund covers measures and investments to improve the energy efficiency of buildings, decarbonisation of heating and cooling of buildings, and to improve access to zero- and low-emission mobility. Additionally, targeted direct income support can be granted temporarily to tackle the social impacts of the EU ETS2 on vulnerable households and transport users but only a limited amount of the Social Climate Fund, i.e. a maximum of 37.5% may be used for direct income support.

Box 2 Definitions in the Social Climate Fund Regulation of energy and transport poverty, and of vulnerable households and transport users.

The Social Climate Fund Regulation (EU, 2023d) defines energy poverty and transport poverty as follows:

- **‘Energy poverty’** means a household’s lack of access to essential energy services that underpin a decent standard of living and health, including adequate warmth, cooling, lighting, and energy to power appliances, in the relevant national context, existing social policy and other relevant policies.
- **‘Transport poverty’** means individuals’ and households’ inability or difficulty to meet the costs of private or public transport, or their lack of or limited access to transport needed for their access to essential socioeconomic services and activities, taking into account the national and spatial context.

It also defines vulnerability of households, micro-enterprises and transport users:

- **‘Vulnerable households’** means households in energy poverty or households, including low income and lower middle- income ones, that are significantly affected by the price impacts of the inclusion of greenhouse gas emissions from buildings within the scope of Directive 2003/87/EC and lack the means to renovate the building they occupy.
- **‘Vulnerable micro-enterprises’** means micro-enterprises that are significantly affected by the price impacts of the inclusion of greenhouse gas emissions from buildings or road transport within the scope of Directive 2003/87/EC and that, for the purpose of their activity, lack the means either to renovate the building they occupy, or to purchase zero- and low-emission vehicles or to switch to alternative sustainable modes of transport, including public transport, as relevant
- **‘Vulnerable transport users’** means individuals and households in transport poverty, but also individuals and households, including low income and lower middle-income ones, that are significantly affected by the price impacts of the inclusion of greenhouse gas emissions from road transport within the scope of Directive 2003/87/EC and lack the means to purchase zero- and low-emission vehicles or to switch to alternative sustainable modes of transport, including public transport.

The Social Climate Fund is established for the period from 2026 to 2032. Hence, it will start one year earlier than the initial launch of the EU ETS2 to enable Member States early access to the revenues to combat energy and transport poverty in line with the objectives of the Social Climate Fund. It will be mainly funded by revenues from the EU ETS2, together with the auctioning of allowances from the EU ETS1, up to a maximum amount of EUR 65 billion. Under the EU ETS2, first, 150 million allowances will be directly auctioned for the Social Climate Fund. Further allowances from the EU ETS2 will be allocated to the Fund,

with the goal of a maximum cumulated revenue of EUR 65 billion until 2032²⁸. The Member States must cover at least 25% of the estimated total costs of their national Social Climate Plans themselves. They can use EU ETS2 revenues to supply this contribution. Together with the mandatory co-financing from Member States, the Social Climate Fund will therefore mobilise at least EUR 86.7 billion until 2032.

The Social Climate Fund regulation specifies, amongst other things, the allocation rules to divide the budget amongst the Member States, the elements that should be included in the national Social Climate Plans, the principles governing the fund, the eligible measures, and the assessment of the plans by the European Commission. The maximum budget allocation for each Member State is based on a set of socio-economic and emissions-related variables at Member State level, comprising of:

- the population at risk of poverty living in rural areas,
- CO₂ emissions from fuel combustion by households,
- the percentage of households at risk of poverty with arrears on their utility bills,
- the total population,
- the gross national income per capita, measured in purchasing power standard, and
- the share of reference emissions from road transportation, commercial and public services and the residential sector.

This allocation formula is designed to reduce the negative distributional consequences of the EU climate policy and ensure a fair and equitable distribution of funds among Member States. The resulting shares to each Member State are shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14 Relative share of each EU-27 Member State in the allocation of the Social Climate Fund (box size represents share).

Note: For 3 countries the share is not printed in the graph. The share of Cyprus is 0.2%, that of Luxembourg is 0.1% and that of Malta is 0.1%. Due to rounding the sum of all shares may be different from 100%.

Source: ETC CM elaboration based on Annex II of Regulation (EU) 2023/955 (EU, 2023d).

²⁸ Additionally, Article 10a(8b) of Directive (EU) 2023/959 (EU, 2023c) specifies that 40 million allowances of the EU ETS1 from the quantity which could otherwise be allocated for free, and 10 million allowances of the EU ETS1 from the quantity which could otherwise be auctioned, shall be made available for the Social Climate Fund. They are to be auctioned in 2025. This provision is applied again in 2025 with the European Climate Law.

Jüngling et al (2025) illustrate the order of magnitude of the available funds in each EU-27 Member State, per household in the lowest 10, 20 or 30 percent of the income distribution, and assuming a price of EUR 60 per allowance (Figure 15).

Figure 15 Average Social Climate Fund revenue per household with revenue allocation to households in the lowest 10, 20 or 30 percent of the income distribution, in EUR.

Source: Jüngling et al. (2025).

In addition to these funds, under EU Cohesion Policy, countries like Poland, Romania, and Bulgaria receive more generous allocations from the Just Transition Fund (JTF) and Modernisation Fund due to their higher carbon intensity and lower GDP per capita (BPIE, 2021; Gore, 2022).

Provisions regarding the auctioning revenues not allocated to the Social Climate Fund

In addition to the revenues that Member States receive from the Social Climate Fund, the remaining EU ETS2 auctioning revenues will be distributed to the Member States in shares relative to their reference emissions in 2016-2018 (Figure 16).

Figure 16 Relative share of the EU-27 Member States in the CO₂ emissions of the EU ETS2 sectors in the reference period 2016-2018 (box size represents share).

Note: For 2 countries the share is not printed in the graph. The share of Cyprus is 0.2% and that of Malta is 0.1%. Due to rounding the sum of all shares may be different from 100%.

Source: Based on estimate by Graichen and Ludig (2023).

The following figure gives an estimate by the Bruegel think tank (Jüngling et al., 2025) of the size and composition of the revenues per Member State, as percentage of gross domestic product (GDP), assuming a price of EUR 60 per EU ETS2 allowance.

Figure 17 Estimate of the annual expected EU ETS2 resources per EU-27 Member State, as share of GDP.

Note: Expected revenues with assumed carbon price of EUR 60 per tonne CO₂.

Source: Jüngling et al. (2025).

While Member States have some discretion in allocating the EU ETS2 auction revenues, they are bound by the EU ETS Directive to prioritise climate action and social measures, with mandatory reporting to ensure compliance and transparency. Transparency in the distribution of the revenues enhances trust and credibility.

The EU ETS Directive specifies that these remaining national revenues (or the equivalent financial value of these revenues) shall be used for broad-based climate and social measures, or for one of the following:

- “6. [...] (a) measures intended to contribute to the decarbonisation of heating and cooling of buildings or to the reduction of the energy needs of buildings, [...] as well as measures to provide financial support for low-income households in worst-performing buildings;
- (b) measures intended to accelerate the uptake of zero-emission vehicles or to provide financial support for the deployment of fully interoperable refuelling and recharging infrastructure for zero-emission vehicles, or measures to encourage a shift to public transport and improve multimodality, or to provide financial support in order to address social aspects concerning low- and middle-income transport users;
- (c) to finance their Social Climate Plan [...];
- (d) to provide financial compensation to the final consumers of fuels in cases where it has not been possible to avoid double counting of emissions or where allowances have been surrendered for emissions [...].” (EU, 2023c).

No automatic adjustment of the revenue allocation in response to changing EU ETS2 prices is foreseen. This implies that with higher prices a lower share of the auctioning revenues will be allocated to the Social Climate Fund, and vice versa. With high EU ETS2 prices the extra auction revenues will be directed to the Member States in proportion to their emissions in the reference period 2016-2018.

3.3. Experience from existing ETS mechanisms for road transport and buildings sectors in the EU Member States

Two European Member States currently have in place a national ETS, which will transition into the EU ETS2: **Germany** and **Austria**.

3.3.1. Germany: national emissions trading system

As part of the Climate Action Programme 2030, Germany introduced its Fuel Emissions Trading Act (Brennstoffemissionshandelsgesetz – BEHG) which entered into force in 2021. The national emissions trading system (nEHS) has a similar but somewhat larger scope than the EU ETS2²⁹. Like the EU ETS2 it uses the 2016-2018 period for the determination of the cap until 2030. While some fuels/activities were excluded from the nEHS scope in 2021-2023, the full scope of the nEHS applies as from 2024.

From 2021-2025 the price is not determined on the market but set exogenously by the government. The initial price-level was EUR 25 per tonne CO₂. This was gradually increased over time to EUR 55 per tonne CO₂ in 2025. With an exogenous price, the nEHS is like a carbon tax and is not yet a fully-fledged cap-and-trade system. In 2026 the price can fluctuate within a price corridor. It was planned that from 2027 onwards it would be completely set by the market.

On 31 January 2025, the German Parliament adopted a law outlining the transition from the nEHS to the EU ETS2. The German law includes provisions to use the EU ETS2 “opt-in” option, allowing Member States to extend coverage beyond the mandatory sectors. In addition to fuels covered by the EU ETS2, Germany will opt-in fuels used in agriculture and rail transport, which are currently covered by the nEHS. However, the law does not extend the opt-in option to waste incineration which is also covered in the German nEHS

²⁹ During these three years, emissions under the nEHS scope were about 2% larger than under the EU ETS2 scope (Jörß et al., 2023)

as from 2024. With the start of the EU ETS2 delayed to 2028, the German nEHS would stay in place in 2027 (Clean Energy Wire, 2025, 2025; Umweltbundesamt, 2026).

In 2024 the total income from the sale of the almost 295 million³⁰ nEHS certificates (nEZs) equalled around EUR 13 billion. In 2023 this was EUR 10.7 billion (German Environment Agency, 2025). The revenue from the nEHS flows into the Climate and Transformation Fund, which finances a wide range of programmes aimed at decarbonising the economy. Part of it is also used to finance relief for consumers and businesses, and to support innovation in climate technologies, energy efficiency, and new sustainable industries.

In 2023 the share of the nEHS in Germany's total emissions in 2023 was around 283 million tonnes of CO₂, or approximately 42%. Around 85% of Germany's total emissions in 2023 were subject to a carbon price under either the EU ETS or the nEHS.

Within the nEHS the main drivers of emission trends are the transport and building sectors. In Germany, total emissions from transport decreased by around 1.8 million tonnes of CO₂ equivalent (a reduction of 1.2%) in 2023 compared to 2022. The reduction in emissions was more pronounced in the buildings sector, with a decline of around 8.3 million tonnes of CO₂ equivalent (a reduction of 7.5%) compared to the previous year, 2022 (Deutsche Emissionshandelsstelle, 2024).

3.3.2. The national emissions trading system in Austria

The Austrian Ecological Tax Reform Act of 2021 contained a variety of climate and compensatory measures for citizens and companies. A central part is the implementation of the national ETS (Nationales Emissionszertifikatehandelsgesetz – NEHG) applicable as of July 2022.

The NEHG covers emissions outside the EU ETS1. While it is designed as an ETS and not as a carbon tax, during its initial phase, the NEHG has a fixed price phase from July 2022 until the end of 2025. The fixed prices have increased gradually from EUR 30 per tonne of CO₂ in 2022, to EUR 35 in 2023, EUR 45 in 2024 and EUR 55 in 2025 per tonne CO₂. While the maximum number of available allowances is not limited in the initial phase, this will change with the market phase at the beginning of 2026, according to market rules that still need to be decided. The 2026 price will be kept at EUR 55 per tonne CO₂ if no agreement on price change is achieved. In 2023 the revenue generated from the NEHG amounted to EUR 843 million (ICAP, 2022).

The implementation of the NEHG is flanked by several measures to reduce unwanted effects of carbon pricing instruments. For example, in 2022-2024 the Austrian government implemented a so-called “regional climate bonus”, also known as the “Klimabonus”, a geographically and socially targeted climate dividend, which was paid to all citizens with a primary residence in Austria as a compensatory measure for the novel carbon price. The Klimabonus payments varied according to regional differences in urban-rural typology and quality ratings for public transport (“ÖV-Güteklassen”). These factors assessed the availability and accessibility of public transport and public facilities such as secondary schools, hospitals and district administrations in the area. In regions where switching to more climate-friendly transport options – and thus reducing CO₂ – was difficult, an additional regional adjustment was added (Austria, Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, Climate and Environmental Protection, n.d.). However, under the Social Climate Fund, this measure would be considered “Direct Income Support” and would have to be limited in time. In addition, the NEHG contains compensatory measures for businesses. The ecological reform also includes accompanying measures in the income tax act, corporate income tax act, and electricity tax.

³⁰ In 2024, 278 million nEHS certificates (nEZs) were sold on the European Energy Exchange (EEX) at a fixed price of EUR 45 per nEZ with a total value of around EUR 12.5 billion. Around 17 million additional nEZs for 2023 were sold at the fixed price of the previous year (EUR 30 per nEZ) as part of the limited buyback option for nEHS certificates, generating a revenue of about EUR 0.5 billion.

On 15 May 2024, the Austrian Parliament stipulated that the Austrian national ETS will cease its operation by 31 December 2026, preceding the entry into force of EU ETS2 from 1 January 2027. If the launch of the EU ETS2 is to be delayed to 2028, the Austrian NEHG would continue to operate for another year. The Austrian Parliament also adopted measures to ease the transition between the two schemes for covered entities.

3.4. Factors affecting the price of the EU ETS2 allowances

In any carbon market, the price of allowances and their evolution over time result from the interplay between demand and supply of allowances. The supply equals the number of allowances put on the market. The demand for allowances depends on general factors affecting the demand for road transport and in buildings, such as the level of economic growth the end-user price of the fuels and electricity, spatial planning policies, climate and meteorological factors, etc.

Turning to the EU ETS2 market itself, the demand depends on the marginal abatement costs and the value of banking allowances for future use. While studies have been done on the marginal abatement costs in the sectors covered by the EU ETS2, these are still uncertain and could reduce significantly over time, for example with support from complementary policies and investments in decarbonised technologies, technological innovations, market upscale and production efficiencies, as well as changes in perception of consumers towards EVs or heat pumps.

Günther et al. (2024) list the following additional price drivers:

- The effectiveness of other legislation at EU level or in the Member States in reducing the emissions in the sectors covered by the EU ETS2. In addition, expectations of the market participants on whether the policies will be carried out as planned or not will play a role.
- The EU CO₂ emission performance standards for road vehicles or the Renewable Energy Directive are examples of complementary EU legislation. They will reduce the demand for fossil fuels, which will reduce the demand for EU ETS2 allowances, and will – ceteris paribus – lead to lower EU ETS2 prices. For the price to be relatively low, the complementary policies need to lead to substantial emission reductions. To be noted is that these complementary policies impose certain technologies/fuels to reduce CO₂ emissions. As the technologies are imposed, the emitters have less flexibility in the way in which they reduce their emissions. With stringent complementary policies, the EU ETS2 price will be lower, but the abatement costs (also considering the cost of the imposed technologies/fuels) may be higher, because there is less flexibility to reduce emissions in the way that is cheapest (Abrell et al., 2024).
- Market expectations. For example, while the evolution of the EU ETS2 cap has been set out in the Directive, the expectations of the market participants could be different, also affecting the price.
- The link with the EU ETS1. The EU ETS2 is set up as a separate system from the EU ETS1. However, the European Commission will assess in the future (by October 2031) the feasibility of integrating the two systems. In case an integration would be decided, the prices can be expected to converge. Possibly, this could happen even before the actual integration of the two systems. This depends, among others, on the expectations of the market participants, and on whether allowances issued before the integration can be traded on the linked market.
- The behaviour of the regulated entities or end users. For example, the actions of some market participants may be driven more by short-term prices instead of long-term price expectations. An additional complexity is that under the EU ETS2 the regulated entities who bid for the allowances are not the end consumers and therefore are different from the ones deciding on emission abatement. Possibly, this could lead to distortions in price formation.

The EU ETS2 was introduced to work in combination with complementary measures and policies in the ETS2 sectors, helping achieve the 2030 emission reduction targets. Indeed, according to the modelling for

the Commission Impact Assessment for the Fit for 55 package a complementary policy mix of carbon pricing and regulatory measures is the most cost-effective approach, addressing all barriers to decarbonisation and limiting the burden on households. Hence, the implementation of complementary policies and actions at national level, such as those set out in the National Energy and Climate Plans, will be key to deliver the expected emission reductions and will impact EU ETS2 prices. A shortfall in the implementation of regulatory policies and national measures would increase the abatement volumes achieved through carbon pricing, driving EU ETS2 prices upwards.

Box 3 The Assessment of the National Energy and Climate Plans

In terms of the current status of complementary policies, the Commission assessment of the final National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs) (EC, 2025c) indicates that, overall, Member States have presented significant improvements from their draft plans following Commission recommendations, raising the ambition. Collectively the EU is closing in on meeting the net GHG emission reduction target of -55% for 2030 compared to 1990 levels, as committed under the European Climate Law. According to Member States' projections, net emissions will decrease by around 54% by 2030, if the existing policies and measures as well as those set out in the NECPs are implemented alongside EU policies.

Nonetheless, ambition gaps remain across sectors. Emissions from sectors covered by the Effort Sharing Regulation (ESR), such as transport, buildings, agriculture, small industry and waste, are projected to decrease by around 38% by 2030, compared to 2005 levels. This demonstrates substantial progress from the draft plans, and on the way towards reaching the EU's 40% target. Five of the 23 assessed plans though project a gap towards the ESR national target, underscoring the need for more action in these Member States.

On energy efficiency, which affects the EU ETS2 sectors, in particular buildings, the final plans show progress equivalent to an overall 8.1% reduction in final consumption, but a gap of 31.1 million tonnes of oil equivalent (Mtoe) remains. This calls for more decisive action to reduce energy demand to reach the EU target of 11.7%.

3.5. Expected GHG emissions reductions from the EU ETS2

From 2005 to 2023, direct emissions covered by the EU ETS2 decreased by 37% and 36% in residential and non-residential buildings respectively and just 4.4% in road transport. Designed to drive decarbonisation in the private sector, the EU ETS2 aims to achieve a 42% reduction in fuel emissions by 2030 compared to 2005.

In general, in a cap-and-trade system such as the EU ETS2, emission reduction targets in the sectors covered are achieved by design, since the quantity of emissions is fixed (under the cap). Difficulties in decarbonisation do not lead to increased emissions, but to increased prices. As discussed in Section 3.2 mechanisms are in place and additional mechanisms have been proposed recently to avoid excessively high prices.

The Impact Assessment of the EC regarding the EU ETS2 (EC, 2021b) mentions that “the building sector responds better to the carbon price than road transport.” This also comes forward in modelling outcomes by Cambridge Econometrics (Stenning et al., 2020).

Generally, under the EU ETS2 the additional reductions³¹ can be expected to take place where it is cheaper to reduce emissions than to pay the higher fuel costs. A higher relative reduction of emissions could occur in the building sector compared to the road sector in view of relatively cheaper abatement possibilities such as fuel switch, more efficient boilers or improved insulation. In absolute terms, however, the reductions may be higher in the road transport sector.

Due to the relatively high fuel taxes for road transport in the EU Member States (see Box 5), it was already profitable to invest in energy efficiency improvements for road transport and hence the ‘low hanging fruit’ has been picked already in that sector. According to a global assessment by Goldman Sachs dating from February 2025 (Della Vigna et al., 2025), the weighted average marginal abatement cost³² in transport is around EUR 400 per tonne CO₂, in 2025, and EUR 350 per tonne CO₂ for electric passenger cars, compared to EUR 210 per tonne CO₂ in the buildings sector³³. These cost assessments evolve over time³⁴, and may also be substantially affected by changes in the geopolitical situation. However, in past assessments, technologies for abatement in road transport have consistently been on average more expensive than for buildings. Goldman Sachs also finds that the relative cost comparison between the two sectors remains valid with the assumption of more local production (which increases costs) or more imports from cheaper production regions (which reduces costs).

In an earlier assessment Goldman Sachs projected substantial battery price decreases by 2030, with the possibility of price parity for car buyers³⁵ in 2027-2026 in key European markets (Goldman Sachs, 2024). In China, the most advanced market, EVs accounted for close to 50% of new car sales in 2024 (IEA, 2025)³⁶, and are likely to overtake ICEs in sales in 2025 or 2026.

For road transport the emission reductions induced by decreasing fuel demand are also expected to be low because of the low fuel price elasticity (EC, 2021b) and the existing taxes which imply that the relative price increase in this sector will be lower than in the buildings sector. Overview studies of empirical work on price elasticities indicate that the average fuel price elasticity varies between -0.15 to -0.3 for the short run (1 year) and -0.3 to -0.8 for the long run (5 to 10 years) (Brons et al., 2008; Labandeira et al., 2017; Aklilu, 2020)³⁷. This means that in the short run an increase of the fuel price by 10% would reduce the fuel consumption by 1.5 to 3%. This short run fuel consumption may be reduced through a combination of

³¹ I.e. compared with a situation without the EU ETS2.

³² This indicator is calculated by weighting the marginal abatement cost of each abatement technology by the amount of emissions it can abate, and then averaging across all technologies. The marginal abatement cost refers to the cost of reducing an *additional* unit of emissions. It is the cost from the point of view of society, which differs from the cost of the end-user perspective (which is also affected by taxes/subsidies, and which entails a different discount rate for impacts that take place in the future).

³³ This corresponds with respectively EUR 401 per tonne CO₂ (transport), EUR 352 per tonne CO₂ (electric passenger cars) and EUR 214 tonne CO₂ (buildings)(exchange rate of 23 May 2025).

³⁴ For example, compared to the abatement cost assessment of Goldman Sachs for 2023 (Della Vigna et al., 2023), the abatement costs for passenger cars and biofuels have fallen by 2025, thanks to cost deflation and innovation in EV batteries and lower renewable fuel prices, but the costs for the abatement of emissions from heavy duty transport have increased, due to the update in the expected development of economies of scale for the EV technologies in that market segment. In the buildings sector the 2025 weighted average carbon abatement cost is estimated to be 10% lower than in 2023, because of a more favourable assessment of heat pumps compared to more expensive technologies.

³⁵ This analysis takes the end-user perspective, which also considers taxes and subsidies and uses another discount rate than in the analysis of the previous paragraph which takes a societal perspective.

³⁶ Of these new electric cars in China in 2024, about 10% were extended-range EVs, 30% were plug-in hybrid electric vehicles and 60% were battery electric cars. As factors behind this high uptake IEA (2025) refers to the improving price competitiveness of these cars, as well as to support programs for the car buyers.

³⁷ For information: the impact assessment of the EU ETS mentions a fuel price elasticity of -0.17 in the short run and -0.34 in the long run, and indicates that the fuel demand impact could be larger if market failures and barriers for decarbonisation are tackled, and with the transition to electric vehicles (EC, 2021b).

reactions: a limited decrease of vehicle travel, shifts to more fuel-efficient vehicles in multi-vehicle households and reduced speed. In the long run, a 10% fuel price increase would translate in further reduction in fuel consumption. These elasticities must however be used with caution to predict future fuel demand changes because they are based on historic observations for fossil fuel vehicles. In the future, when zero-emission cars become much more available and affordable, one can expect more elastic fuel demand responses. To be noted is that the fuel price elasticities also differ across countries, as indicated for example in the analysis of Aklilu for the EU (2020).³⁸ The underlying factors are not explored in that study, but economic theory suggests this may be related to factors such as the share of freight and passenger road transport (freight being less price sensitive), the availability of alternatives to car transport, the fuel price level compared to the electricity price, the fuel efficiency of the vehicle stock, cultural factors etc.

For the buildings sector the price elasticities are somewhat higher and the percentage increases in the energy price is also expected to be higher, given the current lower levels of taxation. Ewald et al. (2021) estimated price elasticities of -0.1 in the short run and -0.5 in the long run in the European residential building sector. For the EU, the only comparable estimate that has previously been estimated is the one by Ó Broin et al. (2015) that find an average long-run elasticity of -0.25 for residential heating demand for France, Italy, Sweden, and the UK. Price elasticities tend to be higher in the long run in households because of the time it takes to implement structural measures to reduce energy consumption. For district heating the long-run price elasticity is somewhat lower and depends on the functioning of the local energy infrastructure and household socio-economic and dwelling characteristics (Trotta et al., 2022)³⁹.

³⁸ For gasoline demand, Aklilu (2020) reports that the price elasticity ranges between -0.09 for Malta and -2.8 for Spain. For diesel it ranges between -0.02 for Denmark and -2.7 for Czechia. The author mentions that the results per country should be interpreted with caution due differences in data availability between the countries. In addition, fuel switching behaviour is not considered in the analysis.

³⁹ For information: the impact assessment of the EU ETS mentions a very low price elasticity in the short run and a price elasticity of -0.23 to -0.5 in the long run for heating fuels, and indicates that the demand impact could be larger if market failures and barriers for decarbonisation are tackled (EC, 2021b).

Box 4 How electricity-gas price differentials shape household heating technology choices.

Retail prices of electricity and natural gas for households in the EU are composed of three main components: the energy and supply, network charges, and taxes and levies (Eurostat, 2025b, 2025c). The first component covers wholesale energy costs, retail margins and other supply-related costs. The second component reflects transmission and distribution tariffs, and the third includes excise duties and value added tax (VAT) (Eurostat, 2025b, 2025c).

In the first half of 2025, average EU household electricity prices were EUR 28.7 per 100 kWh (Eurostat, 2025d) and natural gas prices were EUR 11.4 per 100 kWh (Eurostat, 2025e). Taxes and levies accounted for about 28% of the average electricity price, with shares ranging from negative values in countries applying subsidies (Ireland, Luxembourg, and Netherlands) to above 40 percent in others (Denmark, and Poland) (Eurostat, 2025b). For gas, taxes and levies represented around 31% on average, ranging from 5% in Croatia to 54% in the Netherlands. Although the shares for electricity and gas are comparable, the absolute tax burden is higher for electricity, averaging EUR 7.9 per 100 kWh, compared with EUR 3.6 per 100 kWh for gas, making the taxes and levies cost component in electricity more than double that in gas.

Cross country variation is largely driven by VAT and excise duties. The Energy Taxation Directive (EU, 2023e) sets minimum excise rates for electricity and heating fuels, while Member States may apply higher rates or differentiate them across consumer groups. The Energy Taxation Directive (EU, 2023e) sets minimum excise rates, and Member States may apply higher or differentiated rates. VAT, regulated at EU level by the VAT Directive (Council of the EU, 2006), is charged on the full energy bill, with some countries using reduced or temporary zero rates. These tax differences, combined with the fact that electricity is already covered by the EU ETS1 while natural gas is not yet subject to carbon pricing, contribute to higher retail electricity prices relative to gas. This gap is expected to narrow as the EU ETS2 is introduced. Furthermore, under the Energy Taxation Directive, Member States may apply preferential rates of excise duties to power generated from alternative energy sources. However, this is challenging to apply in practice, resulting in green electricity facing the same tax rate as carbon intensive electricity, limiting the extent to which retail prices reflect its lower environmental impact.

These structural and policy-driven differences in price components determine the electricity-to-gas price ratio faced by households and thereby influence investment decisions in heating technologies and other long-lived equipment. The EU average ratio was above 3 between 2020 and 2021, after which, the ratio stabilised downward, standing at 2.5 in the first half of 2025 (Eurostat, 2025e, 2025d). In 2025, 10 Member States continued to register a ratio above 3, with the highest values observed in Belgium, Romania, Hungary, Czechia and Croatia. In contrast, Sweden, Netherlands, Bulgaria, and Portugal had ratios below 2 in 2025. Gas price data for Poland are unavailable from 2024 onward.

A high retail electricity-to-gas price ratio is associated with lower heat pump uptake and slower fuel switching away from gas boilers (KfW Research, 2025). When the ratio falls towards values of about 2 to 2.5, efficient electric heat pumps become cheaper to operate over their lifetime than gas boilers for a typical dwelling, strengthening the economic case for investment in electrification (Heat Pump Association, 2024; KfW Research, 2025). In this context, the design of VAT and excise duties on electricity and gas, and the allocation of policy-related levies across fuels, directly affects households' expectations about future running costs, payback times and perceived risk of investing in low-carbon technologies. Stable and predictable tax structures that narrow the electricity-gas price gap are therefore an important enabling condition for households to respond to the carbon price signal in the EU ETS2 by investing in energy efficiency and switching from fossil-fuel based heating to electricity and other clean energy options.

3.6. The EU ETS2 within the wider EU policy landscape for road transport and buildings

The long-term decarbonisation strategy for the EU was set out in the **European Green Deal** communication (EC, 2019). With this strategy, the EU expressed its ambition to become the first climate-neutral continent by 2050. This ambition was put into a legal commitment with the EU Climate Law (EU, 2021) which binds the EU to achieving climate neutrality by 2050 and sets an intermediate economy-wide target of a net 55% reduction in GHG emissions by 2030 compared to 1990. To achieve this intermediary target the EU relies on overarching Union Policies, namely the EU ETS Directive, the Energy Taxation Directive (ETD), the Effort Sharing Regulation (ESR), the Renewable Energy Directive (RED), and Energy Efficiency Directive (EED).

The ambition level for transport is further detailed in the **Sustainable and Smart Mobility Strategy** (EC, 2020a). This introduces a roadmap for a sustainable and smart future for European transport, with an action plan to reduce the emissions from the transport sector by 90% by 2050. The Strategy indicates that to reach the climate targets “all policy levers must be pulled”. The strategy further specifies several milestones. By 2030, at least 30 million zero-emissions cars will drive on the European roads and by 2050 almost all cars, light commercial vehicles, buses and new heavy-duty vehicles will be zero-emission. To put this in perspective, in 2024 the number of battery electric cars in the EU-27 numbered 5.92 million or 2.2% of the total car fleet (EAFO, 2025). Also, modal shift is important in the Strategy which aims for a doubling of high-speed rail travel in 2030 and a fully operational, multimodal Trans-European Transport Network (TEN-T) for sustainable and smart travel with high-speed connectivity by 2050.

The **Renovation Wave Strategy** (EC, 2020b) reconfirms the objective of reducing GHG emissions by at least 60% in the building sector, its final energy consumption by 14%, and energy consumption for heating and cooling by 18% by 2030 compared to 2015. By 2050, the objective is to achieve a decarbonised, zero-emission building stock. The Energy Performance of Buildings Directive is instrumental to implement the necessary measures and actions that contribute towards these objectives, including a steady decrease of the average primary energy use in kWh per m² of the entire residential building stock aiming to transforming it into a zero-emission building stock by 2050.

The following subsections show the interactions between the new EU ETS2 together with the Social Climate Fund and other EU policies and measures aimed at decarbonising the EU economy. The relevant policies are categorised into three subsections: horizontal EU legislation, sectoral policies, and funding and Union energy poverty policies. **Horizontal EU legislation** consists of economy-wide frameworks or cross-sectoral instruments that set binding targets, pricing signals, or general rules. The EU acquis also comprises **sectoral policies** with targeted regulations addressing the (road) transport and buildings sectors. They include technical standards, infrastructure requirements, or sector-level CO₂ limits. Furthermore, the Union policy framework consist of funding measures that provide **financial support mechanisms** to facilitate the green and just transition. More information on the scope of the individual EU legislation is summarised in Annex 2.

3.6.1. Horizontal EU legislation and the EU ETS2 in road transport and buildings

The EU ETS1

For buildings, the EU ETS1, under Directive (EU) 2023/959 and Regulation (EU) 2023/957, already affects electricity prices since 2005, encouraging efficiency and renewable energy sources. The EU ETS1 however does not cover fossil fuel consumption in buildings - used mostly for heating. The EU ETS2 fills this gap by applying a carbon price to heating fuels, in turn passing a price signal in the perspective of accelerating energy efficiency and electrification of heating.

For road transport, part of the well-to-tank emissions from road transport are covered by the EU ETS1 even without the separate EU ETS2. This includes CO₂ emissions from the production of electricity used by

electric vehicles, and the CO₂ emissions from fuel production at refineries, for the part that is produced in stationary installations covered by the EU ETS1. This will be reflected in the price of electricity and fuels for road transport. With the expected increase in the number of electric vehicles in the future, an increasing share of road transport will therefore be (indirectly) covered by the EU ETS1. In addition to this, the EU ETS2 covers the exhaust gas CO₂ emissions from vehicles with an internal combustion engine, sending an additional price signal and making non fossil fuel-based mobility options more cost effective.

While EU ETS1 and EU ETS2 allowances remain separated and cannot be traded between the two systems, there is a possibility on further integration in future for some procedures such as monitoring, reporting and verification.

The Effort Sharing Regulation

The Effort Sharing Regulation (ESR) (EU) 2023/857 (EU, 2018) sets targets for each EU Member State to reduce GHG emissions in sectors currently not covered by emissions trading, namely transport, buildings, agriculture, waste and small industries. These sectors account for 66% of the EU's total GHG emissions (EEA, 2025a). The ESR with its annual emission limits for each EU Member State ensures that all Member States contribute in a fair and just manner to EU climate action. It is designed to distribute the national effort in line with Member States' GDP per capita, where Member States with a higher GDP per capita have higher emission reduction targets. The national targets result in a 2030 reduction target of 40% compared to 2005. Most Member States are currently below their annual emission limits, but with existing measures projections show a gap between the 2030 effort sharing emissions and 2030 targets (EEA, 2025a), requiring additional measures.

The EU ETS2 helps close this gap by targeting sectors where the ESR sectors' progress has been insufficient, particularly in transport and buildings. Unlike the ESR, which places responsibility on Member States, the EU ETS2 enforces carbon pricing at the EU level for fuel suppliers, shifting transport and buildings away from fossil fuels and imposing costs on emissions from these sectors.

It is critical to acknowledge that, although a carbon pricing system provides a stronger incentive to reduce EU-wide transport and building emissions than the ESR national targets, it is not sufficient on its own. Regulatory measures are needed to address market failures, invest in infrastructure, support the uptake of zero-emission cars and promote building renovation.

While the EU ETS2 creates a uniform carbon price across the EU, its impact on emissions in the road transport and building sectors will vary among Member States due to socio-economic and emission profile differences. This will help some Member States in overachieving their reduction targets under the ESR, while others might fall short, and countries can trade their annual emission allowances (AEAs) as part of the flexibility mechanism under the ESR. The resulting revenues from AEA trading can be used to finance abatement measures or mitigate negative social impacts of climate policies.

Figure 18 gives an impression of the size of ETS2 emissions on ESR emissions in 2023. While ETS2 emissions cover 84% of ESR emissions in Luxembourg, the share is only half as high in Ireland. The other relevant sectors in ESR emissions are displayed, too: agriculture, waste and emissions from energy and industry which are not covered in ETS1 and ETS2. These emissions form a very relevant part in Malta with 24% of ESR emissions, but even more in Island and Norway (31% and 32%).

Figure 18 EU ETS2 emissions as part of the ESR scope by countries in 2023.

Source: EEA Greenhouse Gases – data viewer (EEA, 2025b), EU Emissions Trading System (ETS) data viewer (EEA, 2025c), compilation by Öko-Institut 2025.

The Energy Efficiency Directive

The Energy Efficiency Directive (EU) 2023/1791 (EED) (EU, 2023e) mandates energy savings, such that the overall EU energy consumption in 2030 does not exceed 992.5 million tonnes of oil equivalent (Mtoe) for primary energy and 763 Mtoe for final energy. To reach the 2030 target, the pace of energy savings by Member States must accelerate, requiring further reductions of 131 Mtoe in final energy consumption and 216 Mtoe in primary energy consumption (EEA, 2025a). To achieve this, Member States have to implement efficiency measures, such as minimum energy performance standards and energy savings obligations, particularly benefiting energy-poor households. The Energy Efficiency Directive also stresses the importance of public awareness and protection for vulnerable consumers (Sibileau and Broer, 2022).

The Energy Efficiency Directive and EU ETS2 are complementary policies driving building decarbonisation through regulatory and market-based mechanisms. The EU ETS2 reinforces these goals by introducing carbon pricing in the building sector, encouraging lower energy consumption. As carbon costs rise, building operators must adopt efficiency measures, such as improved insulation and advanced heating, ventilation, and air-conditioning systems, to offset financial impacts, aligning with the EED’s Article 8 on efficiency measures.

The Social Climate Fund and Article 8 of the EED are complementary tools in addressing energy poverty and supporting vulnerable households. Article 8 of the EED obliges Member States to implement energy efficiency improvement measures specifically aimed at alleviating energy poverty. More specifically, under Article 8(3) of the revised EED, each Member State is required to dedicate a share of its cumulative end-use energy savings to priority groups, specifically those affected by energy poverty, vulnerable customers, and low-income households. Crucially, the minimum mandatory share for these priority groups must be at least equal to their proportion within the population, as reported in the National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP). For example, if 20% of households in a country are classified as energy-poor according to the NECP, then at least 20% of the total energy savings under Article 8 must benefit those households. This rule ensures an equitable distribution of efficiency gains, preventing disproportionate benefits going to better-off households and safeguarding vulnerable groups. In parallel, the Social Climate Fund provides targeted financial support to mitigate the social impacts of carbon pricing under EU ETS2, helping low-income households, transport users, and micro-enterprises to invest in energy efficiency and sustainable mobility.

The Renewable Energy Directive

The Renewable Energy Directive (RED) (EU) 2023/2413 (EU, 2023f) mandates renewable energy integration in transport and buildings, aligning with the EU's climate neutrality goals, as set in the Climate Law (EU, 2021). The average annual trend between 2005 and 2023 shows that past progress will not be sufficient to meet the EU's objective in 2030 of at least 42.5%⁴⁰ (EEA, 2024a).

The EU ETS2 will provide an additional incentive to increase renewable energy and decrease fossil-fuel consumption in transport and buildings, positively contributing to increasing the share of renewable energy in the EU. In buildings, the Renewable Energy Directive promotes renewable heating and cooling by requiring favourable regulations for solar, wind, and geothermal adoption. The RED also encourages modern district heating networks, which could also play an important role in the EU ETS2. In order to mainstream the use of renewable energy in the transport sector, Member States must either ensure that the share of renewable energy in transport is at least 29% by 2030 or that the GHG emission intensity is reduced by at least 14.5% by 2030, compared to a baseline.

The Energy Taxation Directive

The Energy Taxation Directive (ETD) (EC) 2003/96 (EU, 2003) establishes minimum tax rates for energy products, influencing fuel prices in buildings and transport sector and incentivising a shift towards cleaner energy sources.

The EU ETS2 gives similar financial incentives as energy fuel taxation⁴¹. The key difference lies in the policy design: under taxation, the fuel tax is set in advance and the resulting emission reductions are uncertain, as they depend on how consumers and producers respond to price signal. In contrast, under the EU ETS2, the emission cap acts as the key driver of the carbon price. This ensures that the overall emissions reduction target is achieved by design.

There is a clear overlap between the ETD and the EU ETS2 in their impact on fuel use and emissions in buildings and transport. This creates a complementary relationship, where both tools can reinforce incentives for decarbonisation. At the same time, coordination between the two is necessary to avoid inconsistent price signals, improve policy coherence, and to ensure that mitigating actions to address affordability take account of cumulative impacts.

⁴⁰ The share of renewables between 2005 and 2023 grew on average with 0.8 percentage points per year. In 2023 the share was 24.6% of gross final energy consumption. This means RES-total share will need to more than double compared to the previous five-year average, averaging 2.6 percentage points per year to align with the target trajectory (EEA, 2025a).

⁴¹ The existing fuel taxes take up this role already (even if they do not perfectly reflect the carbon content of the different fuels, and they are not the same in all Member States) as in many Member States they imply relatively high carbon prices for road transport. See also Box 5 on national energy taxation in this chapter.

Box 5 National energy taxation.

The Energy Taxation Directive sets the general framework for the taxation of energy in Member States, but Member States have flexibility in the taxes and levies they put on energy. A number of Member States have introduced explicit carbon taxes or a national ETS. In addition, there are levies and excise taxes on energy that are proportional to the quantity of fossil energy used. All of these instruments add up to what the OECD calls the net effective carbon tax (OECD, 2024a). This concept integrates the price signals that result from fuel excise taxes, carbon taxes and ETS. The following figures show the net effective carbon tax in 2023 for road transport (Figure 19) and for buildings (Figure 20) for 22 of the EU-27 Member States, Iceland and Norway, as well as for the EU-27 average, together with the composition of this tax rate.

The net effective carbon tax is in general substantially higher in road transport than in the buildings sector. The EU average level is EUR 184 per tonne CO₂ for road transport, compared to only EUR 27 per tonne CO₂ for the buildings sector. This implies that the EU ETS2 will lead on average to a larger relative change in end user prices in the buildings sector than in road transport.

In all Member States, except for one country considered here, the fuel excise tax is the most important component of the net effective carbon tax in road transport. As mentioned elsewhere in this report, some countries have implemented an explicit carbon tax or ETS for the sectors covered by the EU ETS2. A number of countries used fossil fuel subsidies that lowered the effective carbon tax. For the buildings sector the net effective carbon tax was even negative in some countries in 2023 because of these subsidies.

Another observation is that the net effective carbon tax rate differs across the EU Member States, with the largest differences for the buildings sector.

What is not visible in the graphs, but relevant to note, is that there are also differences in the net effective carbon taxes across the different types of fuel/energy within the road transport and buildings sectors.

Figure 19 Net effective carbon tax for road transport in a selection of EU27 Member States, Iceland and Norway, and for the EU27 as a whole – 2023 (EUR per tonne CO₂).

Source: ETC CM elaboration based on OECD (2024b).

National energy taxation (Continued)

Figure 20 Net effective carbon tax for the buildings sector in a selection of EU27 Member States, Iceland and Norway, and for the EU27 as a whole – 2023 (EUR per tonne CO₂).

Source: ETC CM elaboration based on OECD (2024b).

The fact that in 2023 there were (sometimes large) differences in the net effective carbon tax rates across the Member States, across the two sectors and across the fuels within these sectors implies that there is currently low cost-efficiency in abatement. This means that emission abatement does not take place at the lowest cost. The highest cost efficiency can be obtained if all sectors pay the same carbon price. Therefore, if the EU ETS2 allowance price is added to the current taxes, the highest cost-efficiency will still not be met (even if countries decide to reduce their carbon tax or replace their national ETS by the EU ETS2) (Ovaere and Proost, 2022).

3.6.2. Sectoral policies

CO₂ emission performance standards for road vehicles

The new CO₂ emission performance regulations (EU) 2023/851 and (EU) 2024/1610, for passenger cars, light commercial vehicles and heavy-duty vehicles (EU, 2024a, 2023b) set CO₂ emission standards for new vehicles, thereby reducing exhaust emissions from road transport and enabling the wider deployment of clean and affordable low- and zero-emission vehicles. The binding CO₂ emission performance standards apply to the average emissions of each manufacturer's new registered vehicles across the EU, rather than to each individual new vehicle or Member State. For cars and light commercial vehicles, the 2030 CO₂ target is as follows: -55% for new cars and -50% for new vans, compared to a reference period. From 2035, the target for both new cars and vans is 0 g/km. In the Automotive Package that was presented by the European Commission on 16 December 2025, the target for 2035 is reviewed, alongside other measures (EC, 2025d). By 2035 carmakers will need to comply with a 90% tailpipe emissions reduction target, while the remaining 10% emissions will need to be compensated through the use of low-carbon steel made in the EU, or from e-fuels and biofuels. The Automotive Package also includes a reduction of the 2030 CO₂ vans target from 50% to 40%. Regarding corporate vehicles, mandatory targets are set at the Member State level to support the zero- and low-emission vehicle uptake by large companies.

While the CO₂ emission performance regulation reduces the CO₂ emissions of new road vehicles, it does not provide incentives for drivers to reduce their CO₂ emissions by driving less, using alternative modes of transport, or by adopting eco-driving behaviour (e.g. driving more in electric mode in the case of plug-in electric hybrid (PHEV) drivers). Stricter standards can also lead to unintended effects, e.g. owners delaying replacement of old cars because of higher new vehicle prices (Jacobsen et al., 2023), the purchase of heavier cars⁴² or other rebound effects because of a lower energy cost per km.

The carbon price via the EU ETS2 is a complementary measure to these standards. It gives an incentive to all drivers to reduce their CO₂ emissions via all possible abatement options: by driving less, by driving more in electric mode in the case of PHEV drivers, by choosing more efficient vehicles, by scrapping older vehicles and by choosing less carbon intensive fuels.

The interaction of the emission standards with the EU ETS2 also goes in the opposite direction: as the new vehicles with lower emission factors penetrate in the vehicle stock, the exhaust CO₂ emissions of road transport will fall, thereby contributing to reaching the cap of the EU ETS2. Ceteris paribus, this will have a downward pressure on the carbon price under the EU ETS2.

As stated in the Political Guidelines for the European Commission 2024-2029, in the context of the revision of the CO₂ emission standard regulation, the Commission will take a technology neutral approach in which e-fuels have a role to play to reach climate neutrality. However, these fuels are still under development and there is great uncertainty about their future availability, environmental impact, and cost (Grahm et al., 2022).

Alternative Fuel Infrastructure Regulation

The Alternative Fuel Infrastructure Regulation (AFIR) (EU) 2023/1804 (EU, 2023g), in combination with the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) (EU, 2024b) reinforce the uptake of zero- and low-emission vehicles by increasing the availability of charging and hydrogen refuelling infrastructure of the desired quality, and the user-friendliness of the charging services.

The Toll Directive for road transport

The Toll Directive or Eurovignette Directive (EU) 2022/362 (EU, 2022) allows for CO₂ differentiation of road charges. The preamble of the Toll Directive mentions that “the Commission should, where appropriate, propose the amendment of provisions on variation of charges according to CO₂ emissions and of external-cost charging for CO₂ emissions, in order to prevent double charging through different carbon-pricing instruments.”

Energy Performance of Buildings Directive

The Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) (EU) 2024/1275 (EU, 2024b) serves as a tool to guide Member States towards a zero-emission building stock by 2050. Article 9 introduces minimum Energy Performance Certificate standards (F by 2027, E by 2030), and Article 14 ensures free access to building data, facilitating energy performance monitoring.

The EU ETS2 reinforces the EPBD's long-term goals by incentivising building renovations and efficiency measures through price signal making investments in energy efficiency financially more cost effective. While the EPBD sets regulatory frameworks for building energy performance, EU ETS2's carbon pricing (Squire Patton Boggs, 2024) pushes building owners toward renovations and integration of renewable

⁴² New passenger cars have become heavier over time, both including and excluding electric cars (Pardi, 2022; Tietge et al., 2024). Related to this, Reynaert (2021) found that in the past firms mainly used technology adoption and gaming of emission tests to decrease emissions, rather than shifting the sales mix or downsizing.

heating systems to reduce costs, aligning with EPBD's Zero Energy Buildings targets. As energy-poor households may struggle to invest in building energy efficiency upgrades (Sibileau and Broer, 2022), the EPBD specifies that Member States have to provide financial support to address market barriers. As a priority, this should target vulnerable households, people affected by energy poverty and people living in social housing. The EU ETS2 can help bridge this gap further by reinvesting revenues via the Social Climate Fund into financial aid, technical assistance, and advisory services. While the EPBD lacks deep renovation mandates, the EU ETS2 can accelerate retrofits through carbon costs.

Ecodesign and Energy Labelling Directive

Ecodesign and Energy Labelling Directive (EC) 2009/125 and Regulation (EU) 2017/1369 is an informational regulation that aims to increase the energy efficiency of products, reducing their overall environmental impacts, promoting the use of better performative energy-related products within the EU, and supporting consumers with information, allowing them to select the product with less environmental impact (EHPA, n.d.). This regulation consists of white goods, lighting, and products used in buildings for heating, cooling and ventilation systems.

3.6.3. Funding policies

The Social Climate Fund was created to mitigate potential economic and social impacts of the EU ETS2 on vulnerable households, vulnerable micro-enterprises and vulnerable transport users of higher fuel prices for a socially fair transition towards climate neutrality. It is however not the only European funding available to mitigate the social consequences of the green transition. Climate and energy-related EU funding forms part of the traditional EU cohesion policy under the multi-annual financial framework, including the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), for investments in the social and economic development of all EU regions and cities, and the Cohesion Fund (CF), for investments in the less prosperous EU countries. For the period 2021-2027, a minimum of 30% of the EU budget should be earmarked for mainstreaming climate objectives. Specifically for vulnerable households, the European Social Fund Plus has been established. Between 2021 and 2027, the ERDF, the CF, the Just Transition Fund and the European Social Fund Plus dedicate approximately EUR 39.7 billion into investments focusing on energy efficiency and decarbonisation, including high-efficiency co-generation, district heating and cooling or renewable energy resources (EC, 2023b).

Complementary programmes and funds for adaptive support to prevent psychological and social effects (Strambo et al., 2022) such as European Skills Agenda, the Recovery and Resilience Facility, the EU Social Fund+ and the ERDF can be mobilised by Member States for transitional assistance.

Via the Recovery and Resilience Fund, Member States allocated approximately EUR 73 billion to energy efficiency measures, including building renovations (EC, 2023c). The National Recovery and Resilience Plans are developed by EU Member States to support economic recovery post-COVID-19 while aligning with the EU Green Deal objectives, hence providing short-term recovery and funding mechanisms. In line with the EU guidance on the Social Climate Plans, Member States should align the Social Climate Plan with their National Recovery and Resilience Plan.

4. Towards a Green Transition – Leaving No One Behind

Key messages:

- There are different decarbonisation strategies, both technological as behavioural, readily available in the building and transport sector that can be implemented to reduce greenhouse gas emissions in line with the emission trajectory that the EU ETS2 imposes.
- To ensure that the decarbonisation in the transport and building sectors is accelerated requires further addressing the different financial and systemic barriers, via a diverse set of financial and regulatory policies and measures.
- The EU ETS2 is already complementary with other EU policies that are aimed at decarbonising the road transport and buildings sectors. This coherence will also have to be ensured with local, regional and national policies and measures.
- As any carbon price mechanism, the EU ETS2 has an inherent distributional effect, affecting disproportionately vulnerable households, unless corrective measures are implemented.
- The Social Climate Fund, supplied by the revenues generated by the EU ETS2, and National Social Climate Plans will play a pivotal role via targeted financial support, subsidies, or compensation mechanisms to help the vulnerable citizen adopting low carbon options, ensuring both social fairness and maintaining support for the policy.
- EU ETS2 revenues will have to be used efficiently to offset cost impacts, improve energy efficiency, and finance climate transition measures for low-income groups. Social Climate Fund shall support vulnerable groups to cope with higher energy costs, while Member States must direct revenues to climate and energy measures, especially for those most affected.
- Engaging with citizens, businesses, and policymakers ensures transparency, fairness, and public support for EU ETS2, addressing concerns about potential economic and social impacts.

4.1. Introduction

The implementation of the EU ETS2 presents an incentive for end-users in reducing their GHG emissions. By creating a price signal, the system encourages investments in building renovations and zero-/low-emissions mobility. Emissions reductions can also be achieved through efficiency improvement, shifts to low- or non-emission technologies, and behavioural changes in the short- and long-term. These measures need to take place not only at individual, household, or enterprise level, but also require broader private and public investments, for example, district heating networks, collective neighbourhood renovations, and public transport, to address the systemic barriers for decarbonising buildings and road transport.

While technological solutions are available, end-users often face significant barriers, most notably the high upfront investment costs required to avoid increased energy or fuel expenses. The disparity between the immediate increase in operational costs due to carbon pricing and the (often substantial) capital expenditure needed for emissions-reducing technologies creates a financial barrier for some end-users. In buildings, there is also a misalignment between those who bear the costs and those who receive the benefits, particularly within the context of landlord-tenant contractual relationships. This also creates a misalignment between short-term price signals from carbon pricing and long-term investments needed for adopting low-carbon solutions, particularly among vulnerable groups with limited access to capital. This financial gap can limit the broader effectiveness of the EU ETS2, which implies that the EU ETS2 requires supporting policies to overcome barriers, especially for the most vulnerable groups.

The EU ETS2 will generate substantial revenues that can be used to address exactly these barriers and provide Member States with funding to finance support measures. These funds can help lower upfront investment costs, facilitate the adoption of clean technologies and ease the transition for vulnerable groups and the wider population. The Social Climate Fund is designed to direct funds to vulnerable groups. Yet the effectiveness of this approach will depend on how revenues are allocated and translated into concrete and well-targeted measures within the national Social Climate Plans.

Past experiences suggest that while public support for climate action is strong in principle, acceptance of specific policies depends largely on whether their social impacts are perceived as fair. These policies especially run the risk of being opposed by citizens when their costs are unevenly spread across society, while redistribution to low-income households helps to bridge such gaps (Tathan & Peters, 2023). It will therefore be critical for maintaining public trust to ensure that EU ETS2 revenues are visibly and effectively used to support both equity and emission reductions.

This chapter is structured as follows. The first sections examine the existing indicators used to assess energy and transport poverty or vulnerability. It then explores the potential adverse impacts of the EU ETS2, both from a general perspective and in terms of how these impacts may disproportionately affect vulnerable groups, by analysing potential distributional effects. The chapter proceeds to identify existing decarbonisation options in the road transport and buildings sectors as possible responses to the price signal generated by the EU ETS2. Finally, it discusses the role of the Social Climate Fund and national Social Climate Plans in supporting end-users in the decarbonization path, while mitigating potential negative impacts.

4.2. Indicators for the assessment of energy/transport poverty and vulnerability of households and transport users

The concept of energy poverty was first introduced in EU policy in the Directive on common rules for the internal electricity market (EU, 2009). Since then, the EU recognised the need for the green transition to be fair and just and the concept of energy poverty was included in key EU legislation (e.g. the Energy Efficiency Directive and Energy Performance of Buildings Directive) and addressed in specific actions, e.g. the Energy Poverty Observatory and Energy Poverty Advisory Hub (EPAH). The issue was put prominently on the agenda during the COVID-19 crisis and the surge in energy prices following the Russian invasion in Ukraine, which led to a growing number of households unable to keep their homes adequately warm. Approximately 40 million Europeans faced energy poverty in 2022, a significant increase from 2021, particularly affecting lower-income households. Vulnerable groups, including families with children, persons with disabilities, and single-parent households, were disproportionately affected (EC, 2023b). People in the lower income quintiles may lack the financial means to transition to greener alternatives or more energy-efficient infrastructure. Households already at risk of energy poverty also tend to present very low elasticity of demand, particularly for heating needs. This means that an increase in carbon pricing may not result in a reduction of energy consumption and CO₂ emissions as intended, but rather in the complete elimination of space heating, which could have adverse effects on the health and wellbeing of these households.

Without adequate support to help energy/transport poor and vulnerable households adapt to the changes that carbon pricing will bring, the EU ETS2 risks increasing the cost of living and deepening existing socio-economic inequalities. It is therefore important to monitor its effects.

The Social Climate Fund Regulation (EU) 2023/955 (EU, 2023d) incorporates definitions of energy and transport poverty and vulnerability of households, micro-enterprises and transport users.

When addressing energy/transport poverty and vulnerabilities, a target oriented approach that identifies the specific characteristic of vulnerable groups, creates a fair and inclusive ground (Noka et al., 2025).

Improving the collection and use of data on e.g. energy efficiency, carbon intensity and household characteristics will help identify the most vulnerable populations (Noka et al., 2025) the most relevant to be targeted by action aiming at protecting them from any adverse effects of the EU ETS2.

Collecting relevant data is key to identify and address energy/transport poverty and target relevant households. To enhance the social and environmental effectiveness of policies, it is essential to consider key contextual factors like income, location, household composition, and employment status. Measures should be tailored to vulnerable groups based on these variables to ensure both greenhouse gas reduction and social fairness, which in turn boost public acceptance (EEA and Eurofound, 2021). Recent and upcoming ad hoc modules of European statistics such as those on households' ability to maintain comfortable indoor temperatures or afford adequate energy offer valuable insights at national and regional levels. With climate change increasing the risk of heatwaves, it is important to understand households' full energy needs to develop effective, targeted policies (EU, 2023h). That's why Member States should equip themselves with proper information system; and ensure data quality, transparency, and use standardised indicators, including in terms of income levels. Establishing and empowering national energy poverty observatories involving various stakeholders can help monitor and address energy poverty more effectively (EU, 2023h).

Although there is broad agreement on the need for a unified assessment approach to enhance the understanding of energy and transport poverty and vulnerability, many Member States still need to establish a methodology for assessing and monitoring these issues. Others already have more experience. For example, the French National Observatory on Energy Poverty (ONPE) (ONPE, n.d.) collects and analyses data on energy consumption, housing conditions, and household income to identify vulnerable populations. ONPE claims to have the best practice in identifying energy poor households and providing tailored support (Bosseboeuf et al., 2023). One more attractive feature of its approach is France also does multistakeholder management for effective coordination.

There is no single universally accepted method for defining or measuring energy/transport poverty in the EU. Different institutions and initiatives use varying sets of indicators, reflecting the multi-dimensional nature of the issue (Widuto, 2023). Due to the complexity of energy/transport poverty and vulnerability, to effectively address these issues across the EU, a clear definition and robust indicators are essential for making consistent monitoring and targeted policymaking dependent on well-defined concepts and harmonised data (Maier and Dreoni, 2024). Although the Energy Efficiency Directive provides a list of four indicators for energy poverty, these are not uniformly applied. These are: arrears on utility bills, low absolute energy expenditure, high share of energy expenditure in income, and inability to keep home adequately warm (Bouzarovski and Thomson, 2020). The EU Energy Poverty Observatory (now the Energy Poverty Advisory Hub) also uses a broader set of primary and secondary indicators (EC, n.d.), which capture different dimensions of the issue. The Energy Poverty Advisory Hub (EPAH) provides online and targeted training and support to stakeholders, including to local governments, on energy poverty. Their work on indicators is also helpful to Member States to choose and articulate indicators at national and local level.

The European Commission (2023c, 2023b) offers detailed guidance on how to identify and define energy poverty and determine when a considerable share of households is affected. It outlines a framework of 13 potential indicators that Member States can draw upon, choosing those most applicable and accessible in their specific circumstances to assess the extent of energy poverty nationally. These indicators encompass multiple dimensions of the issue and can be supplemented with other data sources to capture local conditions more accurately, for instance, the prevalence of excessive indoor temperatures during summer, the influence of gender and ethnic disparities, and combined analyses of income levels and energy use to gain deeper insights into the affordability problems experienced by households facing energy poverty. Further work was done by EC (2024c), including a prioritisation of the data/indicators considered to be more useful. The key indicators identified in their study (EC, 2024c) are presented in the summary table below, which draws on the datasets of the Statistics on Income and Living Conditions (SILC) and Household

Budgetary Survey (HBS), and obtained based on EC recommendations and indicators of the Energy Poverty Advisory Hub.

Table 2 List of energy poverty indicators based on EC’s 2024 study.

Database	EC recommended indicators	EPAH indicators and others
SILC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inability to keep home adequately warm (IKW) • Inability to keep home adequately warm and at risk of poverty (IKW_AROP) • Arrears on utility bills (AUB) • Arrears on utility bills and at risk of poverty (AUB_AROP) • Presence of leak, damp or rot (LDR) • Presence of leak, damp or rot and at risk of poverty (LDR_AROP) • At risk of poverty (AROP) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Equalised disposable income (EPAH) • Total housing costs (EPAH) • Housing cost overburden (EPAH) • Dwelling too dark (EPAH) • Dwelling comfortably warm in winter (Cool) (EPAH) • Dwelling comfortably cool in summer (Warm) (EPAH)
HBS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2M (share of energy expenditure in income is twice the national median) • M/2 (absolute energy expenditure is below half the national median) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LHC – Low-income, high-cost (income after energy expenditure is below the poverty line (60% of median income)) (other)

Source: EC (2024c).

Regarding transport poverty, a recent study for the European Commission by Cludius et al. (2024a) reports a wide range of indicators, with a careful discussion of their relative merits. They conclude that several indicators are needed to capture “the different dimensions of transport poverty (availability, accessibility, affordability, as well as the cross-cutting issues of adequacy)” (p. 78). They consider the indicators listed in Table 3.

Table 3 List of transport poverty indicators as defined in the EC’s 2024 study.

Dimension of transport poverty	Indicator
Availability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Materially and socially deprived individuals who own a car • Public transport stop is ‘too far away’ • ‘Very’ difficult access to public transport • Access to public transport is too difficult for persons with reduced mobility
Accessibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One-way commute to work of more than 30 minutes
Affordability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enforced lack of a car • Public transport is ‘too expensive’ • Expenditure on transport exceeds 6% of total expenditures of a household (6%) • Share of total expenditures spent on transport by a household exceeds twice the national median (2M)

Source: Cludius et al. (2024a).

To assess the extent of transport poverty, good data are needed. The main data sources used by Cludius et al. (2024a) are the SILC, the European Quality of Life Survey and the household budget surveys. However, recent data are not always available for the construction and assessment of the indicators. The study recommends the collection of reliable data and to repeat this at regular intervals, such that the evolution over time can be monitored. They also point to the need for better survey data and spatial data covering all EU Member States. Geospatial data on the location of essential services and transport networks and data on important target groups (e.g. women) are especially useful. Besides this, the EU-analysis can also be enriched by data collected at national and local level.

Other studies, such as for example Eden et al. (2023), Schumacher et al. (2025) and Cludius et al. (2024b), consider additional indicators regarding transport poverty and vulnerability of transport users, and discuss the (dis)advantages of the different indicators.

4.3. Exploration of elements affecting the potential impacts of the EU ETS2

Carbon pricing policies need complementary measures that correct for distributional effects that may disproportionately impact low-income households, vulnerable populations, and certain geographic regions. These groups often depend more heavily on fossil fuels and lack the financial means to invest in energy efficiency upgrades or transition to greener technologies. Adequate safeguards are crucial to ensure the transition does not exacerbate existing social inequalities, creating barriers to equitable access to energy, mobility, and other essential services.

Energy and mobility poverty and vulnerability have become increasingly pressing issues in the EU over recent years. The COVID-19 pandemic, followed by a sharp rise in energy prices due to the Russia's war against Ukraine, has further exacerbated an already challenging situation for many European households.

4.3.1. Elements affecting average impacts across Member States

The average impact on households in Member States depends firstly on the average carbon intensity of energy demand in residential buildings and road transport. The following graph shows the **average CO₂ emissions per capita for 2023 related to household fossil fuel use for space heating, hot water, cooking and transport** in the EU Member States, Iceland and Norway.⁴³ In this graph the EU Member States are ordered by the median equivalised disposable income per capita, in purchasing power standard (PPS) in 2023^{44,45}. The data for household emissions do not cover emissions from district heating, electricity supply (e.g. for cooling) or public transport. The emissions from large district heating facilities and electricity plants are covered by the EU ETS1. So are the emissions from electricity used in public transport. However, the emissions from smaller district heating plants and fossil fuel use in public transport are not yet covered by the EU ETS1.

⁴³ For a similar analysis, see Eden et al. (2023).

⁴⁴ Eurostat explains this concept as follows: "To consider differences in household size and composition and thus enable comparisons of income levels across countries and population groups, the concept of equivalised disposable income is used. This measure is based on the total net (also referred to as disposable) household income divided by the number of 'equivalent adults' in the household, using a standard (equivalence) scale. Eurostat employs the 'modified OECD scale', which assigns a weight of 1.0 to the household head, 0.5 to each additional adult (aged 14 and over), and 0.3 to each child (aged under 14). The weights are summed to calculate an equivalised household size, which is then used to divide the total household income and determine the equivalised disposable income attributed to each household member."

Regarding purchasing power parities: "PPS is the technical term used by Eurostat for the common currency in which national accounts aggregates are expressed when adjusted for price level differences using PPPs."

Source: (Eurostat, 2024a, n.d.)

⁴⁵ In 2023 the median equivalised income per capita ranged between EUR 10 670 PPS for Slovakia and EUR 34 777 PPS for Luxemburg, with the median value for the EU-27 at EUR 19 955 PPS. Not corrected for the differences in the cost of living, these incomes are respectively EUR 9 214, EUR 47 636 and EUR 20 350.

Figure 21 CO₂ emissions per capita for space heating, hot water, cooking and transport of private households, 2019.

Note: Average CO₂ emissions per capita for 2023 related to household fossil fuel use for space heating/hot water/cooking and transport. The data for household emissions do not cover emissions from district heating, electricity supply (e.g. for cooling) or public transport. Household transport emissions cover other private transport modes than road transport (e.g. private boats), but their share is small.

The countries are ordered according to their median net equivalised income in PPS per capita in 2023.

Source: ETC CM analysis based on Eurostat indicators ilc_di03 (median equivalised net income per capita in PPS, data for 2023), tps00001 (Population on 1 January 2023) and env_ac_ainah_r2 (Air emissions accounts by NACE Rev. 2 activity, data for 2023).

The information for the household emissions per capita can also be visualised on the following map, which presents this for the sum of the emissions related to space heating, hot water, cooking and transport by households.

Figure 22 Household emissions per capita, in tonne CO₂ emissions per capita in 2023.

Note: Average CO₂ emissions per capita for 2023 related to household fossil fuel use for heating/ hot water/cooking and transport. The data for household emissions do not cover emissions from district heating, electricity supply (e.g. for cooling) or public transport. Household transport emissions cover other private transport modes than road transport (e.g. private boats), but their share is small.

Source: ETC CM analysis based on Eurostat indicators tps00001 (Population on 1 January 2023) and env_ac_ainah_r2 (Air emissions accounts by NACE Rev. 2 activity, data for 2023).

It is clear that the household CO₂ emissions per capita vary a lot across Member States. Generally, they are larger in higher income countries, but several other factors are influencing the emission level per capita. For space heating, hot water, and cooking, the lowest household CO₂ emissions per capita are found in countries with a large share of district heating systems and/or electricity (heat pumps) (e.g. Bulgaria, Sweden, Finland)⁴⁶ and countries with a low space heating demand (e.g. Malta, Portugal). Concerning the latter point, the following graph gives the five-year average heating degree days in the EU countries.

⁴⁶ A map with an overview of the share of district heating in each country can be found here: <https://www.wedistrict.eu/interactive-map-share-of-district-heating-and-cooling-across-europe/>

Figure 23 Annual average heating degree days in Member States, based on period 2019-2023.

Source: ETC CM analysis based on Eurostat dataset for cooling and heating degree days by NUTS 3 region - annual data (Eurostat, 2024b).

High space heating/hot water/cooking emissions per capita are found in countries with a high space heating demand and a high share of fossil fuel heating (e.g. Belgium, Czechia, Germany, Hungary, Italy, the Netherlands, Luxembourg and Poland).

For transport the emissions per capita are the lowest in Bulgaria, the Czech Republic and Malta. They are the highest in Cyprus, Lithuania, Estonia, Slovenia and Ireland. The transport emissions are influenced by the annual car mileage per capita, in combination with the age of the vehicle fleet, which affects the fuel efficiency of the vehicles, and the share of electric vehicles. These factors are influenced by many other factors such as the income level, the availability of alternatives to car transport, the cost of car transport versus the other transport modes, congestion levels, spatial planning policies, among others.

The relative impact across Member States will also depend on the **impact of the EU ETS2 on the price of fuels for heating and road transport**. This varies across Member States due to differences in the net effective carbon tax rates that are currently in place (see Box 5Box 5). With the introduction of the EU ETS2, Austria and Germany will replace their national ETS by the EU ETS2. Compared to the 2025 level of the national ETS systems, the net impact of an EU ETS2 price will therefore be lower than for other EU Member States that have a lower net effective carbon tax rate. Countries with a carbon tax (such as e.g. Portugal) may consider reducing or abolishing this tax, also resulting in a lower relative impact of the EU ETS2 on fuel prices.

The impact per country will also vary within the country across income groups, regions and other characteristics of the population, as discussed in the next section.

4.3.2. Elements affecting the distributional impacts within Member States

Some groups of people are more vulnerable to fuel price changes than others and different indicators are used to assess the level of vulnerability. Here we present a number of self-reported indicators based on the SILC (Statistics on Income and Living Conditions), in addition to indicators that have been derived from the household budget surveys (HBSs). The SILC give information on lived experience and perception of deprivation (people feel they cannot afford something). The limitation of such data is that cultural, climatic or social norms affect perceptions. Some households may underreport and others may overreport

deprivation. The household budget surveys give information on actual spending patterns, and therefore allow for a more precise quantification of the economic burdens. However, the indicators based on the HBSs do not capture whether households feel or are deprived (for example, households under-consuming energy to keep costs down). Given the advantages and disadvantages of both approaches, it is useful to combine them.

Many indicators are being used to assess the severity of energy/transport poverty and vulnerability, each with their own (dis)advantages. Below, only a selection is reported. For a broader set of indicators and a more detailed discussion, the reader is referred to the studies mentioned in Section 4.2.

The data reported below present the situation in the (recent) past that does not account for demand changes that could potentially be brought about by the EU ETS2 nor for future improvements that can be expected in energy efficiency and emission intensity as a result of other EU and national policies, or the future evolution of income levels in the EU Member States.

Indicators reflecting self-reported income and living conditions of households

The first type are self-reported indicators. Below, data are reported for a selection of indicators. These present information on the share of the population (or different subgroups of the population):

- with arrears on utility bills,
- unable to keep warm,
- who cannot afford a personal car,
- who are socially and materially deprived and own a car

The Statistics on Income and Living Conditions (SILC) indicate that in the EU-27 on average 6.9% of the population report to have arrears on utility bills, 10.6% are unable to keep warm and 5.6% cannot afford a personal car. This corresponds to approximately 30.9 million, 47.5 million and 25.1 million of Europeans, respectively⁴⁷. The latter group will not be hit by higher car fuel prices, but it will become more difficult to have a personal car for people who cannot afford to have one today. Given the supply of transport options, having a car is often still essential in getting to work or having access to services.

Underlying these averages for the EU-27 are large differences across the Member States, as can be seen in the next graph. The level of vulnerability by country differs according to the indicator that is used, as each indicator focuses on a specific issue. The share of people with arrears on the utility bills ranges between 1.2% (the Netherlands) and almost 33% (Greece). The share of people who report that they are unable to keep the home inadequately warm ranges between 2.1% (Luxembourg) and 20.8% (Portugal). A personal car is unaffordable to 1.2% (Cyprus) to 16.6% (Romania) of people. For three countries the share of people for all three indicators is higher than the EU average: Bulgaria, Romania and Greece. Eight countries have a lower share of people than the EU-average for all three indicators: Czechia, Poland, Italy, Slovenia, Malta, the Netherlands, Austria and Luxembourg.

⁴⁷ Considering that the EU-27 population in 2023 was 448.3 million, according to Eurostat indicator `demo_gind` (Eurostat, 2025f).

Figure 24 Selected SILC data related to energy poverty or mobility poverty, 2023.

Note: The countries are ordered according to their median net equivalised income in PPS per capita in 2023.

Source: ETC CM analysis based on SILC – Eurostat indicators ilc_mdcs01 (Eurostat, 2025g), ilc_mdcs07(Eurostat, 2025h), ilc_mddu05(Eurostat, 2025i).

Cludius et al. (2024a), based on Mattioli (2017), report an indicator of transport poverty could be considered to be the reverse of the unaffordability of a personal car, namely the share of the population that is materially and socially deprived and that owns a car (which Mattioli (2017) labelled “forced car ownership”). In 2022 this share was 14.6% in the EU-27 and ranged from 4.6% in Sweden to 37.9% in Greece. The indicator was above the EU average in eight Member States: Greece, Cyprus, Spain, Portugal, Bulgaria, France, Romania and Ireland.

Figure 25 Share of the population that is socially and materially deprived and owns a car.

Source: Cludius et al. (2024b).

No recent EU-wide data on the affordability of regular use of public transport or the level of difficulty in accessing public transport is available, unfortunately.

When considering the SILC indicators according to gender, female-led households are more likely to experience problems for heating/cooling their home than male-led households on average. Based on the SILC for 2019 8.1% of female-led households are unable to keep their home warm (as opposed to 7.5% for male-led) while 8.3% of female-led households report to have arrears in utility bills (7.2% for male-led) (Koukoufikis & Uihlein (2022) as reported in Murauskaite-Bull et al. (2023)).

The self-reported indicators give an indication of the share of people that are currently experiencing problems heating/cooling their home or personal transport. However, they do not allow to project how these indicators would change as a result of the EU ETS2, on its own or in combination with the other national policies and EU policies that have been put in place of the future.

Indicators based on household expenditure

Many indicators are constructed on the basis of data from the household budget surveys. The following are reported below:

- 2M indicator: Share of energy / transport in total expenditures is more than twice the national median
- 2M x AROP: Share of energy / transport in total expenditures is more than twice the national median AND household is at risk of poverty (AROP), i.e. total expenditures are less than 60% of the national median. This is done because indicators without such an income threshold are likely to overestimate the share of vulnerable households by including also households in higher income deciles. The AROP is but one type of income threshold that could be used. The choice of an appropriate threshold is an area for further research.
- Low-income-high-cost indicator (LIHC indicator): the share of households that spend more on energy or personal transport than the national median and that fall below the poverty line after energy expenses or personal transport expenses have been paid.
- Share of spending on energy/transport as share of total spending, by gender

To be noted, is that, for example in the case of transport, people who do not travel much because of financial reasons are not captured in the previous list of indicators, as it concerns people who do spend on transport relatively more than the average household. For this dimension other indicators are available (see the reports referred to in Section 4.2), but they are not reported here.

The graphs below give an indication of the extent of vulnerability to higher energy costs. The impact of the EU ETS2 will depend on the price level of the EU emission allowances, as well as on the possibility of people to change their energy demand for heating/cooling and personal transport in response to this. Therefore, the graphs below only give a first indication of the share of the population that could be most vulnerable⁴⁸.

➤ 2M and 2M x AROP indicators

Cludius et al. (2024b) have recently assessed the 2M and 2M x AROP indicators for 10 EU Member States. However, some results have to be interpreted with caution due to missing information. In the two figures below this is indicated with shaded bars. In the case of heating, the share of vulnerable households according to the 2M indicator is the lowest in Poland and Czechia, with a share of about 12%. The share is the highest in Spain and Denmark (at around 22%). For transport, when considering the countries for

⁴⁸ To be noted also is that also without the EU ETS2, the indicators can be expected to change in the future, as a result of other national and EU policies to decarbonise these two sectors, as well as changes in income levels.

which no data are missing⁴⁹, the share of vulnerable people according to the 2M indicator is the highest in Bulgaria (36.6%), and the lowest in Germany (11.2%).

When combining the 2M indicator with an income threshold for those at risk of poverty (AROP), the share of vulnerable households decreases significantly, both for heating and for transport.

Figure 26 Share of vulnerable households related to heating according to the 2M and 2M x AROP indicators.

Note: Cludius et al. (2024b) point out that IE, PL, and RO have to be treated with caution due to missing information in the HBS data. These countries' bars are shaded. According to Eurostat rules, CZ & DK should be flagged for the indicator '2M x AROP' due to a low number of observations (20-49 observations).

Source: Cludius et al. (2024b).

⁴⁹ The authors note that the high value of the 2M indicator in Denmark should be treated with caution as the data include a very high share of households with zero transport expenditures.

Figure 27 Share of vulnerable households related to heating according to the 2M and 2M x AROP indicators.

Note: Cludius et al. (2024b) point out that DK and ES have to be treated with caution due to missing information in the HBS data. These countries' bars are shaded. According to Eurostat rules, CZ and DK should be flagged for the indicator '2M x AROP' due to a low number of observations (20-49 observations).

Source: Cludius et al. (2024b).

➤ **Low-income-high-cost indicator (LIHC-indicator) according to income decile**

The following graphs present the share of the population that is vulnerable to higher energy costs for heating fuels and electricity⁵⁰ (Figure 28) and personal transport (Figure 29) according to the LIHC-indicator, with a distinction according to the income decile to which they belong. The figures are calculated for energy and personal transport separately. The two shares should not be added, as many people are likely to belong to both groups.

⁵⁰ The CO₂ emissions from electricity generation are covered by the EU ETS1, and not by the EU ETS1.

Figure 28 Share of the population identified as vulnerable to higher energy costs for heating fuels and electricity according to the LIHC indicator, by Member State and income decile.

Note: Analysis based on data from the household budget survey for 2015 and the SILC survey for 2019. The countries are ranked from low to high median equivalised disposable income in 2019.

Source: Eden et al. (2023).

According to the analysis by Eden et al. (2023), the LIHC-indicator regarding expenditures for heating and electricity ranges between more than 5% (Finland) to more than 20% (Croatia, Greece, Spain, Luxembourg; Figure 28). Even for some richer countries this share is larger than 15%. The persons who experience difficulties mainly belong to the first and the second income decile. However, in quite some countries even people from the third decile are in this situation, and in a more limited number of cases also people from higher deciles.

The LIHC-indicator for personal transport ranges between almost 5% (Czechia) and almost 20% (Greece and Spain). The differences between high- and low-income countries are smaller than in the case of the heating and electricity expenditures. People facing this situation belong mostly to the first and the second income decile, as well as the third decile. Some people in the higher deciles are also vulnerable as defined by this indicator.

Figure 29 Share of the population identified as vulnerable to higher energy costs for personal transport according to the LIHC-indicator, by Member State and income decile.

Note: Analysis based on data from the household budget survey for 2015 and the SILC survey for 2019. The countries are ranked from low to high median equivalised disposable income in 2019.

Source: Eden et al. (2023).

➤ **Low-income-high-cost indicator (LIHC-indicator) according to degree of urbanisation**

Regarding the place where people live, Eden et al. (2023) find that in lower-income countries, households that are identified as vulnerable to higher transport fuel costs according to the LIHC-indicator are more likely to live in rural areas. In higher-income countries, on the other hand, it is often households in urban areas that are in this group.

Regarding heating and electricity expenditure/cooling in lower-income countries people living in rural areas are more likely to qualify as vulnerable to higher energy costs compared to those living in urban areas (Eden et al., 2023). This is not always the case for higher-income countries.

Box 6 Energy poverty by degree of urbanisation.

Energy poverty in households is driven not only by the interplay of poor energy efficiency, limited disposable income, and high energy costs, but also by broader socio-economic and vulnerability-related factors. Local-level evidence indicates that rural areas may face greater exposure to energy poverty due to lower income levels, higher rates of material deprivation, geographic isolation, and a housing stock that is generally older, larger, and equipped with less efficient heating systems (Hormigos Feliu et al., 2025).

At the EU level, energy poverty is most prevalent in rural areas, while towns and suburbs tend to align with the EU average, and cities consistently show the lowest levels (Hormigos Feliu et al., 2025). The highest energy poverty scores are observed in rural regions of Bulgaria, Romania, and Greece. In Member States with above-average energy poverty levels, rural areas are typically the most affected territorial category, whereas urban areas are the least impacted. These conclusions are drawn from a composite energy poverty index that combines four key indicators: (a) inability to keep the home adequately warm, (b) arrears on utility bills, (c) total population living in a dwelling with a leaking roof, damp walls, floors or foundation, or rot in window frames or floor, (d) at-risk-of-poverty rate, alongside household expenditure on energy.

The same study (Hormigos Feliu et al., 2025) also examines disparities in the EU building stock across territorial typologies, highlighting that rural areas are more likely to face energy efficiency challenges compared to towns, suburbs, or cities. In some countries, such as Latvia and Lithuania, these challenges coincide with elevated energy poverty levels, particularly high at-risk-of-poverty rates. The differences across territories largely stem from characteristics typical of rural areas: larger residential space per capita (which requires more energy to heat), lower building compactness, and generally colder climates. It is also interesting to mention that in EU rural areas, wood logs comprise 25% of total energy use, as compared to 7% in towns and suburbs and 2% in cities (Hormigos Feliu, 2025), highlighting the higher access and high substitution potential in rural versus urban areas. It is also worth noting that rural buildings often present greater potential for rooftop photovoltaic installations, due to higher rates of home ownership and more suitable building structures, and rural areas already have higher renovation rates for energy efficiency improvements compared to urbanised areas. (Hormigos Feliu et al., 2025).

➤ ***Share of spending on energy and personal transport according to gender of the reference person of the household***

Based on the household budget survey of 2015, households with a female reference person spend a higher share of their household budget on energy compared to households with a male reference person. This was observed for all countries except for Denmark, Cyprus and Finland. Relatively large high differences in shares of households with female versus male reference persons were seen in Slovakia, Czechia, Estonia and Latvia. This is linked to, among others, the lower-than-average income for women, the quality of the housing stock, the fact that women-led households are more likely to rent a house rather than own one, with implications for investing in energy efficiency and the availability of renovation subsidies for owners versus renters.

Figure 30 Share of spending on energy in total expenditures by gender of the reference person of the household – Household budget survey 2015.

Source: Koukoufakis & Uihlein (2022) as reported in Murauskaite-Bull et al. (2023).

For personal transport, however, the differences in the spending share are much larger. Moreover, one sees the opposite pattern than for spending on energy: on average, households with a male reference person have a substantially larger share of spending non personal transport than female led households. In some countries these differences are very large. This disparity in the share of personal transport expenditure between households with male and female reference persons can be attributed to variations in economic stability, as well as cultural preferences regarding the car ownership versus the use of alternative modes of transportation.

Figure 31 Share of spending on personal transport in total expenditures by gender of the reference person of the household – Household budget survey 2015.

Source: Koukoufakis & Uihlein (2022) as reported in Murauskaite-Bull et al. (2023).

The set of indicators that is reported here provides a broad overview of the degree of energy and transport poverty and vulnerability across the EU. The wide range of estimates reflects the multi-dimensional nature of these issues. Each indicator has its own merits and drawbacks, which should be considered when used for policy purposes. For example, the 2M indicator tends to give high vulnerability estimates unless combined with income thresholds. Moreover, caution is warranted when interpreting indicators based on outdated or incomplete data. Supporting studies for the European Commission, such as Cludius et al. (2024a), have highlighted the need for the collection of up-to-date and high-quality data. Furthermore, when defining policy measures under the national Social Climate Plans, more in-depth, country-specific analyses are essential to accurately identify the underlying factors affecting vulnerability, which can vary across and within each Member State.

4.4. Measures for the decarbonisation of road transport and buildings

What are the decarbonisation options available to road transport users and for buildings? And what are the policy options that address other barriers to support deeper emissions reductions under the EU ETS2? These questions are explored in the sections below for road transport and buildings separately, in which the range of available responses are categorised and described as explained below.

Users in the road transport and buildings can respond in various ways to the carbon price signal introduced by the EU ETS2. A well-established framework for characterising these options is the '**Avoid-Shift- Improve (ASI) typology**', originally developed for the transport sector (Dalkmann and Brannigan, 2007), and recently adapted to the energy sector (Jarre et al., 2024).

- 'Avoid' strategies focus on reducing the overall demand for transport or energy by targeting consumption at source.
- 'Shift' strategies involve changing energy sources or technologies to more sustainable, less carbon-intensive alternatives.
- 'Improve' strategies are aimed at increasing efficiency of existing transport or energy systems.

In addition to categorisation by domain of action, these decarbonisation options are also distinguished based on their **timeframe for implementation**. The response to changing energy prices varies significantly across different time horizons, due to several factors such as relative effort and time needed for implementation, the ease to adapt routines and behaviours, and financial costs involved, including both capital investments and operational costs. The identified decarbonisation options provided in the next sections for road transport and buildings are categorised into short-, medium-, or long-term timeframes as an indication of the complexities involved. However, these timeframes are only indicative and should be viewed as relative rather than strictly defined. In practice, they can vary substantially between persons or households, depending on individual financial capacities, social and cultural circumstances. The timeframe categories are not rigid as they represent a time range that may overlap. These are defined as follows:

- **Short term (0 to 24 months)**: these actions are generally low-effort and/or low-cost, and are relatively easy to implement within a short period of time. They include operational or behavioural changes, or minor technological upgrades that require minimal or no investment and can be quickly adopted in response to price signals.
- **Medium term (2 to 5 years)**: These actions typically involve moderate effort and/or moderate investment, requiring relatively more coordination and time for implementation.
- **Long term (over 5 years)**: These actions are high-effort and/or high-cost, involving greater complexity and coordination. They include capital-intensive interventions and/or transformative solutions that require extensive decision-making and longer implementation periods.

Finally, decarbonisation strategies are also considered along a **spectrum from individual-level action to collective or policy-driven interventions**. While households and businesses play a direct role through behavioural and investment choices, enabling conditions, such as infrastructure, financing, and regulatory frameworks, are shaped by national, regional, and local policies.

Alongside the examples of measures provided in this chapter, recent work by the European Commission offers further insights into how decarbonisation strategies can be effectively supported in practice. The study *Assessment of supporting measures promoting decarbonisation in the sectors covered by ETS2* reviews a range of good practice measures that illustrate how Member States can facilitate targeted decarbonisation in sectors covered by the EU ETS2, with particular attention to impacts on lower- and middle-income households (EC et al., 2025). The measures highlighted in the study have been implemented across several Member States and were selected based on their potential for replication, scalability, cost-efficiency, and their ability to deliver emissions reductions in the short term.

The next sections apply this three-part framework of action (Avoid–Shift–Improve), timeframe (short-, medium-, long-term), and level of intervention (individual versus collective or policy-level), to systematically present the available decarbonisation options in the road transport and buildings sectors under the EU ETS2.

4.4.1. Road transport decarbonisation options

Decarbonisation options available to road transport users

Road transport users can respond in various ways to the price incentive given by the EU ETS2 carbon price. In the case of transport, the 'avoid, shift and improve' strategies are usually defined as follows:

- 'Avoid' strategies involve reducing the number of trips or the trip length.
- 'Shift' strategies involve a shift towards other transport modes such as public transport, walking and cycling, that emit less GHGs. Together with the avoid strategies, these shift strategies involve a change in transport demand choices.
- 'Improve' strategies involve the use of less CO₂ emitting vehicles or fuels.

The possibility to react to changes in fuel prices will be different in the shorter run than in the longer run. In the long run the flexibility is higher, as more fundamental changes can be made to reduce CO₂ emissions, such as buying a new vehicle, or changing the home or work location to reduce the number of km travelled. The following table presents a classification of potential CO₂ reducing actions, according to the time frame.

An important consideration is that the impact of the short term or medium actions could also become stronger over time, when they are implemented more broadly. The national Social Climate Plans (see Section 4.5) are being set up to provide support to vulnerable households and micro-enterprises.

Not all of these actions are possible for everyone. There may be financial limitations, limitations due to the work schedule, people may have physical restrictions, people may not have access to public transport, etc. However, if actions to reduce CO₂ emissions are taken by part of the population, this will in turn lower the EU ETS2 allowance prices for everyone.

Table 4 Options for decarbonisation of road transport according to the Avoid-Shift-Improve framework, by timeframe (non-exhaustive list).

	Actions	Timeframe
Avoid	Teleworking and digital meetings	Short-term – Can be implemented relatively quickly. Depends on job characteristics.
	Consolidating trips (trip chaining)	Short-term – Requires planning, not infrastructure.
	Reducing delivery frequency / optimising logistics	Short- to medium-term – requires changes in logistics setup.
	Using local suppliers/services	Medium- to long-term – Requires changes in supply chains or habits, and optimised land use planning.
	Changing home/work location	Medium- to long-term – often linked to life transitions; affected by land use policies
Shift	Shift from car to public transport	Short- to medium-term – for existing public transport supply, or with changes in public transport supply that can be realised within this time frame. Medium to long-term with bigger developments in public transport services and capacity, and transit-oriented development projects.
	Shift to walking or cycling	For short(er) trips; Short-term if infrastructure exists; Medium-term if improvements are needed.
	Carpooling/ridesharing	Short- to medium-term – Requires coordination and digital platforms.
	Shift freight from road to rail/inland waterways	Medium- to long-term – requires infrastructure and logistics reconfiguration.
	Adopt shared mobility services for low emission vehicles (e.g. car clubs, e-scooters)	Short- to medium-term – requires supply of such services
	Shift to consolidated/green delivery options	Medium-term – requires actions from e-commerce and logistics providers.
Improve	Use more fuel-efficient vehicles	Medium-term – typically happens during vehicle replacement cycles.
	Upgrade to zero-emission vehicles (ZEVs)	Medium- to long-term – typically happens during vehicle replacement cycles; for long-term this requires supply of vehicle models for different market segments, capital investment and charging infrastructure.
	Use renewable fuels	Short- to medium-term for (advanced) biofuels; Long-term (large uncertainty) for renewable fuels of non-biological origin
	Adopt eco-driving practices	Short-term – Can be implemented quickly with information/training.
	Maintain vehicles regularly	Short-term – Immediate improvement in efficiency.
	Use digital route optimisation tools	Short-term – Readily available apps and services.
	Install vehicle add-ons (e.g., aerodynamic kits)	Medium-term – Moderate investment and installation time.

Source: ETC CM elaboration.

The following figures give an estimate of the CO₂ emissions from various passenger and freight transport modes, according to different dimensions of the emissions cycle. For the purposes of this report, the exhaust emissions (or tank-to-wheel, TTW emissions) are relevant, as they are the ones covered by the EU ETS2. For passenger transport, among these modes, cars, buses and motorcycles consume fuel that falls under the EU ETS2 emissions cap. For the electric road vehicles, the TTW emissions are zero. The emissions of their electricity supply (the so-called well-to-tank emissions, WTT) are to a large extent covered by the EU ETS1 cap. The same is the case for the WTT emissions for diesel and gasoline cars, as far as they take place in installations covered by the EU ETS1. The first figure shows the potential CO₂ emission reduction

per passenger km by switching to another motorised mode (“Shift”) or using more fuel efficient or zero-emission vehicles (“Improve”), for passenger transport in the Netherlands in 2022. The second figure gives similar information for freight transport, in this case for Germany in 2017. Also, in this case the TTW emissions of battery electric vehicles (not shown in the graph) are zero, while the EU ETS1 applies for the emissions in electricity production.

The CO₂ emissions also depend on the age of the vehicle, as well as on the size of the vehicle (Ligterink et al., 2021; Steinmetz et al., 2025), which both give additional options to reduce emissions: by switching to a newer vehicle and by choosing a smaller vehicle. To illustrate this, Figure 34 compares the average fuel consumption of gasoline cars of the different car segments compared to an average car.

In general, one can say that people will weigh on the one hand the saving in fuel costs that they can achieve with the costs of changing their choices. These costs can either be monetary (e.g. higher vehicle costs) or non-monetary (e.g. higher time costs when they switch to another mode, lower access to diverse services if they choose to shop more locally, etc.)

Figure 32 CO₂e emissions per passenger-km for a selection of passenger transport modes in the Netherlands, 2022.

Notes: The following assumptions are made about the number of persons per vehicle: car: 1.31, motorcycle: 1.15, bus: 8.11, coach: 48. For rail transport the following occupancy rates are assumed: 24% (local electric train), 26% (local diesel train), 32% (intercity train), 36% (tram), 84% (metro). The calculation of the WTT emissions of electric vehicles is based on the average electricity mix for the Netherlands.

Source: ETC CM elaboration based on Table 1 in van Seters and van den Berg (2025).

Figure 33 CO₂e emissions per tonne-km for a selection of freight transport modes in Germany, 2017.

Source: ETC CM elaboration based on Tables 70 and 72 in Allekotte et al. (2020).

Figure 34 Fuel consumption per kilometre of different car segments compared to that of an average gasoline car in the Netherlands, 2022.

Source: ETC CM elaboration based on webtool of van Seters and van den Berg (2025).

Regarding the choice for more fuel-efficient vehicles or zero emission vehicles, the EU ETS2 will change the financial evaluation that people make when they decide which car to buy. Together with other factors such as driving range of the vehicle, the availability of infrastructure, etc., the financial evaluation will co-determine their choices. The following analysis for Germany in 2025 illustrates this for the choice between a gasoline car and a battery electric car (BEV), as a function of the annual mileage and the electricity price. It indicates at which carbon tax level an electric vehicle would have a lower total cost of ownership (TCO) compared to a gasoline vehicle with an internal combustion engine. The exercise applies to medium-sized cars. For people who buy electricity at a price of 36 eurocent/kWh or lower, a BEV is already interesting without an additional carbon price, except for those who do not drive a lot. For people who pay a higher electricity price (because of a higher share of public recharging) a higher carbon price is needed to make the BEV more attractive. For information, EAFO reports the following indicative average recharging prices for Germany in 2024: 32 eurocent per kWh for private recharging, 51 to 58 eurocent/kWh for public AC

charging and 61 to 72 eurocent/kWh for public DC charging, depending on whether one has a subscription or not with a Mobility Service Provider for public recharging (EAFO, 2024). The second part of the table considers a gasoline vehicle fully running on e-fuel (power-to-liquid; PtL), which could be an alternative strategy for emission abatement, but are not an option today. In this case no cost advantages are observed across the parameter ranges considered, even not for the lowest values that are very unlikely. The vehicle costs remain the same as for a car fuelled with fossil gasoline and the cost of PtL-fuels remains higher than that of fossil gasoline even under optimistic price forecasts. Depending on the price level of the PtL-fuels very high carbon prices would be required to achieve the same TCO as with a car fully fuelled with fossil gasoline.

Figure 35 Total Cost of Ownership (TCO) and required CO₂ price for the cost-effectiveness of battery electric

		Annual mileage(km/year)				
		5000	10000	15000	20000	25000
ICEV - gasoline (annual TCO, €/year)						
Gasoline price at the pump (€/l)	1.8	5632	6679	7722	8763	9800
BEV (% change in annual costs compared to ICEV gasoline)						
Electricity price (€/kWh)	12	1.8%	-6.4%	-12.4%	-16.9%	-20.6%
	20	3.3%	-3.9%	-9.1%	-13.1%	-16.3%
	28	4.8%	-1.3%	-5.8%	-9.3%	-12.0%
	36	6.3%	1.2%	-2.6%	-5.4%	-7.7%
	44	7.8%	3.7%	0.7%	-1.6%	-3.4%
	52	9.3%	6.2%	4.0%	2.3%	0.9%
	60	10.7%	8.7%	7.3%	6.1%	5.2%
ICEV-PtL (% change in annual costs compared to ICEV gasoline)						
PtL price at the pump (€/l)	2.1	2.0%	3.4%	4.4%	5.2%	5.8%
	2.4	3.9%	6.6%	8.6%	10.1%	11.3%
	2.7	5.8%	9.9%	12.8%	15.0%	16.8%
	3	7.7%	13.1%	16.9%	19.9%	22.2%
	3.3	9.7%	16.3%	21.1%	24.8%	27.8%
	3.6	11.6%	19.5%	25.3%	29.8%	33.3%
	3.9	13.5%	22.7%	29.5%	34.6%	38.7%
Legend	Required CO ₂ price to compensate for additional costs in €/tonne CO ₂					
	< 100	< 200	< 300	< 400	>= 400	

vehicles (BEVs) and gasoline vehicles fully fuelled with e-fuels compared to the use of gasoline.

Source: Adapted by ETC CM from Figure 11 in Braungardt et al. (2024).

Policy strategies strengthening the responses of road transport users, in addition to the EU ETS2

In addition to the EU ETS2, several policy interventions, at EU level and in the Member States, at local, regional or national level provide incentives for decarbonisation of road transport, acting on the Avoid, Shift and/or Improve dimensions. The following table, adapted from EEA (2022) gives examples for the EU level.

In addition to these, national, regional and local level policies in the EU Member States play a key role. Member States use a range of policies and measures, to achieve the binding national Effort Sharing legislation targets, as stated in their National Energy and Climate Plans, and in order to contribute to other targets set at EU level (see e.g. the RED, the AFIR, etc.). The following table gives an overview of such policies and measures according to the way in which they aim to reduce CO₂ emissions: ‘Avoid’, ‘Shift’ or ‘Improve’. Different approaches can be taken, for example the use of economic or market-based instruments, the provision of infrastructure for public transport and active modes, the supply of

sustainable transport services, or a range of regulatory measures in transport, as well as in related systems such as land use or building policy. Usually, different types of measures are combined.

Table 5 Examples of Avoid-Shift-Improve strategies in the road transport sector at EU level.

Avoid	Shift	Improve	Selection of approaches	Examples
		X	Regulating the CO ₂ emissions of road transport vehicles and fuels, and alternative fuel infrastructure	CO ₂ emission performance standards of road vehicles Alternative Fuel Infrastructure Regulation Renewable Energy Directive*
X	X	X	Confronting all modes with their external costs	Toll Directive EU ETS1* EU ETS2* Energy Taxation Directive (and its proposed revision)*
	X		Financial support to sustainable modes via dedicated programs	Trans-European Transport Network Regulation (EU, 2024c) supported by Connecting Europe Facility European structural and investment funds* Loans and guarantees from the European Investment Bank* Research and Innovation programmes*
	X		Removing administrative and technical barriers	Railway packages European Rail Traffic Management System (ERTMS) European deployment plan Transport policy frameworks for inland waterways and short sea shipping
X	X		Supporting digital solutions	Legislative and non-legislative digitalisation initiatives in all transport modes (e.g. TEN-T regulation (EU, 2024c), ITS Directive (EU, 2023i), European Mobility Data Space (EC, 2023d)) Policies related to the development / enhancement of digital skills and the improvement of connectivity and broad band coverage* Research and Innovation programmes*
X	X		Combination of approaches targeted at urban mobility	Initiatives and funding programmes to stimulate sustainable urban mobility approaches and innovative solutions. See e.g. New EU Urban Mobility Framework (EC, 2021c); CIVITAS and the EU Urban Mobility Observatory

Note: The legislation and initiatives marked with an * are also relevant for the decarbonisation of buildings.

Source: Adapted by ETC CM from EEA (2022).

Table 6 Examples of policy instruments at local, regional and national level, by type of strategy for decarbonisation of road transport.

Approach	Decarbonisation strategy			Examples	Typical level of government		
	Avoid	Shift	Improve		Local	Regional	National
Economic or market-based instruments	X	X	X	Congestion pricing schemes, distance-based charging	X	X	X
				Fuel taxation			X
				Car taxation		X	X
				Tax treatment of company cars			X
				Tax treatment of commuting costs			X
		X	X	Car scrapping schemes	X	X	X
	X	X		Parking prices	X		
	X		Public transport pricing	X	X	X	
		X	Subsidies/tax benefits for alternative fuel infrastructure provision		X	X	
Transport infrastructure and supply of sustainable transport services		X		Coverage, frequency, comfort, information and ticketing systems of public transport	X	X	X
			Reallocating road space	X	X		
			Traffic management and control	X			
			Infrastructure for multimodal freight transport	X	X	X	
			Providing or enabling sharing platforms for low carbon transport services	X	X	X	
			Quality and coverage of infrastructure for active modes and light electric vehicles	X	X		
Spatial planning	X	X		Planning to increase urban densities, to foster mixed use of land, transit oriented development, to improve connectivity and accessibility	X	X	
Regulatory measures	X	X	X	(ultra) low emission zones, car bans, pedestrian zones, other access regulations	X	X	
	X	X		Traffic rules, including speed limits	X	X	X
	X	X		Parking regulation, on-street, off-street (including in private buildings)	X		
			X	Regulation alternative fuel infrastructure - (semi) public, private		X	X
			X	Fuel blending mandates, CO ₂ emission intensity standards fuels			X
Other policy measures		X		Multimodal transport information, management and payment	X	X	X
	X	X	X	Marketing and rewarding	X	X	
			X	Quality labels for second-hand zero-emission vehicles/batteries			X
	X	X	X	Awareness campaigns	X	X	X
	X			Legislation on teleworking			X
	X	X		Site-based travel plans	X	X	

Source: Adapted by ETC CM from EEA (2022).

Box 7 Spatial planning in the Walloon Region of Belgium.

In the Walloon region of Belgium, the “Schéma du Développement du Territoire” (SDT), defines the spatial development strategy for 2050. It is accompanied by a revision of the “Code du Développement territorial” (CoDT), which is the toolbox that brings together the regulatory texts needed to implement it. The strategy interacts with the regional mobility strategy “La Vision Fast 2030”.

If the objectives of the SDT are indeed achieved in the coming decades, this could be a major inflection factor.

The regional spatial development and planning objectives aim to achieve:

- spatial optimisation, which includes combating urban sprawl, preserving as much land as possible, and the efficient and coherent use of land by urban development,
- socio-economic development and the attractiveness of the region,
- quality management of the living environment,
- controlling mobility.

The SDT includes concrete measures that allow to optimise the territory, by controlling the development of land and by combating urban sprawl. For this, actions should be taken in three areas:

- Reducing the amount of built-up land by directing projects towards land that has already been developed and renovating buildings
- Densifying housing in urban and village centres and making buildings more compact
- Refocusing activities by encouraging development in areas that are well served by facilities and services and accessible by public transport.

The two big objectives are to have three out of four new housing in centralities, and to arrive at a zero net development of land by 2050, with a close monitoring of the annual evolution.

The development of central areas should follow the ‘10-minute town or village’ model. This model proposes developing urban or village centres in such a way as to limit dependence on the car. In concrete terms, all amenities and facilities should be made accessible within a 10-minute walking or cycling distance from where people live or work.

Source: Wallonie, SPW Territoire (n.d., n.d.)

Box 8 Policies for promoting the uptake of emerging small and “car-like” electric vehicles.

Up to now, EV policies mostly aim more for a “like-for-like” replacement of road vehicles with an internal combustion engine by identical electric vehicles. In urban areas the uptake of smaller, lighter and shorter-ranged vehicle types could be an interesting alternative transport option, with comparatively lower requirements for electricity supply and charging infrastructure, lower materials needs, lower emissions, safer traffic, and better affordability also for lower income groups. Such vehicles could be either emerging “smaller-than-car” EVs – both micro EVs and electric microcars- or electric two- and three-wheelers. The International Transport Forum (2023) lists a set of policies that could facilitate the uptake of such vehicles. Many of these measures can be taken in Member States, while some, including vehicle standards, are to be set at EU level. An integrated package of measures is advised, which can consist of, for example:

- Infrastructure measures, such as:
 - o The provision of separated infrastructure, of good quality (in terms of e.g. lane width and type of pavement),
 - o The provision of micromobility-specific traffic lights and signalling,
 - o The provision of a dedicated parking infrastructure.
- Regulation, including:
 - o Mandating protective gear,
 - o The homologation of emerging smaller electric vehicles and the safety regulation for all vehicles, including those for larger vehicles to ensure that they are adapted to interaction with the smaller EVs,
 - o Adaptions to traffic regulations to guarantee the safe shared use of road systems without putting a market barrier for newcomers,
 - o Urban vehicle access regulations.
- Economic incentives, such as:
 - o Reform of taxation in line with the internalisation of the external costs of all transport modes,
 - o Reform of vehicle taxes, subsidies, feebate systems, bonus-malus programmes to promote the uptake of smaller EVs and discourage the purchase of larger ones,
 - o Differential parking costs.
- Other instruments, such as R&D support for innovations in the small and “car-like” EV.

4.4.2. Buildings decarbonisation options

This section explores interventions that can support the decarbonisation path of buildings. Interventions can be implemented at **building level**, including practical solutions that households and businesses can implement to reduce energy consumption, reduce reliance on fossil fuels, and enhance energy efficiency in buildings. Given the various challenges faced at building level to decarbonise, such as financial barriers, or infrastructural needs at a larger geographical scale, supporting measures and actions at a higher governance level are needed to support individual action. **Policy interventions and collective actions** are also explored to look at the broader support mechanisms at different governance levels to facilitate the transition, incentivise users, secure public funds, and provide the infrastructural development.

Interventions at building level and policy and collective actions are categorised under the ASI framework. In the buildings sector these strategies are categorised as follows:

- 'Avoid' strategies involve behavioural changes to reduce the energy demand.
- 'Shift' strategies involve a shift towards climate neutral alternatives of the energy source in heating and cooling technologies such as renewables and electrification.

- 'Improve' strategies involve the use of energy efficient and less CO₂ emitting technologies and systems. This involves the policy interventions and collective actions.

Decarbonisation options at building level

The table below shows a non-exhaustive list of ASI decarbonisation interventions at the building level, classified by an indicative timeframe for implementation.

Table 7 Options for decarbonisation of buildings according to the Avoid-Shift-Improve framework, by timeframe (non-exhaustive list).

	Actions	Timeframe
Avoid	Avoiding unnecessary consumption; Switching off idle appliances	Short-term, potentially in the immediate term
	Adjusting thermostat settings	Short-term, potentially in the immediate term
	Conducting energy audits	Short-term
	Optimising space use (e.g., prevent overbuilding or underusing rooms)	Short- to medium-term, as may require some building alterations
	Optimising heating and cooling schedules; Real time monitoring with smart meters	Short-term, provided that smart meters are installed
Shift	Electrification via heat pumps	Short- to medium- term, depending on the buildings' readiness to deployment of heat pumps and owner's financial capacity
	Installation of on-site renewables such as PV systems	Short- to medium-term, depending on local planning requirements and owner's financial capacity
	Connecting to renewable-based district heating	Short- to medium-term, given that a district heating is already available in the area
Improve	Installing smart thermostats, meters, and energy management systems	Short-term
	Upgrading of existing heating and cooling systems to more energy efficient (or hybrid) equipment	Short- to medium-term
	Deep renovation and retrofitting of building envelope (bioclimatic design, insulation, windows, doors, roof, ventilation)	Medium- to long-term, depending on starting point of energy rating of building
	Relocating to passive or net-zero building	Short- to medium-term, depending on household's flexibility to relocate

Source: ETC CM elaboration.

The key actions identified in the table above are discussed in further detail below.

➤ ***Behavioural change of building occupants***

Reducing overall energy demand is key to reducing the need for fossil fuel use, thereby facilitating the decarbonising the building sector. The efficient and responsible use of resources, as well as reducing unnecessary energy consumption, can potentially help building occupants avoid excessive energy costs and taxation while maintaining living standards (IEA, 2021).

The 'Avoid-Shift-Improve' framework puts the emphases on consumers to make behavioural changes for more resource efficient choices, providing opportunities for socio-cultural, infrastructural, and technological change (IPCC, 2022). Short and long-term actions include:

- Adjusting thermostat settings to minimise energy waste,
- Optimising space utilisation by preventing overbuilding and/or underusing energy-intensive infrastructure, and
- Making effective use of energy monitoring systems, such as smart meters, for real-time monitoring of energy use to incentivise energy-saving actions (EEA, n.d.).

➤ ***Passive systems and building envelope renovation prioritising low embodied carbon material***

In line with the EPBD, renovation of buildings is key to improving the energy performance of buildings and reduce losses. Passive system upgrades should be prioritised to enhance energy efficiency and reduce heating and cooling-related emissions (EEA, 2024b). Key renovation measures include upgrade of building envelope materials, including bioclimatic principles in the design phase, passive house standards, high-performance insulation, energy-efficient windows, and retrofitting for better thermal performance to minimise heat losses and risk overheating in summer. The renovation process should also prioritise the circular economy principles and the use of lower embodied carbon construction products.

➤ ***Improving the energy efficiency of heating and cooling equipment***

Improving the efficiency of existing heating and cooling equipment is essential to reducing operational emissions and lowering dependence on fossil fuels. Key measures aiming for short-term improvement include:

- Retrofitting of existing heating equipment to improve efficiency without full-system replacement,
- Maintenance and tuning of existing systems for optimal efficiency,
- Adjusting hydronic balance heating system water flow to ensure even heat distribution,
- Installing programmable or smart thermostats and energy management systems to optimise heating schedules and incorporate occupancy sensors for demand-based control,
- Installation of thermostatic radiator valves to allow room-by-room temperature control to prevent overheating,
- Install heat recovery ventilation or energy recovery ventilation systems to reuse heat from exhaust air,
- Improved insulation of heating distribution systems, and insulating pipes, valves, and tanks to reduce heat loss in distribution,
- Use reflective insulation behind radiators on external walls, and
- Install weather-compensated controls or building management systems for dynamic adjustment and enable zoning of heating systems.

➤ ***Shifting to decarbonised heating systems and heat pumps***

For the medium- and long-term relief from the fossil fuels, changing the existing heating systems into decarbonised options is necessary, by switching to:

- renewable energy heating boilers using biomass,
- solar thermal systems or geothermal heating, and
- heat pumps, including air, ground or water source.

Heat pumps are a promising technology for heating spaces in buildings through electrification. They are significantly more energy-efficient than fossil-fuel boilers, typically consuming three to five times less energy. This is due to their ability to extract renewable ambient heat from the air, ground or water. Their performance is regulated under the EU Eco-design and Energy Labelling Directive, ensuring minimum efficiency standards across the EU market.

Since heat pumps operate on electricity, their use is indirectly subject to carbon pricing under EU ETS1, which is reflected in electricity prices. When combined with on-site solar PV and energy storage, heat pumps can further improve both economic and environmental performance. Integrating heat pump installations with building envelope improvements provides a strong, synergistic approach to achieving deep decarbonisation.

➤ ***Shifting to renewables energy use***

The integration of renewable energy sources in buildings offers an effective approach for reducing CO₂ emissions in buildings. This can be achieved through a range of technologies, including building-integrated renewable energy systems such as solar photovoltaics, solar thermal or biomass boilers, as well as offsite solutions such as connections to renewable energy grids and waste heat recovery networks (European Academies' Science Advisory Council, 2021).

An important synergy arises when these systems are coupled with the uptake of electric vehicles. Buildings equipped with renewable energy generation, particularly solar PV, can power electric vehicles charging, thereby supporting low-emission mobility while maximising on-site energy use. This integration not only reduces GHG emissions across both sectors but can also enhance grid flexibility and energy self-sufficiency at the household or community level.

➤ ***Holistic approach for deep renovation leading to near-zero energy buildings, net-zero carbon buildings and positive energy buildings***

Each of the individual mitigation actions identified above plays a critical role in advancing the decarbonisation of the existing building stock across the EU. However, the ultimate objective is to identify the most effective combination of these measures to maximise their collective impact. Achieving this requires a holistic approach embedded within an integrated deep renovation strategy. When successfully implemented, such an approach can lead to outcomes such as near-zero energy buildings, net-zero carbon buildings, or even positive energy buildings.

Achieving this transformation, however, goes beyond technical interventions alone. It demands enabling policy frameworks and collective action mechanisms that support and empower end-users across all levels.

Policy strategies and collective action strengthening the response of end-users, in addition to the EU ETS2

Emission abatement technologies and behaviours have financial implications for building owners and users. Well-structured policies and measures, and financial incentives are needed to accelerate this transition by making renovations, more energy-efficient, and low- or zero-carbon technologies more accessible and affordable.

The table below investigates the options for policies and measures at national and sub-national levels, according to categorised by main strategy approach, and according to Avoid-Shift-Improve framework.

Table 8 Examples of policy instruments at local, regional and national levels, by type of strategy for decarbonisation of buildings.

Approach	Decarbonisation strategy			Examples	Typical level of government		
	Avoid	Shift	Improve		Local	Regional	National
Economic or market-based instruments		X	X	Targeted financial incentives for households and businesses (e.g. grants, concessional loans, subsidies) to adopt renewable energy installations, and energy renovations		X	X
		X	X	Tax reliefs, deductions, or fiscal adjustments to encourage investment in renewable energy installations, and energy renovations		X	X
			X	Pay-as-You-Save (PAYS) schemes allowing costs of energy renovations to be recovered through future savings		X	X
		X		Leasing of heat pumps		X	X
		X	X	National and regional vocational training programmes for upskilling workers and developing a qualified renovation workforce; Certification for professionals in energy efficiency and renewable systems		X	X
Spatial planning, infrastructure and supply of energy services		X		Urban planning for district heating and cooling systems	X	X	X
		X		Promotion and facilitation of renewable energy communities and citizen-led energy initiatives	X	X	
Regulatory measures		X	X	Implementing minimum energy performance standards for existing buildings		X	X
		X	X	Introduction and promotion of building renovation passports to provide step-by-step renovation pathways for individual buildings		X	X
Sufficiency and behavioural measures	X			Public awareness campaigns and behavioural change programmes to encourage energy-efficient practices	X	X	X
	X		X	Development and integration of energy sufficiency or sobriety plans to promote reduced energy demand in line with climate targets		X	X
Other policy measures	X	X	X	Strong policy coordination between different governance levels (EU, national, regional, local) and ensuring coherence between energy, climate, housing, and social policies	X	X	X
	X	X	X	Integration of building decarbonisation within Just Transition Plans to ensure fairness and social acceptance			X

Source: ETC CM elaboration.

Box 9 Energy sobriety/sufficiency plan in France.

France has introduced the national measure, the Energy Sobriety/Sufficiency plan (Gouvernement de la République française, 2022) in relation to their NECP. This plan comprised of 15 measures, ranging from behavioural changes such as using maximum temperature of 19°C in public buildings, encouragement of carpooling and teleworking, to dimming or shutting off public lighting during specific hours. Additionally, subsidies for the installation of heat pumps and other more energy-efficient heating systems were also part of the plan. Thanks to these measures France managed to use almost 10% less electricity in winter 2022 compared to previous years.

➤ *Regulatory measures to support the renovation of the existing building stock*

A coordinated policy approach is essential to increase deep renovation rates from the current level of 0.2% to at least 3% annually (BPIE, 2021b), particularly to accelerate renovations in low-income areas.

The implementation of **minimum energy performance standards** (MEPS) for heating systems, embedded in building energy codes at the national level, is critical for reducing household energy costs over time. These measures align with the principles of the **Energy Performance of Buildings** (Directive (EU) 2024/1275), which emphasise the importance of providing incentives and funding to encourage the switch towards non-fossil-fuel-based heating and cooling systems. In addition, MEPS for landlords and property owners may also serve as important regulatory tools to ensure that minimum energy efficiency levels are met before properties are rented or sold (Rogulj et al., 2023). This may potentially contribute to the overall improvement of the housing market.

To support the long-term renovation planning, the EPBD introduces **renovation passports** as a voluntary tool. These passports provide a clear, staged roadmap for deep renovations, helping owners and investors to plan the timing and scope of interventions effectively. While encouraging the use of renovation passports, it is essential to ensure that they do not impose excessive administrative burdens on building owners. Together with the **Energy Performance Certificates** (EPCs), renovation passports provide valuable, structured information that supports building decarbonisation efforts and helps link policy objectives with practical implementation.

➤ *Financial support and incentives for renovation and uptake of clean, efficient technology*

Blended and targeted financial mechanisms are essential tools to support the deep energy renovation of buildings envelopes and adoption of clean and efficient technologies, such as heat pumps, energy efficient appliances, and renewable energy systems. These financial tools help mitigate high upfront costs, making the transition to low-carbon buildings more accessible. Key instruments include grants, subsidies, and (zero interest) loans, which increases access and affordability of decarbonisation measures. In this context, it is strategic for Member States to ensure the availability of sufficient public funding and support schemes, which are critical to drive large-scale renovation efforts and deliver on climate and energy targets.

Prioritising support for the deep energy renovation of poorly performing buildings can yield climate, economic and public health benefits (Keliauskaitė et al., 2024), while potentially also contributing to the reduction of energy poverty. To maximise the effectiveness of these supports, it is essential to **reduce bureaucratic hurdles** in accessing them (Braungardt et al., 2022). Establishing clear eligibility and monitoring criteria ensures that support reaches vulnerable households, while preventing free-riding effects. Special attention should be given to low-income households and tenants, to ensure inclusive access to funding schemes.

Box 10 'MaPrimeRénov' grant scheme in France.

'MaPrimeRénov' (République Française, 2025) is a grant scheme introduced in 2020 offering income-based aid for home energy renovation in France. The amount is scaled according to income brackets, covering up to 90% of renovation costs for the lowest-income households. When the EU ETS2 comes into effect, this scheme is expected to be expanded (Réseau Cler, 2025).

To further reduce financial barriers, several **innovative financing models and fiscal measures** may also be considered. One such model is the Pay-as-You-Save (PAYS), which enables households to repay energy efficiency or decarbonised heating technology investments through energy bill savings, thereby reducing upfront financial barriers. Combining subsidies with PAYS or energy-performance contracts can help close the remaining investment gap (Bruegel, 2023). In addition, tax and fiscal adjustments can play an important role. These may include the implementation of low-carbon transition tax credits, aligning VAT and other tax incentives with low-carbon investments, and offering tax deductions for businesses investing in energy-efficient or decarbonising processes. Such measures are particularly beneficial for micro and small enterprises, helping to bridge the gap between the policy objectives and market conditions. Moreover, tools such as accelerated depreciation for energy-efficient renovations, clean heating technologies, or renewable energy systems, can further ease capital constraints and improve the economic case for early action.

Additionally, there is no EU level singular renovation fund, but there are multiple sources that provide support to households, including the Social Climate Fund, Recovery and Resilience Facility, ERDF, CF, LIFE Clean Energy Transition Sub-programme, InvestEU and European Investment Bank.

Box 11 Heat pumps leasing models.

New service-oriented business models are starting to develop across Europe to lower the financial and organisational barriers associated with heat pump installation. Similar to models established for electric vehicles, in these service frameworks, consumers would engage in long-term rental agreements that include monthly fees covering the cost of equipment, installation, and maintenance (EHPA, 2025). Examples of companies providing such services are in **Germany** (Reuters, 2022) and **Spain** (Inspenet, 2025), offering integrated service packages where households pay monthly instalments covering technical assessment, system design, equipment, installation, maintenance, servicing, warranty, and support with accessing public subsidies. These models shift the complexity of procurement and coordination to specialised providers while spreading investment costs over time, which reduces the upfront burden for households.

Applying a subscription model to low-income households through social leasing could further enhance access to heating technologies for all segments of society. Social leasing can offer low-income households the opportunity to utilise heat pump systems by overcoming the upfront cost through monthly rental payments. While no national government currently runs a social leasing scheme for heat pumps, such schemes would require the active involvement of governments, particularly to act as guarantors of the scheme (EHPA, 2025).

➤ **Scaling up district heating and cooling (DHC)**

Article 26 of the EED promotes the development of efficient district heating and cooling (DHC) systems. Prioritising DHC in urban, district, and neighbourhood-level planning can support the decarbonisation

process. Cities, municipalities and federal governments are encouraged to integrate DHC plans into their short-, medium- and long-term urban development planning.

Currently, nearly 10% of heat in the EU comes from district heating, with the highest prevalence being in the northern, central, and eastern regions of Europe. However, fossil fuels contribute to two thirds (69%) of the energy mix used in district heating (EEA, 2023). This shows there remains significant potential to decarbonise DHC systems by integrating renewable energy sources, particularly in metropolitan areas where neighbourhood-scale measures can be more effective. For example, combining electric boilers, and heat pumps with DHC in urban areas, can enhance system efficiency, while enhancing local energy resilience (EEA, 2025f).

While expanding DHC offers numerous environmental benefits, upgrading existing networks can be costly and technically complex compared to individual household renovations. DHC retrofits require a coordinated, collective effort to replace boilers, heat exchangers and distribution infrastructure (EEA, 2023). This collective nature makes implementation more challenging but also presents opportunities for achieving larger scale decarbonisation impacts.

Historically, DHC systems were covered under the EU ETS1, which may have disincentivised investment in new DHC infrastructure (Roca Reina et al., 2024). However, the implementation of the EU ETS2, is expected to create stronger incentives for renewable energy integration and increase demand for clean heat sources, including DHC systems powered by biomass, waste heat, and other renewables.

In addition to residential buildings, small industries are also incentivised under the EU ETS2 to reduce their reliance on fossil fuels for energy-intensive operations. Adopting circular economy practices, such as waste heat recovery and industrial symbiosis, can further reduce fossil fuel dependence and optimise energy use across sectors.

➤ *Renewable energy communities and community-led initiatives*

Renewable energy communities represent a transformative model that requires a shift from a centralised system to a decentralised, community-led approach. These communities generate and manage renewable energy locally, supporting the creation of carbon-neutral energy systems.

A core element of renewable energy communities is collective self-consumption, where electricity generation and consumption are (near-)instantaneously matched within a local area. The model is enabled by a suite of digital and smart technologies, including smart meters, micro-controllers, battery storage, electric vehicles, and online trading platforms, that facilitate real-time energy balancing between production and demand at the community level (EEA, 2024b). The EU-level legal foundation for renewable energy communities is established under Article 22 of the RED II, which recognises their role in accelerating the energy transition.

Renewable energy communities and community-led initiatives can play a particularly important role in supporting energy justice by increasing access to clean energy for vulnerable households and reducing household exposure to volatile energy markets. These collective approaches enable more equitable participation in the energy transition, while fostering local ownership and resilience. To ensure that such actions are inclusive and accessible, they must be supported by targeted policy frameworks and financial mechanisms, such as grants and subsidies, that help overcome participation barriers faced by marginalised groups (Hanke and Lowitzsch, 2020). Moreover, enabling frameworks should actively support the establishment and scaling of renewable energy communities and prosumers, while encouraging models of co-ownership of generation and transmission assets by regional utilities, energy cooperatives, banks, and small to medium-sized enterprises (EEA, 2025f). In doing so, renewable energy communities can become a powerful driver of both social equity and decentralised, sustainable energy systems.

4.4.3. Complementary and enabling actions to support the green transition

Effective coordination between local, regional and national climate and energy policies is essential to help reduce policy fragmentation and accelerate the uptake of energy efficient technologies. As noted by Cornago (2022), carbon pricing is just one piece of the puzzle; all policies affecting road transport and buildings must align with the EU's long-term climate targets to ensure coherence and effectiveness. This section addresses barriers and gaps in market and policy alignment and proposes measures to enhance policy synergy.

Policy coherence and stability is critical for creating investment certainty, providing regulatory stability and clear long-term signals for markets and households alike (Heller et al., 2024). The success of the EU ETS2, among other factors, depend on how well it is integrated with complementary measures and broader sustainability frameworks. Evidence shows that complementary policies are needed to ensure the ETS2 achieves its emission reduction target (Abrell et al., 2024).

In addition to targeted action, information campaigns and awareness raising stand out as crucial behavioural measures that enhance the effectiveness of policy implementation. Insights from the EU Policy Lab workshop (Marion and David, 2025) revealed that public resistance to change, often rooted in behavioural inertia and limited awareness, significantly hampers the adoption of green measures. By addressing these behavioural barriers through targeted communication strategies, such as nudging, framing messages around co-benefits, and leveraging social norms, information campaigns can shift perceptions and encourage pro-environmental actions. These interventions help overcome low engagement and foster greater public support for decarbonisation policies, making them a key complement to regulatory and financial instruments in the green transition of the building sector (Marion and David, 2025).

While the EU ETS2 does not include provisions for targeted information campaigns, the Energy Efficiency Directive (chapter IV) and the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (Article 29) both have provisions to ensure different stakeholders⁵¹ have **access to information** on available energy efficiency improvement measures, individual actions and financial and legal frameworks. This is an important element to ensure that information on options and benefits of road transport and building decarbonisation is accessible to all, especially for vulnerable households. Delivering information on energy must not be understood as providing market data that must be provided to consumers about the status of their consumption (BPIE, 2024). Providing information should be considered as **a tool to citizens for awareness raising, supporting the consumers in reducing energy consumption**. Raising awareness of social benefits is important to maximise environmental and health co-benefits (EEA and Eurofound, 2021). There is a need for effective communication and accessibility of support measures to maximise environmental and health co-benefits, particularly for vulnerable groups. Overall, a multi-level governance approach is essential for successful policy implementation (EEA and Eurofound, 2021).

Furthermore, to meet rising demand in the construction and renovation sectors, investment in **workforce development** is crucial for the market to operate optimally in the short to medium terms, and especially during the initial years of the EU ETS2 implementation. Expanding training programs for construction work, and support investment in modern construction methods will help create the skilled labour force needed to implement building upgrades at scale. Similar considerations should be given to the road transport, for example to ensure that the public transportation sector has sufficient skilled labour to allow for the needed growth for the green transition. Therefore, the EU ETS2 should be integrated within a **broader just**

⁵¹ All relevant market actors, such as final customers, consumer organisations, civil society representatives, renewable energy communities, local and regional authorities, energy agencies, social service providers, builders, architects, engineers, auditors, and installers of building elements as well as specific groups such as vulnerable customers.

transition strategy to ensure fair labour and social adjustments through re-skilling and upskilling, and job transition programmes for workers in affected sectors to strengthen the process (EC, n.d.).

4.5. Supporting end-users through the Social Climate Fund and the national Social Climate Plans

The EU aims to ensure that the implementation of the EU ETS2 aligns with its broader cohesion goals, helping to guarantee that the transition to a low-carbon economy does not exacerbate existing disparities between countries and regions. Given the diverse levels of economic development and energy dependency across the EU, lower-income households and regions may face disproportionate financial burdens. To prevent this outcome, the implementation of the EU ETS2 needs to be accompanied by targeted policy measures, robust financial support mechanisms, and investment in decarbonised infrastructure. A well-integrated approach that connects the EU ETS2 with EU cohesion policies can maintain principles of fairness, strengthen regional resilience, and ensure that all Member States benefit from the transition to climate neutrality.

Beyond regional cohesion, social justice must be held at the core of the EU ETS2 implementation to avoid placing undue hardships on vulnerable groups within each country and region. As a consequence, the Social Climate Fund has been established to support these vulnerable groups from facing excessive financial pressures due to the introduction of the EU ETS2. In addition to vulnerable households, transport users and micro-enterprises, low income and lower middle-income households may also face challenges with higher fuel costs. Unlike large corporations with greater financial and operational flexibility, these groups might also lack resources and capacity to invest in decarbonisation and energy efficiency measures. Support mechanisms should therefore be carefully designed and tailored to the needs of all segments of society, in order to enable decarbonisation in a manner that is cost-effective, and just, while also ensuring social acceptability.

The Social Climate Fund is a critical tool to mitigate potential social and economic impacts of the EU ETS2. The impacts will differ across society, notably between urban and rural areas, and among different socio-economic groups. Complementary measures at multiple governance levels must therefore accompany the Social Climate Fund to ensure acceptability of the policy instrument and public trust in authorities. Several Member States have already implemented or are planning measures that complement the EU ETS2 or Social Climate Fund, offering good practice examples for other Member States, as demonstrated by national measures reported in 2025 under the Governance of the Energy Union and Climate Action (ETC CM, 2025). As reported by Member States (EEA, 2025g), countries have introduced targeted schemes to support vulnerable households in both buildings and transport. In the buildings sector, Austria has a set of *measures against energy poverty* providing social support for low-income households. Belgium's *0% energy loan* provides interest-free loans for vulnerable families, Denmark's *SHDF-3 scheme* delivers financial aid to the social housing sector, and Spain's *social bonus* offers discounts on electricity and heating bills for vulnerable consumers. In the road transport sector, France provides income-dependent grants for the purchase of EV through the *Bonus à l'achat ou à la location de voitures particulières électriques (Bonus for the purchase or rental of electric passenger car)*. These scope of these measures may extend beyond the existing guidelines.

The Social Climate Fund Regulation explicitly defines "vulnerable households, vulnerable transport users and vulnerable microenterprises" and mandates that national Social Climate Plans include measures to support these groups. Developing, executing, and tracking climate change mitigation policies that are effective, efficient, sustainable, and socially acceptable demands collaboration across various levels of governance and integration across multiple policy domain (EEA and Eurofound, 2021).

The Social Climate Fund aims for fair revenue distribution by establishing mechanisms to return the revenue generated from carbon pricing to the public. Fair revenue distribution refers to the equitable use

of proceeds generated from carbon pricing to ensure that the financial burden of climate policy does not fall disproportionately on vulnerable groups. The core principle of fair revenue distribution is to return the funds generated from CO₂ pricing to citizens in a socially balanced manner, preferably through targeted structural investments (e.g., in energy efficiency, public transport) or temporary direct financial support (e.g., income-based payments) (Haywood and O'Sullivan, 2025). Fair burden-sharing mechanisms, and financial support for energy-efficient technologies and renovations in buildings, and incentives for sustainable mobility solutions will be essential to mitigate the social impacts of the EU ETS2, thus ensuring that the climate neutral transition is inclusive and does not come at the expense of the least able to pay.

To access the funds of the Social Climate Fund, Member States must draft **national Social Climate Plans** with all planned measures and investments in support of vulnerable households, transport users, and micro-enterprises. The draft plans were expected by June 30, 2025 (EU, 2023a). By 12th December 2025, Sweden, Latvia, Lithuania, and Malta have submitted their Social Climate Plans to the European Commission, which are currently under assessment (EC, n.d.).

Member states should identify their national patterns of vulnerability, develop appropriate policy measures and investments and create country specific indicators. The plans are expected to be consistent with the National Energy and Climate Plans and other EU and national level policies and programmes. To ensure the Social Climate Fund's effectiveness, in line with the guidance on the Social Climate Plans, Member States need to have definitions of vulnerable households, vulnerable micro-enterprises and vulnerable transport users, with explanations on of how the definitions of energy poverty and transport poverty are to be applied at national level (EC, 2025e).

A key priority in implementing the Social Climate Plans is to ensure clear and transparent monitoring and communication of how EU ETS2 revenues are spent. This is essential for maintaining public trust and acceptance of carbon pricing mechanisms (Cayol and Monar, 2025). Both international experiences and academic research underline that the visibility of carbon revenue use strongly influences citizen support. A lack of perceived transparency or fairness, such as in the recent repeal of Canada's carbon tax, can undermine public backing, even for well-designed policies (Cayol and Monar, 2025). These lessons show that carbon pricing systems are at risk of failure if revenue use is not clearly and credibly communicated. To safeguard the long-term success of the EU ETS2, particularly under the Social Climate Fund, Member States must therefore actively report, communicate, and engage the public on how revenues are used, particularly in support of vulnerable groups and climate mitigation.

Therefore, crucially, the Social Climate Plans must undergo **public consultations involving local and regional authorities, social partners, and civil society organisations** to enhance transparency and public engagement. This aims to ensure that the Social Climate Fund spending aligns with national needs while fostering citizen awareness of EU ETS2 impacts. In addition to the Social Climate Fund resources, revenues from the EU ETS2 allowances will also contribute to national budgets, enabling further investments in fossil fuel reduction, energy efficiency improvements, and public transport infrastructure. Ultimately, well-designed national Social Climate Plans can enhance social resilience, reduce energy poverty, and promote a just transition towards a low-carbon economy.

Under the Social Climate Fund Regulation, Member States may include **technical assistance** (EC, 2025e) in their Social Climate Plans to support the effective administration and implementation of Social Climate Fund-funded measures and investments. These technical assistance activities (EC, 2025e) are eligible for funding but should be limited to a maximum of 2.5% of the estimated total cost of the Plan. Eligible technical assistance expenses typically include training, programming, implementation, monitoring, control, audit, and evaluation activities, as well as administrative assistance. They may also cover studies, IT-related expenditures, public consultations, and information and communication efforts, all of which are crucial for the successful delivery of Social Climate Fund objectives. Ongoing EU projects and initiatives

also provide technical assistance which may assist countries in developing and implementing their Plans. Such initiatives include Smart Cities Marketplace⁵² and Net Zero Cities⁵³.

In the context of low-carbon energy policies, EEA and Eurofound (2021) provides recommendations for the design of mitigating strategies that can be transferable to the design of national policies in the context of the Social Climate Plans. To ensure the transition is both socially and environmentally sustainable, the report outlines three key strategies. First, it recommends prioritising policies with “win-win” outcomes, those that reduce emissions while also addressing social inequalities. Examples include investment in public transport and active mobility infrastructure, which offer affordable alternatives to car use, and energy efficiency improvements in homes, particularly for vulnerable groups. These policies can yield progressive outcomes by reducing energy bills and improving health and wellbeing. Second, the report highlights the importance of targeted financial compensation to address the regressive effects of carbon pricing. Several Member States, such as Germany and Ireland, have already introduced tax breaks, energy allowances, or direct financial support for low-income households, using revenues from carbon taxes. Well-calibrated subsidies, particularly those aimed at social housing or low-income households, are also cited as effective tools. Third, the report underscores the need to consider non-monetary benefits, such as cleaner air and improved quality of life, as essential components of socially fair climate policies. It calls for stronger evidence on the social distribution of these benefits, greater coordination across governance levels, and the involvement of a broad range of stakeholders, including civil society and social partners. Ultimately, the report emphasises that achieving a fair transition will depend on how well these measures are designed, targeted, and integrated into the broader policy framework.

Further examples of measures that can be replicated by Member States to accelerate decarbonisation whilst mitigating potential distributional impacts is provide by a study conducted for the European Commission (Ludden et al., 2024). It presents a **collection of good-practice examples and case studies**, with a focus on structural measures (instead of direct income support measures) The guiding principle for the collection is cost-efficiency, which is defined as follows for the purpose of the study:

“ [...] measures and investments are considered cost-efficient, when they are designed to 1) have a sustained long-term impact on energy savings and emission reductions, 2) address the root causes of energy and transport poverty, 3) avoid or mitigate adverse effects on vulnerable groups and provide additional co-benefits, 4) ensure accessibility of benefits to vulnerable groups and are well targeted to their needs, 5) improve the affordability of energy and transport services for vulnerable groups, and 6) provide comprehensive administrative support to facilitate access.” (p. 4).

For **transport** two groups of good practices were identified in Ludden et al. (2024). The first group are measures to provide access to zero- and low-emission vehicles and bicycles, the following were showcased: a cargo bike funding programme in Aachen, Germany; the French green bonus for zero-emission vehicles and the French social leasing scheme (see Box 12); the vehicle scrappage scheme set up in the context of the London Ultra Low Emission Zone and the Dutch subsidy programme for zero-emission commercial vehicles. The second group are measures that incentivise the use of affordable and accessible public transport. The study highlighted the following schemes: demand responsive transport in the rural areas of the Spanish region of Castilla y Leon, the cross-border on-demand public transport service in the greater Geneva area (Switzerland and France), the Mobitwin system in the region of Flanders that connects vulnerable people with volunteer drivers, the Mobility Wallets scheme piloted in a number of US cities, and the concessionary bus travel pass of the UK.

⁵² <https://smart-cities-marketplace.ec.europa.eu/about>

⁵³ <https://netzerocities.eu/>

Box 12 France's social leasing initiative.

Launched in December 2023, France's social leasing initiative exemplifies a targeted approach to democratising access to electric vehicles (EVs) and addressing the social equity challenges of the green transition. By offering EVs at affordable monthly rates of EUR 49 to 150, the program enables lower- and middle-income, car-dependent households to participate in the EV transition groups that are otherwise most vulnerable to rising mobility costs under the EU ETS2. The scheme, which combines public subsidies with leasing mechanisms, saw strong uptake underscoring both need and public interest. The initiative has income-based eligibility and ensures vehicle affordability and environmental standards.

Another study (Cludius et al., 2024a) surveyed policies and measures that tackle transport poverty in thirteen EU Member States⁵⁴. The lessons drawn from this analysis are also relevant for the set-up of the national Social Climate Plans. Price-related measures such as social tariffs, discounts and reduced or free tickets and passes, are already implemented in all of the surveyed Member States, at national and/or local level. There are also various examples of financial measures. These include subsidies, vouchers or tax exemptions that facilitate access to clean and accessible transport, as well as the creation of funds for financing availability or accessibility projects, or to finance pricing measures. While already widely implemented, they are however not always aimed at tackling transport poverty. Social and legislative measures involve the definition and identification of vulnerable groups, the establishment of procedures and of funds for investment and other measures. There is a wide variety of processes and procedures across the surveyed Member States, and they can take place at both national and local level. The processes are often complex, involving data collection, data analysis and cooperation across many stakeholders. Infrastructure measures also play a role in alleviating transport poverty. Examples are the extension of the public transport, cycling or walking infrastructure, the creation of public transport hubs or improving the accessibility of public transport infrastructure for people with disabilities or reduced mobility. The authors point out that they are an “[...] important factor of integration, both from a social point of view, and from the perspective of consolidating local links between urban centres and the peri-urban, rural or small-urban communities” (p. 76).

For **buildings**, three main groups of good practices were identified by Ludden et al. (2024). The first group includes support for deep and cost-effective energy renovations, particularly for vulnerable households and those in poorly performing buildings. Among the highlighted examples are: the ‘Factory Reconstruction Grant’ scheme in Estonia, which funds prefabricated renovation of Soviet-era apartment blocks; the ‘Community Energy Savings Programme’ in the UK, which targeted energy-poor neighbourhoods with whole-house retrofits; the ‘Home Energy Efficiency Programmes’ for Scotland, combining grants and zero-interest loans tailored to different needs; and the ‘Gent knapt op’ scheme in Belgium, which provides post-paid renovation support to vulnerable owner-occupants in poor housing conditions. The second group comprises measures that improve access to affordable, energy-efficient housing. Notable examples include the ‘City of Vienna’ subsidised housing model, which blends low-interest public loans, capped rents, and sustainability criteria in developer competitions; and the ‘Klimabonus’ initiative in German cities, designed to prevent “renovictions” by covering additional housing costs for energy-poor tenants receiving income support. The third group involves **measures that support** decarbonising heating and cooling, for example: Austria’s ‘Clean Heating for All programme’, which subsidises climate-neutral heating for low-income households; the ‘ASTER retrofit model’ in the UK, which supports social housing retrofits using energy performance contracts; and Italy’s ‘Reddito Energetico’, which combines solar PV installations with a social income stream for low-income families.

⁵⁴ The following Member States were surveyed: Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Malta, the Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovenia and Spain.

Box 13 **Poland's draft Social Climate Plan.**

Poland, as the largest Social Climate Fund beneficiary, will receive approximately EUR 11.4 billion from the Fund, with a total budget of at least EUR 15.2 billion when including national contributions. These funds will be allocated to direct income support, long-term investments in building renovation, heat source exchange and decarbonisation, social housing, support to vulnerable micro-enterprises and energy communities, development of public transport, on-demand transport, and other sustainable mobility solutions (Polish Ministry of Development Funds and Regional Policy, 2025).

To ensure the effectiveness and fairness of the Social Climate Plans, Member States must prioritise clear and well-structured interventions that are easier to implement and more likely to gain public acceptance (EEA and Eurofound, 2021). Poorly targeted support can lead to inefficiencies and may fail to address those most in need. Research highlights that well-designed climate policies can deliver substantial co-benefits for low-income households and marginalised communities, including improved air quality, healthier living conditions, and reduced environmental inequalities (Cludius et al., 2024a). Since pricing policies come with the risk of exacerbating social disparities and social acceptance, redistribution measures must therefore ensure that they are integrated, transparent, and tailored to societal needs.

5. Concluding remarks

This report has explored the opportunities and challenges presented by the introduction of the EU ETS2 for the buildings and road transport sectors, two areas that have historically been difficult to decarbonise. The analysis underscores the critical role of carbon pricing in driving change but also emphasises that its success depends on thoughtful complementary policy design, broad public support, and social fairness.

The report shows that while emissions in buildings and road transport have gradually declined over the past two decades, the pace of reduction has been insufficient to align with EU climate targets. Progress has largely been driven by energy efficiency improvements and fuel switching, with only limited structural changes. The uptake of key technologies, such as heat pumps, electric vehicles, and deep renovations, has accelerated in recent years but remains uneven across Member States. These historical trends demonstrate both the scale of the challenge and the potential leverage of introducing a robust carbon price signal under the EU ETS2.

With the EU ETS2 as part of its package of decarbonisation policies, the EU has included a key instrument to achieve its climate targets. Up to now it has been a challenge to decarbonise the sectors covered by the EU ETS2 due to their decentralised nature. The EU ETS2 provides an essential additional incentive. Given the importance of the EU ETS2, this report depicts the way in which it has been set up and how it will reinforce other EU decarbonisation policies. It highlighted the mechanisms that have been put in place to ensure a fair transition in a context of geopolitical instability potentially affecting energy prices, alongside the existing socio-economic disparities in the EU. More specifically, these mechanisms initially included the possibility to delay the start of the EU ETS2 in case of excessively high oil and gas prices. This provision was subsequently superseded by the provisional political agreement between the European Council and the European Parliament on the European Climate Law to postpone the start of the ETS2 to 2028. The two remaining mechanisms are the use of the MSR2 in cases of fast price increases or when prices exceed a certain level in the early years, and the establishment of the Social Climate Fund. Together with Member States' contributions, the latter will mobilise in total EUR 86.7 billion to finance the national Social Climate Plans of the EU Member States to help vulnerable households, vulnerable micro-enterprises, and vulnerable transport users who are affected by higher energy and transport costs during the green transition. Part of the auctioning revenues of the EU ETS2 will be set aside for the National Climate Plans, that are prepared by the Member States and must be submitted to the European Commission. The remaining auctioning revenues will also be distributed to the Member States, that are bound to prioritise climate action and social measures when using the revenues. There is mandatory reporting to ensure compliance and transparency, which are essential for the trust and credibility of the system.

Embedding the ETS2 within a broader, supportive policy framework is therefore essential. Carbon pricing alone cannot deliver the transformation needed without complementary policies and investments that enable low-carbon alternatives and address social inequalities. The alignment of EU-level instruments, such as the Effort Sharing Regulation, Energy Taxation Directive, Energy Performance of Buildings Directive, the CO₂ emission performance standards, the EU ETS, and the Social Climate Fund, with EU climate targets and national strategies will be crucial. In this context, the transparent use and communication of ETS revenues is key, not only to maximise social impact, but to secure public trust and legitimacy.

Addressing the social dimensions of the transition remains a central concern. Effectively tackling energy and transport poverty and supporting vulnerable households and transport users requires a targeted approach that recognises the distinct characteristics of vulnerable groups and ensures a fair and inclusive foundation for intervention. Various indicators on transport and energy poverty and vulnerability have already been put forward in academic literature and in policy reports, each shedding light on a particular dimension. It is important to keep track of research on new indicators that could be useful to add.

Moreover, the collection of reliable data, with adequate detail regarding relevant personal characteristics and the spatial dimension, is a prerequisite for the construction and assessment of indicators that can be used for this purpose. So is the repetition of data collection at regular intervals, which allows for a regular update of the assessment, such that corrective actions can be taken in case of unwanted evolutions.

Literature shows that vulnerability to energy and transport poverty varies widely depending on income levels, housing quality, access to mobility, and geographic location. Without targeted and inclusive policy responses, carbon pricing risks placing a disproportionate burden on the most disadvantaged.

The report also maps out the broad range of decarbonisation actions available to households and transport users, categorised by strategy (avoid, shift, improve), by timeframe (short-, medium-, and long-term), and by the level at which action is taken (individual, community, or policy level). While some measures can be adopted quickly with minimal effort, others require significant investment and structural support. The report therefore highlights the importance of tailored national measures to broaden participation and access to clean energy and transport. These actions cover a broad spectrum of behavioural, technological, and policy measures that together enable emissions reductions across both sectors. In transport, avoid strategies include reducing trip frequency and distance, while shift strategies involve increasing the use of public transport and rail, expanding active mobility, and accelerating the uptake of electric mobility. Improve strategies focus on enhancing vehicle efficiency and supporting infrastructure adaptation. In buildings, actions span from behavioural energy savings to deep renovation, electrification through heat pumps, and the integration of renewable energy systems supported by enabling policies and financial schemes. Across both sectors, prioritising investment in high capacity, low carbon modes such as public transport, rail, and inland waterways, is essential to reduce dependency on fossil fuel-based mobility while ensuring accessibility and resilience for all users. In the buildings sector, comparable structural measures include expanding renewable-based district heating and supporting the development of energy communities, which strengthen local supply security, enable collective investment in clean technologies, and enhance the affordability of low carbon heating solutions.

The national Social Climate Plans will serve as a cornerstone for ensuring that the EU ETS2 delivers not only emissions reductions, but also social fairness. To be effective, the Social Climate Plans must go beyond basic income support and embrace a multidimensional approach that combines direct assistance with long-term structural measures. This includes investments in energy-efficient housing, accessible and affordable sustainable mobility, and the removal of barriers that prevent vulnerable groups from participating in the energy transition. Crucially, the Social Climate Plans must be based on a clear understanding of national and regional circumstances, informed by robust data on energy and transport poverty. Transparency, inclusiveness, and accountability are essential throughout the design and implementation phases. Lessons from past carbon pricing efforts, both within the EU and internationally, underscore the importance of clearly communicating how revenues are used and ensuring that support is perceived as fair and effective. Social Climate Plans should therefore prioritise measures that are targeted, easy to access, and aligned with broader national climate and social policies. Done well, these plans can reinforce public trust, foster social cohesion, and act as enablers of a just and enduring transition.

In conclusion, the success of the EU ETS2 will depend not only on price signals and emissions reductions, but on the extent to which Member States design and implement key complementary measures, including flanking measures for the decarbonisation of the ETS2 sectors – such as avoid-shift-improve - and socially responsive policies that leave no one behind in the transition to a climate-neutral future.

Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Name
ACEA	European Automobile Manufacturers Association
AEA	Annual Emission Allocation
AFID	Alternative Fuel Infrastructure Directive
AFIR	Alternative Fuel Infrastructure Regulation
AFIR	Alternative Fuel Infrastructure Regulation
AROP	At risk of poverty
ASI	'Avoid-Shift- Improve' (typology)
AUB	Arrears on Utility Bills
AVR	Accreditation and Verification Regulation
BEV	Battery electric vehicle
CBAM	Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism
CF	Cohesion Fund
CH ₄	Methane
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide
CO ₂ e	Carbon Dioxide-Equivalent
CRF	Common Reporting Format
CRT	Common Reporting Tables
DHC	District Heating and Cooling
EASAC	European Academies' Science Advisory Council
EC	European Commission
EEA	European Environment Agency
EED	Energy Efficiency Directive
EEX	European Energy Exchange
EFTA	European Free Trade Association
EHPA	European Heat Pump Association
ELTIS	European Local Transport Information Service
EMPL	Committee on Employment and Social Affairs
ENVI Committee	Committee on Environment, Public Health and Food Safety
EPAH	Energy Poverty Advisory Hub
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
EPC	Energy Performance Certificate
ERDF	European Regional Development Fund
ESMA	European Securities and Markets Authority
ESR	Effort Sharing Regulation
ETC CM	European Topic Centre on Climate Change Mitigation
ETD	Energy Tax Directive
ETS	Emissions Trading System
EU	European Union
EU ETS1	The original EU Emissions Trading System
EU ETS2	The new EU ETS covering emissions from buildings, road transport and additional sectors
EU27	European Union with 27 Member States (from 2020)
EUR	Euros
EV	Electric Vehicle
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
HBS	Household Budgetary Survey
HDV	Heavy-Duty Vehicle
HGV	Heavy Goods Vehicle
ICE	Intercontinental Exchange
IEA	International Energy Agency
IKW	Inability to Keep home adequately Warm

Abbreviation	Name
ILUC	Indirect Land Use Change
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
ITF	International Transport Forum
JRC	The Joint Research Centre
JTF	Just Transition Fund
km	Kilometre
kWh	Kilowatt-Hour
LCV	Light Commercial Vehicle
LDR	Presence of Leak, Damp or Rot
LIHC	Low-Income-High-Cost
LPG	Liquified Petroleum Gas
LULUCF	Land Use, Land-use Change, and Forestry
m	meters
MEPS	Minimum Energy Performance Standards
MRR	Monitoring and Reporting Regulation
MRV	Monitoring, Reporting and Verification
MSR	Market Stability Reserve
MSR2	Market Stability Reserve linked to the EU ETS2
Mtoe	Million Tonnes of Oil Equivalent
Mtonnes	Million Tonnes
N ₂ O	Nitrous Oxide
NECP	National Energy and Climate Plan
NEHG	Nationales Emissionszertifikatehandelsgesetz (Austrian National Emissions Trading Act)
nEHS	German National Emissions Trading System
nEZs	nEHS certificates
NZEB	Nearly Zero Energy Building
OTC	Over The Counter
PAYS	Pay-as-You-Save (scheme)
PHEV	Plug-In Electric Hybrid
PPS	Purchasing Power Standard
PtL	Power-to-Liquid
PV	Photovoltaic
RED	Renewable Energy Directive
SIEC	Standard International Energy Products Classification
SILC	Statistics on Income and Living Conditions
TCO	Total Cost of Ownership
TEN-T	Trans-European Transport Network
TJ	Terajoule
TNAC	Total Number of Allowances in Circulation
TTW	Tank-To-Wheel
UNECE	United Nations Economic Commission for Europe
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
VAT	Value-Added Tax
WLTP	World Harmonised Light Vehicle Test Procedure
WTT	Well-To-Tank
ZEV	Zero-Emission Vehicles
ZLEV	Zero and Low Emission Vehicle

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Annex 1 Factors considered in the decomposition analysis of the CO₂ emissions from passenger cars and heavy goods vehicles trucks

The decomposition analysis for the CO₂ emissions of passenger cars and heavy goods vehicles (HGVs) of >3.5 tonnes used the same methodology as in TERM 2021 (EEA, 2022). The following six potential driving factors behind the emission trends were considered:

- **Passenger/freight transport activity.** For cars: the number of passenger-kilometres travelled by land-based passenger transport modes, namely passenger cars, powered two-wheelers, buses and coaches, railways, trams and metros. For HGVs: the number of tonne-kilometres carried by inland waterways, railways, pipelines and road transport.
- **Modal share.** The share of passenger-kilometres travelled by car in overall passenger transport activity/the share of tonne-kilometres delivered by HGVs in overall freight transport activity.
- **Energy efficiency.** The energy consumed per passenger-kilometre by passenger cars/energy consumed per tonne-kilometre by HGVs. This includes the energy consumption of fossil fuels, biofuels and electricity.
- **Effect of electrification.** Approximated as the share of non-electric energy (fuels) in the energy consumption by cars. This factor is not used for HGV analysis.
- **Biofuel effect.** Measured using the share of fossil fuels in non-electric energy consumption by passenger cars/HGVs. Biofuels are attributed a CO₂ emission factor of zero in the climate accounting. However, for the methane (CH₄) and nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions the emission factor is nonzero in climate accounting. Therefore, this effect is only considered in the decomposition analysis of the CO₂ emissions.
- **Emission intensity of fuels.** In the decomposition analysis of the CO₂ emissions, this is defined as the CO₂ emissions per unit of fossil fuel consumed (by cars/HGVs).

The following two graphs present the evolution of each of the driving factors in the period 2000-2023. The first graph considers the driving factors for the CO₂ emissions of passenger cars, and the second one for heavy goods vehicles.

Figure A1 Changes in the driving factors considered in the decomposition analysis of the CO₂ emissions from passenger cars in the EU-27, 2000-2023 (2000=1).

Note: The numbers for 2023 refer to the ratio in 2023 relative to 2000.

Source: EEA compilation based on sources summarised in Table A1.

Figure A2 Changes in the driving factors considered in the decomposition analysis of the CO₂ emissions from heavy-duty trucks cars in the EU-27, 2000-2023 (2000=1).

Note: The numbers for 2023 refer to the ratio in 2023 relative to 2000.

Source: EEA compilation based on sources summarised in Table A1.

Table A1 Data source for the decomposition analysis.

Parameter	Data source
CO ₂ emissions from passenger cars and heavy-duty trucks and buses	Greenhouse gas emissions inventory (EEA, 2025d)
Total inland passenger-kilometres	Statistical pocketbook 2025 (EC, 2025f)
Total inland freight tonne-kilometres	
Total car passenger-kilometres	
Total tonne-kilometres transported by heavy goods vehicles	
Electricity consumption by road transport (in the decomposition analysis this is assigned completely to passenger cars)	Eurostat, complete energy balances (Eurostat, 2025a)
Non-electric energy consumption (fuels) by passenger cars and heavy-duty trucks and buses	Greenhouse gas emissions inventory (EEA, 2025d)
The consumption of fossil fuels by passenger cars and heavy-duty vehicles	Greenhouse gas emissions inventory (EEA, 2025d)
The share of emissions and energy consumption by heavy goods vehicles in the emissions and energy consumption of the category heavy goods vehicles and buses of the GHG emissions inventory	EC (EC, 2021d)

Annex 2 EU legislation relevant for the decarbonisation of road transport and buildings

This annex reports the legislative status up until 18 November 2025.

5.1. Horizontal EU legislation

The EU Emissions Trading System for stationary installations, aviation and maritime transport (EU ETS) – Directive (EU) 2023/959 and Regulation (EU) 2023/957

Type of instrument	<p>Cap-and-trade (tradeable emission permits) – market-based policy</p> <p>In the ‘cap-and-trade’ system of the EU ETS there is an emissions cap; companies must be able to submit an allowance for each tonne of emissions. Companies can choose to reduce their emissions or to buy allowances from the other EU ETS companies. The price of the allowances is determined in the market. The ceiling of the EU ETS decreases each year according to a linear path.</p>
Main elements	<p>The 2023 directive specifies that by 2030 the EU ETS emissions have to be 62% lower than in 2005, instead of 43% before. To achieve this reduction, the number of allowances will be reduced following a linear path, with an annual reduction factor of 4.3% from 2024 and 4.4% from 2028.</p> <p>Until the end of 2023 the EU ETS applied to GHG emissions from power plants, from energy-intensive industry production facilities, and from flights in and between countries of the European Economic Area. Among other provisions, the recent amendments have expanded the scope of the EU ETS to CO₂ emissions from large ships, and as from 2026 to N₂O and CH₄ emissions from this sector (100% of voyages between EU ports and emissions within EU ports, and 50% for other voyages from or to EU ports).</p> <p>The EU ETS operates in all EU Member States, Iceland, Liechtenstein, and Norway. The United Kingdom stopped participating with the end of EU membership and established its own system. Since 2020 Switzerland’s ETS is linked to the EU ETS⁵⁵.</p> <p>The emission allowances are partly auctioned and partly distributed for free depending on the industries’ risk of carbon leakage. Under the amended directive the free allowances will be phased out gradually, together with the introduction of the carbon border adjustment mechanism (CBAM – Regulation (EU) 2023/956). The CBAM aims to avoid carbon leakage. It is a pricing system that will apply to energy-intensive products imported into the EU.</p> <p>After each year, the companies must surrender enough allowances to cover their emissions, else heavy fines apply. If a company reduces its emissions and has spare allowances, it can keep them to cover future emissions or sell them to another company. The number of allowances is limited through the Market Stability Reserve, which allows for a better matching between the supply of allowances to be auctioned and demand.</p>
Relevance for road transport	<p>Part of the well-to-tank emissions from road transport are covered by the EU ETS even without the separate EU ETS2:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the CO₂ emissions from the production of electricity used by electric vehicles - the CO₂ emissions from fuel production at refineries covered by the EU ETS.

⁵⁵ Switzerland, Federal Office for the Environment (2019)

	With the expected increase in the number of electric vehicles in the future, an increasing share of road transport will be (indirectly) covered by the EU ETS.
Relevance for buildings	The price of electricity used in buildings already includes a carbon price.

The Effort Sharing Regulation (ESR) – Regulation (EU) 2023/857

Type of instrument	<p>Target setting for emission reductions (general)</p> <p>The regulation covers all GHG emissions that are not covered by the EU ETS or the Land Use, Land-use Change, and Forestry (LULUCF) Regulation.</p> <p>Apart from the objective at EU-level, the regulation also sets binding emission reduction targets per Member State.</p> <p>Member States that overachieve their targets are allowed to trade with those that underachieve their targets.</p>
Main elements	<p>The regulation sets the objective to reduce GHG emissions in 2030 by 40% compared to 2005 (EU-level). This is more ambitious than the target of -30% that was set previously in Regulation (EU) 2018/42.</p> <p>The regulation also sets stricter targets for the Member States than the previous regulation.</p>
Relevance for road transport	<p>Transport (including road transport) is one of the sectors covered by the regulation. In order to meet the targets of the ESR, Member States therefore also consider transport in their policies and measures.</p> <p>However, there is no separate target for transport or its subsectors.</p>
Relevance for buildings	<p>Built environment is one of the sectors covered by the regulation.</p> <p>The ESR sets binding national climate targets with all emissions in built environment for Member States.</p> <p>There is also no separate target for buildings.</p>

The Energy Efficiency Directive (EED) – Directive 2023/1791

Type of instrument	Target setting for energy efficiency (general)
Main elements	<p>The Directive sets the following targets:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A reduction of energy consumption by at least 11.7% by 2030, compared to the 2020 EU Reference Scenario. - The maximum final energy consumption in 2030 is 763 Mtoe. - The indicative maximum primary energy consumption in 2030 is 992.5 Mtoe.
Relevance for road transport	<p>The energy consumption by transport (including road transport) is part of energy consumption.</p> <p>No separate target is set for transport or its subsectors.</p> <p>For the provisions about the energy efficiency in final energy consumption, each Member State can decide to include transport or not.</p>

Relevance for buildings	<p>No separate target is set for buildings or households</p> <p>This directive mandates measures to increase energy savings in both public and private buildings, including minimum energy performance standards and energy savings obligations.</p> <p>New annual end-use energy savings in final energy consumption of 1.3% in 2024-2025, 1.5% in 2026-2027, and 1.9% from 2028 onward, which include energy savings through energy consumption reduction measures in building.</p> <p>Buildings owned and occupied by public bodies must renovate 3% of their total floor area annually.</p> <p>In particular, the focus of energy audits under the EED – even for buildings and households – goes beyond the technical characteristics of the buildings and includes e.g. all electricity uses and behavioural changes such as impact of occupant activity on energy consumption</p>
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The Renewable Energy Directive (RED) – Directive (EU) 2023/2413

Type of instrument	Blending mandate / emission intensity reduction target
Main elements	<p>In 2023 the previous Renewable Energy Directive II (RED II) (Directive 2018/2001/EU) was amended. The amended directive – RED III (Directive (EU) 2023/2413) – sets a higher target for the share of energy from renewable sources in gross final consumption of energy in the European Community of at least 45%, instead of 32%. For transport, Member States must either ensure that the share of renewable energy in transport is at least 29% by 2030 (instead of 14% under the RED II) or that the GHG emission intensity is reduced by at least 14.5% by 2030, compared to a baseline. As in the RED II, multipliers apply for fuels produced with certain feedstocks and for renewable electricity. They depend on the transport subsector where the energy is consumed. Also, as in the RED II, the RED III sets limits for biofuels with high risk of Indirect Land Use Change (ILUC): liquid biomass and fuels from biomass that significantly expand cultivation on land with high carbon storage. Moreover, the share of fuels based on a number of feedstocks that can be processed with mature technologies (including used cooking oils and animal fats) should not exceed 1.7%.</p> <p>While the RED II target applied to energy consumed by road and rail transport, the new targets apply to all energy consumption by transport. Another new feature is that renewable fuels and renewable electricity count towards the emission intensity reduction target based on their GHG emission reductions.</p> <p>The 2023 Directive requires that the combined share of advanced biofuels and biogas and of renewable fuels of non-biological origin in the energy supplied to the transport sector is at least 1% in 2025 and 5.5% in 2030, of which a share of at least 1 percentage point is from renewable fuels of non-biological origin in 2030. It also includes a credit system for the supply of renewable electricity to the transport sector through public charging stations. Private charging stations may also be taken into account here on condition that it can be proved that the renewable electricity is only supplied to electric vehicles.</p> <p>The RED is complemented by Delegated Regulation (EU) 2019/807 which includes criteria for identifying feedstocks with high ILUC risk and general criteria for certifying biofuels with low ILUC risk. Criteria are proposed for improvements in agricultural practices (additionality measures) that allow increasing the yield of food and feed crops on land already used for this purpose or growing such crops on unused or abandoned land.</p>

	<p>The European Commission is required to review the criteria defined in the high-ILUC delegated act by September 2023. The RED III requires that this review assess whether to reduce the threshold of the maximum share of average annual expansion of the global production area in high carbon-stock land before a feedstock is classified as high ILUC-risk. The Commission is also required to review the data underpinning the delegated act and update the act when necessary.</p> <p>In addition, separate targets are set for aviation and maritime transport, with the REFuelEU Aviation (Regulation (EU) 2023/2405) and FuelEU Maritime (Regulation (EU) 2023/1805).</p>
Relevance for road transport	The energy used by road transport is covered by the RED.
Relevance for buildings	<p>Integration of renewable energy in buildings, encouraging the adoption of renewable energy sources for heating and cooling.</p> <p>Promotes solar, geothermal, and biomass systems in new/renovated buildings.</p> <p>Supports renewable-powered district heating for urban areas.</p> <p>It requires Member States to establish a favourable regulatory environment that supports the growth of renewable technologies, such as solar, wind, and geothermal, within the building sector.</p> <p>Annual 1.1% increase in renewable heating and cooling use.</p>

The Energy Taxation Directive (ETD) – Directive 2003/96/EC and amendments

Type of instrument	Rules for energy taxation (market-based policy)
Main elements	The Directive determines the EU rules and minimum excises that Member States should apply to energy products and electricity.
Proposed changes	<p>In 2021 the European Commission published a proposal for recast: COM (2021) 563 final. The legislative process is still ongoing.</p> <p>The proposal includes, among others:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - a new structure of the taxation tariffs, based on the energy content and the environmental characteristics of the fuels and electricity (highest tariffs for the most polluting fuels) - a broader tax base by including more products in the scope of the Directive and by abolishing some exemptions and rebates.
Relevance for road transport	<p>Transport (including transport by passenger cars and light commercial vehicles) uses energy products and electricity that are covered by this Directive.</p> <p>For road transport fuels most Member States apply tariffs that are well above the current minimum levels.</p>
Relevance for buildings	Building energy products, including natural gas, and fuel oil, and electricity are covered by this Directive.

5.2. Sectoral Policies

The CO₂ emission performance standards for cars, light commercial vehicles and heavy-duty vehicles – Regulation (EU) 2023/851 and Regulation (EU) 2024/1610

Type of instrument	<p>Emission standards</p> <p>The binding CO₂ emission performance standards apply to the average emissions of each manufacturer's new registered vehicles across the EU, rather than to each individual new vehicle or Member State.</p>
Main elements of legislation prior to Fit for 55 or prior to recent amendment	<p>In 2019, The regulation set EU fleet-wide targets for reducing the average CO₂ emissions from such new trucks. The targets of the 2019 regulation were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - from 2025, a reduction of 15% compared with the reference period (1 July 2019 to 30 June 2020); and - from 2030 onwards, a 30% reduction compared with the same reference period. <p>The regulation also included an incentive mechanism for zero and low emission vehicles (ZLEV), as well as a credit and debt system.</p>
Main elements – passenger cars and light commercial vehicles	<p>CO₂ emissions standards have long been applied in Europe, starting in 2008 with a voluntary agreement between the European Commission and the European Automobile Manufacturers Association (ACEA) on emissions from new cars. In 2009, this was replaced by mandatory targets for cars, which were tightened over time, and in 2011 a similar approach was introduced for new light commercial vehicles. The regulation was recast in 2019 and has been amended recently in 2023.</p> <p>Under the amended regulation of 2023, the 2030 CO₂ target for the entire EU fleet is strengthened as follows: -55% for new cars and -50% for new LCVs, instead of -37.5% and 31% respectively in the 2019 regulation. From 2035, the target for both new cars and LCVs is 0 g/km. The credits for ZLEVs, that were included in the 2019 regulation, will disappear. The European Commission is required to conduct a review of the effectiveness and impact of the regulation in 2026.</p> <p>According to a non-binding recital in the regulation, the Commission will also make a proposal so that new vehicles with internal combustion engines, outside the scope of the fleet standards, may still be sold new after 2035, provided they run solely and permanently on renewable fuels of non-biological origin (i.e. e-fuels or synthetic fuels produced from CO₂ and hydrogen and produced from renewable energy).⁵⁶</p> <p>The system provides flexibility for manufacturers to decide how to comply and thus aims to increase the cost-effectiveness of achieving the standards. For the intermediate years they can invest in R&D to increase the fuel efficiency of cars with an internal combustion engine, or to make ZLEVs cheaper and/or better performing, or they can increase the share of smaller and more fuel-efficient cars or pool with other manufacturers.</p> <p>The CO₂ emissions for assessing the compliance with the targets are determined in laboratory tests. In the past, it was found that manufacturers partially met their targets by optimising their vehicle emissions during the test cycle, rather than</p>

⁵⁶ The political guidelines for 2024-2029 for the next European Commission of Ursula von der Leyen as candidate for the Presidency of the European Commission mention the following "..., the 2035 climate neutrality target for cars creates predictability for investors and manufacturers. Getting there will require a technology-neutral approach, in which e-fuels have a role to play through a targeted amendment of the regulation as part of the foreseen review." (von der Leyen, 2024, p. 9)

	<p>reducing emissions on the road. Therefore, a new test procedure, the World Harmonised Light Vehicle Test Procedure (WLTP), was developed (UNECE, 2014) instead of the earlier New European Driving Cycle. Since 2021, the assessment is based entirely on the WLTP data. To prevent the gap between tested and real emissions from evolving unfavourably, the European Commission is also collecting data on the actual CO₂ emissions and energy consumption. An implementing regulation sets out the rules for data collection by manufacturers and national authorities. Based on the data collected for 2021 and 2022, EEA (2024c) reports on the real-world CO₂ emissions and fuel consumption from passenger cars on the road.</p> <p>In the Automotive Package presented by the European Commission in December 2025, the existing CO₂ emission performance standards for cars and vans are reviewed, alongside other changes. From 2035 onwards, carmakers will need to comply with a 90% tailpipe emissions reduction target, while the remaining 10% emissions will need to be compensated through the use of low-carbon steel Made in the Union, or from e-fuels and biofuels. (EC, 2025d). It also includes a reduction of the 2030 CO₂ vans target from 50% to 40%. Regarding corporate vehicles, mandatory targets are set at the Member State level to support the zero- and low-emission vehicle uptake by large companies.</p>
<p>Main elements – heavy-duty vehicles</p>	<p>In 2019, Regulation (EU) 2019/1242, setting the first EU CO₂ emission standards for heavy-duty vehicles (HDVs) was adopted. It covered large trucks, which account for 65% of new HDV sales in 2023. Under the new Regulation (EU) 2024/1610 more vehicle types fall under the scope of the regulation: more truck types and also buses, coaches, trailers, and vocational vehicles. Together these vehicle types accounted for 92% of new HDVs sold in 2023.</p> <p>The emission reduction targets are as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Previously regulated trucks: -15% for 2025, -45% for 2030, -65% for 2035 and -90% for 2040. As before, the baseline is the emissions in the 2019 reporting period. Compared to the 2019 regulation, the target for 2030 is stricter (-45% instead of -30%) and new targets have been introduced for 2035 and 2040. - Newly regulated trucks, coaches and interurban buses: -45% for 2030, -65% for 2035 and -90% for 2040. The baseline is the emissions in the 2021 or 2025 reporting period. - Vocational vehicles: -65% for 2035 and -90% for 2040. The baseline is the emissions in the 2025 reporting period. - Semi-trailers and drawbar/centre-axle trailers: respectively -10% and -7.5% in 2030 and afterwards, compared to emissions in the 2025 reporting period. - City buses: 90% of new sales in 2030 are ZEVs and 100% in 2035. <p>A ZLEV incentive mechanism was included in the 2019 regulation, but it will be phased out from 2030 onwards. The credit and debt system that was in the 2019 regulation is reformed. Under the new regulation trading is allowed. This is without limitation between connected manufacturers. Between non-connected manufacturers ZEVs can be traded up to 5% of the value of all heavy-duty vehicle sales of the receiver.</p> <p>Recital 13b of the regulation requires the Commission to assess the role of allowing vehicles running exclusively on CO₂ neutral fuels to be used by manufacturers in achieving compliance. This should be reassessed in the review of 2027.</p> <p>In the Automotive Package presented by the European Commission in December 2025, a targeted amendment is proposed to the CO₂ emission standards for</p>

	heavy-duty vehicles with a flexibility easing the compliance with the 2030 targets. (EC, 2025d)
Relevance for road transport	The CO ₂ emission performance standards apply to the new passenger cars, light commercial vehicles and almost all heavy-duty vehicles sold in the EU ⁵⁷ .
Relevance for buildings	Not applicable

The Alternative Fuel Infrastructure Regulation (AFIR) – Regulation (EU) 2023/1804

Type of instrument	Target setting for alternative fuel infrastructure provision
Main elements	<p>The Alternative Fuel Infrastructure Regulation (AFIR) was adopted in 2023 and replaces the former Alternative Fuel Infrastructure Directive (AFID - Directive 2014/94/EU). The AFIR introduces the definition of the target infrastructure in terms of capacity requirement rather than number of charging points. The capacity based AFIR target requires 0.8 kW of installed capacity per plug-in hybrid electric vehicle and 1.3 kW per battery electric vehicle, provided through publicly accessible charging stations.</p> <p>The AFIR requires the installation of charging and refuelling points targets for light duty and heavy-duty road vehicles on main roads (TEN-T core and comprehensive network). EU Member States also have to ensure that a number of recharging stations are available for heavy-duty vehicles in urban nodes and in safe and secure parking.</p> <p>The regulation aims to ensuring user-friendliness of recharging infrastructure (for example, via provisions regarding payment options, price transparency and consumer information, non-discriminatory practices, smart recharging).</p> <p>The AFIR also sets targets for hydrogen and liquefied/compressed natural gas infrastructure. In addition, it strengthens the governance for the monitoring progress.</p>
Relevance for road transport	The legislation aims to support the transition to alternative fuel vehicles.
Relevance for buildings	Not applicable

The Toll Directive – Directive (EU) 2022/362

Type of instrument	Rules for tolls and road use charges (market-based policy)
Main elements	<p>The Toll Directive sets rules for tolls and user charges in Member States that use such instruments. The 2022 Directive expresses a preference for distance-based charges rather than time-based charges. The latter should be phased out.</p> <p>While the previous Directives only set rules for charges on vehicles with a technically permissible maximum laden mass exceeding 3.5 tonnes, the 2022 Directive provides rules for both light- and heavy-duty vehicles.</p>

⁵⁷ After Brexit, the transitional arrangements specified that the UK remained part of the EU car CO₂ regulation until 2020. Hence, cars sold in the UK in 2020 counted towards the EU target, but not after that date.

	The 2022 Directive introduces the differentiation according to the CO ₂ emissions of the vehicles and allows for a favourable treatment of zero-emission vehicles.
Relevance for road transport	<p>The Directive sets the general conditions for the tolls and user charges imposed on road vehicles in Member States that make use of these instruments. It covers both light- and heavy-duty vehicles. The provisions for the CO₂ differentiation are aimed to incentivise the use of less emitting vehicles.</p> <p>When Member States charge passenger cars, they also have to do so for light commercial vehicles. The opposite is not the case.</p>
Relevance for buildings	Not applicable

The Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) – Directive (EU) 2024/1275

Type of instrument	Target setting for alternative fuel infrastructure provision
Main elements	<p>In 2024 the EPBD was revised. According to the revised EPBD of 2024 Member States are required to simplify, streamline and accelerate the procedure for the installation of recharging points. Targets are set for the infrastructure for sustainable mobility in buildings. Barriers to the installation of recharging points in multi-apartment buildings need to be removed. Recharging points are required to support smart charging and, where appropriate, bi-directional charging.</p> <p>By the end of 2025 the European Commission shall publish guidance for the Member States on the fire safety of buildings with the deployment of batteries and recharging infrastructure.</p>
Relevance for road transport	<p>The legislation aims to support the transition to alternative fuel vehicles.</p> <p>The legislation deals with infrastructure in buildings and adjacent carparks and is complementary to the Alternative Fuel Infrastructure Regulation that deals with publicly accessible infrastructure for road vehicles.</p>
Relevance for buildings	The EPBD is the cornerstone of the EU building policy framework and mandates that all new buildings must be nearly zero-energy buildings (NZEBs) by 2030. It also includes obligations for improving the energy performance of existing buildings, with requirements for regular energy audits and Building Renovation Passports. It aims to reduce emissions through energy efficiency by setting performance standards for new builds and deep renovations. Member States must develop national long-term renovation strategies to decarbonise the building stock by 2050.

Ecodesign and Energy Labelling Directive 2009/125/EC and Regulation (EU) 2017/1369

Type of instrument	Informational, minimum energy performance and environmental impact for consumers
Main elements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ecodesign: Sets minimum energy and environmental performance standards for energy-using and energy-related products. • Energy Labelling: Requires standardized labels for products, displaying energy efficiency ratings (A to G) to guide consumer choices.
Relevance for road transport	Not applicable

Relevance for buildings

Focusing on the building systems such as lighting, heating, ventilation and cooling, energy labelling part of the regulation and directive for fuel using products: Heating, Cooling and Ventilation improving energy efficiency.

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